

**NEURO-SYMBOLIC MODEL FOR
REAL-TIME FORECASTING
PROBLEMS**

DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY

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DECLARATION

The research findings contained in this thesis resulted from my own work and investigation and they have not been concurrently submitted in candidature for the award of any other degree.

J. M. Corchado

2000

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ABSTRACT

The results of an investigation are presented into the development of a strategy for cooperative problem solving. The work focuses on the possible combinations of case-based reasoning and artificial neural networks and their integration. The results obtained demonstrate that for a particular type of problem, a case based reasoning system assisted by an artificial neural network, forming a hybrid artificial intelligence system, can provide a more effective problem solving capability than either of the methods by themselves.

In investigating its effectiveness in a practical real world situation, the approach is applied to a particular problem in the field of oceanography: the prediction of the structure of the temperature of the water ahead of an ongoing vessel in real time. The complexity of the application domain is due to the high activity of the oceanic water masses and to the diversity of their characteristics. A number of algorithms have been investigated in recent years, with the aim of providing a model capable of predicting the value of the ocean temperature several steps ahead of a thermal time series, but without producing sufficiently accurate results.

The hybrid model that has been developed integrates, in a single problem solving mechanism, cycles of an artificial neural network and case based reasoning processes. The hybrid forecasting model has been successfully tested on a cruise in real time, and the results obtained show that this model provided more accurate results than either the case-based reasoning model or the artificial neural networks by themselves. The hybrid model has demonstrated the potential for solving problems, in real time, in situations where it is difficult to define the rules that determine the behaviour of the parameters that may be forecasted.

The success of the system in generating effective forecasts may be attributed to the combination of an extensive database of past cases, supported by the neural adaptation mechanism which, each time around the forecasting cycle, enables the forecasting process to learn from all the selected closely matching cases.

The experimental results obtained are encouraging and indicate that the neural network supported approach is effective in the task of predicting future oceanographic parameter values. Extrapolating beyond these results, it is believed that the approach may be applicable to the problem of parametric forecasting in other complex domains using sampled time series data.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

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1.1 Aims

The research reported in this thesis focuses on the study of hybrid artificial intelligence (AI) systems. The aim is to investigate whether a combination of various problem solving mechanisms could result in the development of a model which might be applied to give more powerful computer based problem solving capabilities than may be obtained using purely algorithmic methods. In particular, the goal is to determine whether the combination of complementary connectionist algorithms, i.e. artificial neural networks (ANN) with symbolic models such as case-based reasoning systems, could result in a model capable of solving problems that neither of these techniques could adequately solve independently.

The research studies artificial intelligence forecasting techniques that are capable of adapting their structure to the changes in the environment in real time, so they can be used in problems for which it is not possible to build a permanent model. Forecasting in real time in this context means that it has to be done within a limited interval of time. In applying the proposed problem solving approach to a practical situation the work centres on the development of an oceanographic forecasting mechanism. Such a mechanism must provide successful results in complex real time problems for which

there is not a complete understanding of their dynamism and driving forces. Forecasting the future value of a variable can be extremely complex if the rules that define the behaviour of the system are unknown and a complete model can not be constructed for it. The difficulty of estimating the future value of a dynamic variable increases if the forecast is carried out in an environment that changes its characteristics spatially and temporally.

1.2 Background

The development of time series forecasting models has been carried out by various scientists (Weigend and Gershenfeld, 1995) using statistical and artificial intelligence based techniques. Over recent decades, several successful models have been built for different types of time series. Most of them are general models that need to be manually adapted for each particular situation. Although artificial neural networks have better abilities to overcome problems with multicollinearity (i.e. the independent variables that define a regression model are related among each other) and heteroscedasticity (i.e. the variance of the perturbations of a time series is not constant) than statistical models (Venugopal Baets, 1994), the majority of artificial neural networks have problems in generating steady successful results if the variables that characterise the problem change substantially over time in an unpredictable fashion.

The lack of solid and efficient models for forecasting dynamic systems (Rees *et al.*, 1991; Lees *et al.*, 1992) has motivated research into artificial intelligence models that facilitate the implementation of autonomous systems. These systems must forecast successfully in real time the evolution in the value of parameters that characterise a particular behaviour. These artificial intelligence models must be capable of adapting themselves to the dynamics of the environment in which they are immersed, and be capable of learning from their errors and generate confidence levels for their predictions.

1.3 Hypothesis

The hypothesis to be tested in this research is that:

- (i) *a hybrid model mainly composed of two different artificial intelligence methods is able to provide a system capable of forecasting the future variation in the parameter of a dynamic environment in real time,*
- (ii) *in particular, in such a complex environment where previous statistical methods or standard AI models have not been sufficiently successful, the combination of symbolic and connectionist methods may allow the successful prediction of the evolution of the system.*

1.4 Work carried out

The work, presented here, has been carried out in collaboration with the Plymouth Marine Laboratory (PML), which has provided financial and logistic support as well as data to carry out the investigation. The project has required the development and use of several computer based applications and the use of confidential, exclusive and sophisticated data sets. Most of the data sets have been obtained by oceanographic vessels and currently are stored in the Plymouth Marine Laboratory databases. Satellite images from the sea surface have been also used during the investigation. The Plymouth Marine Laboratory has also provided these images.

The Plymouth Marine Laboratory is one of the most advanced and sophisticated Oceanographic Laboratories of the world and the most important in Europe for its history, resources and quality of research. Therefore PML has been the ideal place to carry out the research and to contribute to the development of the application of artificial intelligence methods to a problem for which so far there has been no satisfactory solution.

Especially important have been the data recorded during the Atlantic Meridional Transect (AMT) cruises. Oceanographic research vessels carry these cruises out twice a year; they always follow a similar route from the UK to the Falkland Islands and vice versa. These cruises are an extremely good source of information because along their

track there is a high diversity of water masses that are representative of oceanographic water masses in general (Tomczak and Godfrey, 1994).

Standard artificial neural networks were used initially to forecast sea surface temperature. The results obtained with them were unsatisfactory due to the complexity of the data (Corchado *et al.*, 1995, 1996a, 1996b). Artificial neural networks were used, in the experiments, that could be trained fast (within a predefined time limit depending on how far ahead they had to predict) using a relatively small data set from the section of the thermal time series located just before the place from which the forecast was done. It was decided to research into a novel artificial neural network specialised in forecasting time series and that could be trained extremely fast. This decision was taken after studying preliminary results obtained with these methods. The chosen ANN was the *Finite Impulse Response* network (Corchado *et al.*, 1998c). Such ANNs have been proved more effective than any other ANN to forecast thermal time series. Nevertheless the results obtained with this network were not sufficiently accurate.

An ANN could provide extremely good results within a particular water mass if it were trained with adequate data sets extracted from such water mass. However an ANN trained in this form could not be considered as a universal forecasting mechanism because such a network can only be used within a particular water mass and during a particular season of the year. These experiments and the results obtained from them changed the direction of the research and new reasoning techniques were studied. At this point the aim was to identify a reasoning model capable of making use, in real time, of the historical information available in the form of thermal satellite images and historical time series of the sea water surface. A case-based reasoning (CBR) approach was investigated.

Case-based reasoning systems provide the means to:

- select the historical problems (and their solutions) that are most similar to a given one,
- adapt cases and their solutions to match a new situation,
- review a given solution,

- learn from their experiences.

The encouraging results obtained with the CBR systems showed that this reasoning model could be used to partially solve this problem. However it required the assistance of a technology capable of adapting to the new problem the retrieved cases. Methods of combining ANNs and CBR systems were investigated because:

- on the one hand a case-based reasoning system can be considered as a memory capable of retaining and recovering historical problems and of selecting from them those most similar to a new problem (refer to Chapter 3),
- on the other hand an artificial neural network can be considered as a memory capable of adapting and reusing the problems and solutions recovered by the case-based reasoning system (refer to Chapter 6).

1.5 Achievements

The investigation has focused in the study of artificial intelligence methods capable of forecasting dynamic time series with high heteroscedasticity. A universal forecasting mechanism to predict the evolution of such highly dynamic systems has been developed. The universal forecasting model is based on the combination of an artificial neural network and a case-based reasoning system. It is universal in the sense that:

- it has the ability to adapt, by itself, to the evolution of the variables that define the behaviour of the system that must be forecasted,
- the quality of the forecast obtained with it is consistent, regardless of the time and the location in which the prediction must be done,
- the system works in real time and without human intervention.

This hybrid model exhibits the beneficial properties of its components and eliminates the deficiencies with respect to the oceanographic forecasting problem. The combination of both techniques has allowed the implementation of an accurate universal oceanographic forecasting mechanism. The hybrid model has demonstrated the potential

for solving problems, in real time, in situations where it is difficult to define the rules that determine the behaviour of the parameters that may be forecast. The system can adapt itself to the variation in the water masses in real time. The approach has been applied to this problem with the aim of verifying the hypothesis of Section 1.3.

1.6 Structure of the thesis

The structure of the remainder of this thesis is as follows:

Chapters 2 to 5 present the problem to be solved and the techniques used to develop the hybrid system that is introduced in the later part of the thesis.

An introduction to relevant aspects of oceanography is presented in Chapter 2. This chapter outlines the problem to be solved and presents the data used in the experiments. The pioneer systems in the field of oceanographic forecasting are also presented together with the concepts relevant to this area. Finally the need for a system capable of forecasting the temperature of the surface of the oceans water is explained. Chapter 3 presents an introduction to the artificial neural network field. Four different subdivisions are given in this review corresponding to:

1. a general introduction to the field of the artificial neural networks,
2. an introduction to time series forecasting methods and the finite impulse response artificial neural network; the experiments carried out with this type of ANN in standard and oceanographic data sets are also presented,
3. an introduction to radial basis function ANNs and the results obtained with them in the problem under investigation,
4. a discussion of the results obtained with the ANNs presented in this chapter and a comparison of these results with the results obtained with statistical models.

Chapter 4 is a general introduction to case-based reasoning systems. Both Chapters 3 and 4 present the results obtained after applying the respective methods to the oceanographic problem.

Hybrid artificial intelligence systems are reviewed in Chapter 5. Although this chapter is a revision of artificial intelligent techniques, it also presents artificial intelligent models developed, improved or modified in the framework of this investigation, with the aim of obtaining a real time forecasting method to predict the temperature of the water.

The hybrid system that combines the case-based reasoning model and the radial basis function artificial neural network is presented in Chapter 6. Chapter 7 presents and discusses the results obtained with the hybrid system. These results are compared with the ones obtained with other AI techniques and those presented in previous chapters.

Chapter 8 presents the final conclusions and possible paths that may be followed in further investigation.

Four appendices have been included after the Bibliography:

- **Appendix A:** presents several pictures taken from satellites which show the temperature of the sea water surface. Two graphics that represent thermal vectors extracted from one of the satellite pictures are also shown.
- **Appendix B:** presents the architecture used to implement the system presented in Chapter 6.
- **Appendix C:** list of publications.
- **Appendix D:** glossary of technical terms used in the thesis.

Chapter 2

The Oceanographic Problem

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2.1 Introduction

This chapter describes, in depth, the oceanographic forecasting problem on which the research is focused. A brief introduction to the oceanography and the characterisation of the environment in which the hybrid forecasting system developed under this investigation is embedded, are presented. The Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods (Rees *et al.*, 1991), which can be considered the predecessors to the present system, are also outlined. The data used in these experiments is also presented in this chapter, together with some information related to the cruise in which the developed techniques have been tested.

Oceanography is a science that concentrates on the understanding of the physical principles that drive the oceans. This science uses the tools of mathematics and theoretical fluid dynamics to model the behaviour (Tomczak and Godfrey, 1994) of the

oceans. The analysis and interpretation of large volumes of oceanographic data has been traditionally accomplished through the use of statistical software tools. However their processing speed is limited by the need for frequent user intervention. With the aim of increasing the speed of processing such data, investigation into the adoption of knowledge based methods has been undertaken over the last decade (Lees *et al.*, 1992).

This research has investigated ways of using Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems, based on CBR, ANN or hybrid models for forecasting the evolution of parameters in complex environments. Developing general theories in this sense is complicated due to the individual and independent characteristics of each problem and environment even if they share the same general characteristics. Therefore the intention in the research was to develop a methodology to solve a particular problem and extrapolate from it a more general one.

Forecasting the thermal structure of the water ahead of an ongoing vessel in real time was seen as an interesting problem in which AI systems could be applied to obtain a successful methodology. The reasons that influenced the decision to work on this application were:

1. the Plymouth Marine Laboratory (PML), which is an institution with strong links with the University of Paisley (Lees *et al.*, 1992), had an application which was well suited to the application of the proposed hybrid AI approach,
2. data was available,
3. prior to this research, work had been carried out, in PML (in collaboration with the University of Paisley), in this field using several types of artificial intelligence techniques (Rees *et al.*, 1991; Rees and Aiken, 1995),
4. the problem required an intelligent system capable of dealing with the diversity of the ocean and the different characteristics of the oceans' water masses (Lees *et al.*, 1992),
5. several artificial intelligent methods had been used in individual water masses and the results obtained from the experiments carried out with those

methods suggested that further research in this field might lead to a universal forecasting method (Corchado, 1995).

The motivation comes from the oceanographers' need for knowledge of the ocean environment in which they are sampling. Whereas in the past oceanographers would accept shortcomings in the performance of, say, an acoustic detection system due to the vagaries of the ocean environment, now, as instrument measurements have become more sensitive and computers more powerful, it is imperative to know exactly what the environmental contribution is.

2.2 The oceanographic forecasting problem

The focus of this research is to investigate ways to forecast the thermal structure of the water ahead of an ongoing vessel in real time. Several researchers have been working in this field and obtained partial success (Rees *et al.*, 1991). Forecasting the structure of the water is a difficult task due to the nature and behaviour of the ocean waters. As will be explained in following sections, the movement of water masses makes the ocean's water temperature change in a complex manner (Tomczak and Godfrey, 1994). In order to obtain successful predictions, it is required to develop an autonomous universal methodology capable of forecasting changes in the temperature of the water as an expert oceanographer could do. This means that the system should be able to analyse, in real time, the evolution of the temperature of the water on a local basis, using the most relevant local knowledge available and to produce a wise judgement taking into account other factors such as geographical location and season of the year in which the forecast is done. Universal in this context means that the forecasting method should work anywhere in the ocean and at any time of the year.

When a problem such as the one presented in this paper is investigated, questions related to the quality of the final system performance arise: how far ahead should the forecast aim for? what must be the level of accuracy of the forecast? which data should be used to train the ANN or to generate the CBR cases?. All of these questions will be answered during the following chapters.

2.3 The Ocean water masses and their complexity

Oceans are dynamic habitats in which circulation is driven by three external influences: (i) wind stress, (ii) heating and cooling, and (iii) evaporation and precipitation - all of which are, in turn, driven by radiation from the sun. Other features that determine the ocean circulation are the sea surface temperature (in oceanography often called SST), the distribution of sea ice and the Coriolis force as a result of the earth's rotation (Palmen and Newton, 1969). The ocean circulation is what determines the mixture of water masses with different properties (such as temperature) and the variation of these properties with time in a particular geographical location. A water mass can be defined as a body of water with a common formation history. An example of water mass formation is the cooling of surface water near the Antarctic continent that increases the density and causes the water to sink to a great depth. All water that originates from these processes shares the same formation history and is called Antarctic Bottom Water. It moves well beyond its formation region, extending even into the Northern Hemisphere.

Oceans are in a continual state of flux (Tomczak and Godfrey, 1994). The scale of physical motion of the oceans and the atmosphere range from ocean wide through many intermediate sizes (hundreds or thousands of km) to finally the tiny eddies (in the range of 50 to 200 km). At the edge of fronts (boundary between water masses), at a lower scale, smaller features between 10 to 50 km in amplitude can be detected. Between 1 and 10 km local trends in the data set can be determined; movement of less than 1 km represent the noise of the system.

Traditionally, oceanographers have partitioned the oceans (Longhurst *et al.*, 1995) on the basis of:

- **physical characteristics:** topography, geostrophic flows, wind driven circulation, gyres, fronts, upwelling zones and patterns of seasonal stratification and
- **biological properties:** biological productivity, phytoplankton and zooplankton assemblages and community structure.

Taken together, this bio-physical partitioning provides the descriptors of regional ecosystems or biogeochemical provinces, each with discrete boundaries and each having distinct flora and fauna. In each of these provinces, the water properties are moderately homogenous and its variability can be described relatively easily.

The world's dynamic oceans systems have physical, biological and thermal characteristics that change seasonally and annually. The features of the ocean change regularly and their location can vary several degrees in latitude or longitude (where a degree corresponds to a linear distance of 100 km).

Our present knowledge of the ocean structure is still too weak to create a full model of its behaviour. Oceans are dynamic systems, in which the water masses are influenced by so many factors that it is extremely difficult to create even a partial model of the ocean. Therefore to develop a universal system for forecasting the temperature of the water ahead of an ongoing vessel is complicated.

2.4 Predecessor systems

Knowledge-based systems exist to assist in weather prediction (Lees *et al.*, 1991). However there appears to be little evidence of the application of a knowledge based approach as a means of predicting the location and movements of large water masses. Several scientists have been working in the Plymouth Marine Laboratory on the development of techniques for forecasting certain aspect of the ocean behaviour (Rees *et al.*, 1991; Corchado, 1995). Detecting these oceanographic features, their boundaries and being able to predict their evolution is the goal of the "*Knowledge Based Oceanographic System*" (KBOS) (Rees *et al.*, 1991; Lees *et al.*, 1992), its younger brothers the "*On line Real Time Knowledge Based Analysis*" (ORKA) system (Rees and Aiken, 1995) and the "*Simulated Tactical Environmental Bubble*" (STEB) system (Corchado *et al.*, 1997a, 1997b).

This section discusses several knowledge based systems currently used to forecast the thermal structure of the water ahead of an ongoing vessel; it explains their advantages and their weaknesses; it also presents climatological databases which are both a source

of information and reference for oceanographers and a useful element to assess the accuracy of any oceanographic forecasting system.

2.4.1 The KBOS/ORKA system

The KBOS system is a knowledge-based system, which gives a forewarning of impending frontal activity. It is capable of detecting oceanographic fronts in multi-parameter data sets captured *in situ*. Oceanographic fronts differ from the better known and better understood atmospheric fronts. Whilst both have similar motions and features such as eddies, atmospheric fronts are up to 30 times larger in volume than oceanographic fronts. Although oceanographic fronts are not as large as atmospheric ones, very powerful computational systems are needed to model the complex structural and positional changes experienced by oceanographic fronts. In the atmosphere, temperature and density fronts almost always coincide so that the frontal zones are highly baroclinic, with jet streams prominent at higher elevations (Palmen *et al.*, 1969). In the ocean, no unique relationship exists between the temperature and density fronts, due to salinity changes.

The Knowledge based system ORKA was built at the Plymouth Marine Laboratory (PML) in conjunction with Defence Research Agency (DRA) at Portland. This system has been adapted to work with real time data at sea and has undergone extensive testing under the name of ORKA.

2.4.1.1 Oceanographic fronts

Areas in which two water masses converge are called oceanographic fronts. At the fronts the characteristics of the water are extremely heterogeneous and are more variable. Provinces have their own general characteristics that can be described and simulated at a certain level. Oceanographic fronts are dynamic areas of intense biogeochemical activity associated with vertical exchanges in the water column (Tomczak and Godfrey, 1994).

Associated with most fronts is a frontal zone where turbulence or eddies in the water column can be observed, this is caused by jets of water spinning off from the front and mixing with the water of different type (Tomczak and Godfrey, 1994). In many ways, mesoscale (where the prefix 'meso' means intermediate) eddies are the oceanographic analogues of weather systems in the atmosphere. They travel a few kilometres per day and have rotary currents with speeds of the order 0.1 ms^{-1} . Eddies may move away from the front or eventually be 'entrained' back into the front, so whilst detection of an eddy structure is a good indication of frontal activity it does not guarantee it.

From the study of fronts and their associated frontal regions, it is clear that activity of some degree is always present in the coverage of a front (Uda, 1938). The physical parameters temperature and salinity change according to the nature of the jets and eddies in the region. Biological activity is also affected by the divergence of surface waters, with deep water rising to replace it; conversely, when there is a convergence of the surface water, sinking occurs. Fronts are found in every region of the oceans, in the surface as well as the subsurface layers, on scales varying from planetary to local, with many bound to topographic features (Huolbert, 1974).

The major fronts have been heavily sampled, by a variety of oceanographers using different instrumentation. This has led to a large data set for the frontal regions. Figures 2.1 and 2.2 show the temperature and salinity values across the Iceland-Faeroes Front from South to North. The front starts on 07/12:00, then stabilises for several hours before finishing at 07/21:00. The turbulence in the data South of the front is due to mixing between the two water types.

Figure 2.1: Temperature (°C) change across the Iceland - Faeroes front. Data recorded by a vessel crossing the oceanographic front from South to North at a speed of 10 knots. September 1995

Figure 2.2: Salinity change across the Iceland-Faeroes front. Data recorded by a vessel crossing the oceanographic front from South to North at a speed of 10 knots. September, 1995

2.4.1.2 The knowledge based system

The KBOS/ORKA forecasting systems are based on the analysis of the relationship between the temperature and the salinity in a given water mass. It has been established in the descriptive oceanography field that water masses of different geographical origin have characteristic salinity and temperature properties that can be used as unique identifications (Sverdrup, 1942). The quasi-unambiguous temperature-salinity relationship of specific water masses is the basis of this method of identification. It is known from published literature sources that Temperature-Salinity (T-S) relationships particularly for 'surface' waters (to 500m) generally fit linear relationships with no more than a small standard deviation or zone of uncertainty (Emery Meincke, 1986). For this analysis a simple parallelogram of T-S space is needed to envelop the main data, distributed around a basic straight line or curve.

When two or more water masses meet, a front occurs and a region develops which contains water that is a combination of the different water types. This water exhibits unique characteristics, and can be considered frontal water (Tomczak and Godfrey, 1994). In Figure 2.3 the points lying between the two water masses is frontal water as its characteristics belong neither to Atlantic or Arctic water (Hopkins, 1988). Data in this zone is regarded as being part of the front. Figure 2.3 also shows that this transitional (frontal) water is encountered when transiting from Atlantic water to Arctic water or vice versa. Knowledge based identification of the imminent boundary of any known water mass is used by the KBOS/ORKA systems as a forewarning of frontal activity.

ORKA is organised into two separate knowledge bases (KB): Historical KB and Temperature to Salinity (T-S) KB, meta-level production rules are used to combine and quantify to the user the output from the knowledge bases. The Historical KB holds information about the different provinces in the oceans, their limits and rules defining their changes with time together with information that determines each water mass' temperature and salinity characteristics. This system assumes that the ocean is in a stable state whilst the variation in the T-S properties of the data being read in are within a dynamically created mesoscale temperature and salinity core (T-S parallelogram). The

core represents a grouping of T-S values with water properties of the same type. When a point falls outside the current mesoscale core a flag is raised and the data set is analysed for the type of activity occurring. Analysis continues until a new stable state and T-S core is reached.

Figure 2.3. Temperature (°C) versus Salinity across the Iceland-Faeroes front

2.4.1.3 The interaction rules

By imposing the expected T-S relationships (derived from the historical rules) onto the data set (see Figure 2.3), the movement between cores is classified as either:

- forewarning of frontal activity,
- frontal activity, or
- mesoscale variation due to local noise

Production rules are used by the KBOS/ORKA system to determine the type of activity. An example of these rules is:

- **IF** *In frontal water* **AND** *T-S changing* \Rightarrow *Frontal activity*
- **IF** *At edge of a known water mass* **AND** *T-S moving* \Rightarrow *Forewarning of a front*

- IF *In known water mass AND No known front AND T-S moving* ⇒ *Mesoscale variation / possible forewarning*

An algorithm is used to convert the degree of change from the stable state to give a probability of the current activities strength. Typically a change in temperature greater than 0.5 degree centigrade or salinity of 0.1 is a strong indication of frontal activity. The current probability is not viewed in isolation from past probabilities of activity; it is combined with previous probabilities to give the total belief in the activity. This gives the user the overall probability of activity at this point. The forecast accuracy of these systems can be reduced by the possibility that the forewarning signals are of an order of magnitude lower than the local noise, which is found at the same levels. This is the main problem of this system and in this case belief or error limits are highly relevant.

2.4.1.4 Conclusions

The ORKA/KBOS systems are capable of detecting both frontal and forewarning features in a data set, both in real time from *in situ* measurements and in the laboratory from historical files.

These systems forecast changes and attach a probability of their accuracy to their outputs. The systems can predict changes but they cannot determine the degree (or slope) of the change, they cannot control the response-time, and they cannot forecast any relevant features within a water mass. These KB systems were never designed to do so, and were designed using a technology that only facilitates the detection of strong changes in the sea water masses. Although they cannot forecast the thermal structure of the water ahead of an ongoing vessel, they can detect boundaries between water masses and determine in which direction the temperature of the water water is going to change. These systems are the predecessors of the approach presented in this thesis which is based on a completely different AI technology.

2.4.2 Climatology Databases

The oceanographic climatologies are huge databases that hold pre-processed information related to the present and past state of the value of different relevant oceanographic variables such as: temperature, salinity, oxygen, etc. Oceanographic climatologies provide easy access to data that has been taken in situ, and that is essential to improve the understanding of ocean dynamics. Data has been accumulated for more than 100 years and especially during the last 40 years researchers have collected measurements of temperature, salinity, etc. extensively and accurately enough such as to be able to create global density fields. These data, which are normally stored in databases, also reside in condensed, analysed form as climatologies.

Climatologies (Lebitus, 1982) consist of data averaged over well-defined spatial grids and over time periods such as months, seasons or years. A broad distribution of the data in time and in space is best for the formulation of representative profiles in the construction of climatologies. Special interpolation techniques are used to ensure acceptable results. Accurate climatologies are particularly important for numerical model development and evaluation, for quality control of other data sets, for climate studies, and for the design of experiments. One of the most useful products derived from climatologies is the representation of data fields, on seasonal time scales, in atlas format. These atlases are extensively used by oceanographers and can be used to guide the forecast of parameters such as salinity, temperature, etc. Important atlases are the Robinson-Bauer atlases (Robinson *et al.*, 1979; Robinson, 1976), Worthington's North Atlantic atlas (Worthington and Wright, 1970), Levitus (1982) and the Generalised Digital Environmental Model (GDEM) (Davis *et al.*, 1986).

Levitus (1982) published the first worldwide climatology, "*The Climatological Atlas of the World Ocean*", basing it on objectively analysed, gridded sets of temperature, salinity and oxygen fields. The data presented in the Levitus Climatological Atlas were analysed on annual, seasonal and monthly time scales and were gridded in 1° (around 100 km in a straight line) latitude-longitude cells at standard oceanographic levels between the ocean surface and bottom (maximum depth 5500m). Values of variables

differ from climatology to climatology; nevertheless they provide a general value which can be taken as a reference in obtaining a forecast.

The STEB project (Corchado *et al.*, 1997a, 1997b) attempts to simulate in three dimensions the environment around a sea going vessel. Climatologies are a key element in the long distance prediction (more than 100 km in a straight line) of this knowledge system. The main problem of the climatologies is their broad spread or granularity; if an accurate prediction is required just a few km ahead of an ongoing vessel, interpolation of several values will be required and the accuracy of the forecast will be determined by the interpolation technique, the reliability of the climatology and the spread of the values used in the interpolation. In this situation a prediction may not be accurate. Also, because oceans are very dynamic environments, climatologies do not guarantee complete accuracy and reliability since they use historical knowledge to determine their values. And, as it will be shown in following chapters, ocean features change continuously and faster than the climatologies are updated.

Figure 2.4 shows how accurate a climatology can be. Any of the parameters that configure the climatologies such as temperature, salinity or oxygen can be inaccurate up to several degrees; nevertheless they show an accurate general trend. Figure 2.4b presents the values of the salinity recorded *in situ* during the AMT2 cruise (see section 2.5) (Robins, 1996) and the appropriate data from the Levitus climatology. Surface salinity values cannot be derived from space, but monthly climatological data are available (Levitus, 1982). The utility of climatological data maps have been explored by scientists such as Teague (1990), and their limitations are well known:

- smoothing will occur, especially in dynamic regions such as the Falkland Current and Brazil Current confluence (circa 38-46°S, 50-60°W), and in the complex current system of the equatorial zone,
- under-sampling in certain regions and seasons will lead to incomplete or inaccurate maps,
- the data set are spatially coarse, typically on a 1° grid, which corresponds to 100 Km.

Figure 2.4:(a) In situ measurements of temperature (solid line) with AVHRR (Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer) (dashed lines) data from satellite images. (b) In situ measurements of salinity (solid line) with Levitus Climatology (dashed lines) data. This data has been recorded during the AMT cruise by a research vessel from the UK to the Falkland Islands (Rees *et al.*, 1997a)

2.5 Data and AMT cruises

The analysis, design and implementation of a knowledge-based system requires domain knowledge, accurate data sets and the equipment to test it. Several data sets (from different sources) have been used to develop and to test the novel hybrid artificial intelligent based system presented in this thesis. The two major data sets are:

- Thermal data profiles, recorded by oceanographic research vessels and stored in huge databases in the Plymouth Marine Laboratory. Some oceanographic research vessels are provided with sensors that can record the value of the temperature, salinity, conductivity, etc. of the water at different rates (normally at 8 Hz). Those values are stored to be used in different experiments and projects. In the present research they have been used to

train an artificial neural network (ANN), to create cases in case-based reasoning (CBR) systems and to create statistical models, in all cases with the purpose of developing or improving forecasting systems.

- Satellite pictures (See Appendix A) are also an interesting source of information. Satellite technology makes it possible to receive daily sea surface temperature (SST) signals for the majority of the world oceans. From this type of coloured satellite pictures it is possible to extract data tracks in an automated fashion (See appendix A). The definition (or granularity) of these pictures is one km, therefore they can be used to train artificial neural networks, to create cases for case-based reasoning systems, etc. The satellite pictures used in the experiments presented in this thesis have been provided by the Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service (RSDAS) group, at the Plymouth Marine Laboratory, which provides processed satellite data received from the Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) project and the Sea-viewing Wide Field-of-view Sensor Project (SeaWiFS) at Dundee. Satellite images are supplied in a form that can be used without further processing.

Figure 2.4a shows how the along-track Sea Surface Temperature (SST) extracted from satellite images (AVHRR) and the *in-situ* recorded temperature, at 2 km resolution, are overlaid; there is very good agreement between the two data sets. The AVHRR data set offered approximately 70% coverage along the cruise track, with the discrepancies between 35°S and 45°S being ascribed to cloud coverage in the region; data were interpolated over the missing points. The AVHRR data have the required spatial and temporal resolutions and the required accuracy; unfortunately, coverage is adversely affected by clouds and cannot provide data at all points in space and time. For example, in Figure 2.4a it can be appreciated that in the tropics there is some doubt with regard to the accuracy of SST in the marine boundary layer, where low level water vapour may result in false data.

2.5.1 AMT cruises

Twice a year, the Royal Research Ship *James Clark Ross* (JCR) steams between the northern and southern hemispheres in support of British Antarctic Survey (BAS) research activities in the Antarctic and its environs. In September, the ship sails from Grimsby (England) to Stanley (Falkland Islands) with a logistics stop in Montevideo (Uruguay); the return trip takes place the following April.

The Plymouth Marine Laboratory (PML) has started a series of Atlantic Meridional Transect (AMT) cruises, whose primary objective is to investigate the large-scale physical and biological processes in the open ocean between 50°N and 50°S. The first AMT (AMT-1) cruise departed from Grimsby on 21 September 1995 and docked at Stanley on 24 October 1995 (Robins *et al.*, 1995); the return cruise, AMT-2 (Figure 2.5), left Stanley on 18 April 1996 and arrived in Plymouth (England) on 25 May 1996 (Robins R., 1996); since then there have been two AMT cruises every year.

The *James Clark Ross* has been provided with a number of sensors and sophisticated computerised systems that have permitted the implementation and testing of a number of artificial intelligence forecasting methods. Throughout the following chapters reference will be made to these cruises, the data recorded in them (Figure 2.6) and the experiments performed on board the *James Clark Ross*.

Figure 2.5: AMT-2 cruise track (solid line)

Figure 2.6: Temperature recorded during the AMT5 cruise, (September, 1997)

2.6 Summary and conclusions

This Chapter has been an introduction to oceanography. It has presented the problem under investigation in this thesis and the data available to solve it. Several knowledge-based systems developed in the Plymouth Marine Laboratory have been also presented. Those knowledge-based systems are the predecessors of the one presented in this thesis.

The initial study of the data suggested that although classical time series modelling strategies based on statistical or ANN models could be adequate to predict the changes in the temperature of the water, the complex dynamics of the water of the ocean may require the use of a more complex knowledge-based system capable of:

- organising and processing in real time such vast amounts of data,
- selecting and filtering the data according to the spatial and temporal characteristics of the problem, and
- adapting to the different water masses in real time.

A system with these capabilities must also be robust, reliable and autonomous. It is believed that an artificial intelligence based system, that combines the advantages of symbolic and connectionist models may provide a solution to this problem.

Chapter 3

Artificial Neural Networks

Chapter 3

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3.1 Introduction

The aim of this chapter is to present an overview of the field of artificial neural networks, with particular regard to those artificial neural networks (ANN) that have real-time adaptation capabilities and which:

- are specialised in knowledge generalisation, or
- have good abilities for real-time forecasting.

It is common to use time series techniques for forecasting problems. Artificial neural networks have been widely used to solve time series forecasting problems during the last decade (Weigend *et al.*, 1995). Although they have not always been successful the huge amount of research in this field suggested an investigation into the possibility of using ANNs to solve the oceanographic forecasting problem. The characteristics of the problem, previously mentioned in Chapter 2, were considered in selecting what might be an appropriate type of ANN. The artificial neural networks investigated were believed to be capable of adapting to different situations, learning fast and producing an answer in real time.

After reviewing several types of ANNs (Corchado *et al.*, 1998b, 1998c) it was decided to investigate the finite impulse response ANNs because their characteristics showed potential for predicting thermal time series in real time. This type of ANN is presented in this chapter.

After studying several ANNs for time series forecasting and analysing the results obtained, it was concluded that this technology could not solve the problem itself due to the high heteroscedasticity (i.e. the variance of the perturbations of a time series is not constant) and multicollinearity (i.e. the independent variables that define a regressive model are related among themselves) of the data. Nevertheless ANNs have shown some adequate and useful properties and features. Such properties could be used in combination with other technologies to solve the forecasting problem because the networks have extremely good generalisation and adaptation abilities as will be shown in following sections.

This Chapter presents a general overview of neuro-computing AI techniques and a classification of ANNs. It shows the present state of the art regarding the use of ANNs for forecasting and in particular, it focuses on a finite impulse response ANN specially

developed in the framework of this project for oceanographic forecasting. Also radial basis function ANNs are good at generalising, and have excellent adaptation capabilities (Fyfe, 1996). They have been found to be good forecasting mechanism (with excellent real time and adaptation capabilities). This type of ANN is analysed in this chapter.

A conceptual comparison between ANN and symbolic AI techniques is presented here. The results obtained with Radial Basis Function (RBF) and the Finite Impulse Response (FIR) ANNs are compared with the results obtained from a linear regression and an Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model.

3.2 Introduction to artificial neural networks

Artificial neural networks are relatively crude software or hardware models based on the basic principles that characterise the neural structure of the animal brain. The brain basically learns from experience. It is well known that some problems beyond the scope of current computers are indeed solvable by animal brains. Even simple animal brains are capable of functions that are currently impossible for computers, such as real-time identification of faces from different angles. However computers are able to do routine things well, such as keeping ledgers, handling masses of data or performing complex mathematics.

Research shows that brains store information as patterns (Haykin, 1994). And although some of these patterns are very complicated, humans have the ability to recognise individual faces from many different angles. The operation of an ANN encompasses the process of storing information as patterns and utilising those patterns in solving problems. ANNs do not use traditional rule based programming techniques; they use massively parallel networks which are trained to solve specific problems.

In using current ANNs the aim is to attempt to replicate in a very primitive way the most basic elements of human brains. The current goal of artificial neural networks is not the re-creation of the brain, rather ANN researchers are seeking an understanding of natural

capabilities for which people can engineer solutions to problems that have not been solved by traditional computing.

Although biological neural networks are constructed in a three-dimensional world from microscopic components and are capable of multiple interconnections, artificial neural networks are completely different; integrated circuits, using current technology, are two-dimensional devices with a limited number of layers for interconnection. This physical reality restricts the types, and scope, of artificial neural networks that can be implemented in silicon.

Figure 3.1: A Typical Neural Network

The most common type of ANN has the structure or topology shown in Figure 3.1. The diagram shows how some of the neurons (represented by circles) interact with the environment to receive the network's inputs and others provide the environment with the network's outputs. This output can be the particular element that the network has scanned or the particular number that it associates with the input values. The rest of the neurons are hidden from the environment.

An ANN is a group of neurons with a particular structure and with appropriate connections between them. The general elements that make up an ANN are

- neurons grouped into layers,
- connections between layers, and
- the summation and transfer functions of the neurons.

In most networks each neuron in a hidden layer receives signals from all of the neurons in the previous layer, typically an input layer. After a neuron performs its function it passes its output to all of the neurons in the following layer, providing a feedforward path to the output. The connections between neurons are weighted, and provide a variable strength to an input. There are two types of connections:

- connections that cause the summing mechanism of the next neuron to add,
- connections that cause it to subtract.

ANNs can be designed so neurons inhibit each other in the same layer. This is called lateral inhibition. This happens commonly in pattern recognition problems where neurons in the input layer inhibit each other, this is called competition.

Figure 3.2: ANN with Feedback and Competition

3.3 Classification of ANNs based on their learning mode

ANNs need to be trained before they can be used. This process starts with the assignment of initial values to the connection weights and to other learning parameters (as appropriate). The initial weights are chosen randomly. Then, the training regime, or learning, will adapt them.

There are two common learning approaches:

- **Supervised learning** requires the pairing of each input value with an output value (or target) and a teacher who controls the learning and provides error information. Thus, supervised training involves teaching the network to produce the desired output either:
 - (i) by manually "grading" the network's performance, or
 - (ii) by providing the desired outputs with the inputs
- **Unsupervised learning strategies** use only input vectors to the ANN training. The output is determined by the ANN during the course of training. Unsupervised methods construct internal models that capture structure in their input values without receiving any additional information or teaching.

3.3.1 Supervised training

In supervised training, both the inputs and the outputs are provided during the learning stage. The ANN then processes the inputs and compares their resulting outputs against the desired outputs. Errors are then back propagated through the ANN layers, causing the system to adjust the weights which control the network. The data used for the training is called the *training set*. During the training of an ANN the same set of data is processed many times and in each training step the weights are slightly modified. The training time is defined by how well the ANN converges to the right answer. The training process can range from seconds to weeks, stopping when the ANN reaches

some desired point, or accuracy. It also could happen that the ANN does not learn, because:

- the input data does not contain the specific information from which the desired output is derived, or
- there is not enough data to enable complete learning. Ideally, there should be enough data so that part of it can be held back as test data to monitor the learning curve of the ANN.

An ANN can memorise a data set. This is an undesirable ability that can be detected and avoided. Monitoring the learning of an ANN can be done by using a validation set (a subset of the training data set which has been held back and not used for the training) to check the learning, at periodical intervals, during the training time. To avoid memorisation, learning should stop as soon as the performance of the ANN deteriorates on this independent data set. Memorisation can also be avoided by not having too many processing elements.

The rules that guide training are also extremely important (Haykin, 1994). Different algorithms can be used to supervise the adaptive feedback required to adjust the weights during training. The most common technique is the back-propagation (Haykin, 1994) algorithm.

Training an ANN is a difficult task that requires a conscious analysis to ensure that the network is not over-trained. ANNs can learn about aspects of the data which may be hidden. Once the system is correctly trained, and no further learning is needed, the weights can be frozen.

Supervised learning ANNs have been used for zip-code recognition, time series prediction, rolling mill control, marketing, etc. The most frequently used ANN of this type is the multi-layer perceptron (using back-propagation) but there are other types, such as the RBF (Radial Basis Function) ANNs (Haykin, 1994) which have been used successfully in different applications. Extensive experiments have been performed with

these types of ANNs under the framework of this research (Corchado *et al.*, 1997a, 1997b, 1997c). These experiments have shown the potential of radial basis function ANNs for adaptation, fast learning and generalisation (especially for interpolating). This type of ANN forms part of the hybrid system presented in Chapter 6 and is analysed in the following sections.

So, to summarise, it may be said that:

- Supervised learning is applicable if in the training set the desired outputs are known.
- The strength of ANNs, that use supervised learning, lies in their capability to form efficient nonlinear models in high-dimensional input spaces.
- The multi-layer perceptron and the radial basis function ANN are the two most important exponents of this type of ANNs, that use supervised learning.

3.3.2 Unsupervised training

Networks using unsupervised training are only provided with input data. The system itself must then decide what features will be used to group the input data and then to generate the outputs. This is called self-organisation or adaptation. Then there are no target values (or supervision) nor feedback (or reinforcement).

Learning is possible by finding structures in the data such as features, correlations, clusters and redundancy. These ANNs are used to understand data sets, for dimensionality reduction, to pre-process data (filter data or re-package data in a more amenable form), to model the brain, etc.

There is a huge variety of learning models (Haykin, 1994) and architectures, which includes:

- SOM (Kohonen's Self-Organising Maps)
- Principal Components Analysis Models
- Hopfield and BAM (Bi-directional associative Memory)

- Learning Vector Quantization
- ART (Adaptive Resonance Theory)
- FIR (Finite Impulse Response).

The experiments performed with some of the ANNs discussed here have shown the potential of some of these systems to produce accurate real time forecasting.

In this respect special interest was taken in a FIR model initially investigated by Fyfe (1996) and adapted to the oceanographic forecasting problem.

3.4 General differences between ANNs and other AI systems

3.4.1 ANNs versus Expert Systems

ANNs solve problems by creating models from complete data sets. Traditional AI methods can solve problems which can be well defined, such as keeping ledgers, and keeping tabs of inventory, chess problems, etc (Luger *et al.*, 1989). Table 3.1 identifies the two basic differences between the two computing approaches (Anderson and McNeill, 1992).

CHARACTERISTICS	EXPERT SYSTEMS	ANN
Processing style Functions	Sequential Processing (left brained): via: rules, concepts, calculations	Parallel Processing (right brained): via: images, pictures, controls
Learning Method Applications	By rules (didactically): Accounting, word processing, math, inventory, digital communications, ...	By example (Socratically): Sensor processing, speech recognition, pattern recognition, text recognition, ...

Table 3.1: Basic differences between ANN and Expert systems

Typically, expert systems consist of two parts,

- an inference engine, which is generic and handles the user interface, external files, program access, and scheduling,

- a knowledge base that contains the information that is specific to a particular problem; this knowledge base allows an expert to define the rules which govern a process.

Expert systems have been found to be feasible only when applied to specific problems. There have been attempts to develop general knowledge-based systems but this increases substantially the complexity of such systems, which then demand too much computing resources and become too slow (Rome, 1992).

ANNs are aimed to provide a tool that both programs itself and learns on its own. They can seek patterns in data that no one knows are there. A more detailed comparison between Expert Systems and ANNs is presented in Table 3.2.

CHARACTERISTICS	EXPERT SYSTEMS	ANN
Processing Approach	Processes problem: one rule at a time; sequential.	Multiple, simultaneously.
Connections	Externally programmable.	Dynamically self programming.
Self learning	Only algorithmic parameters modified.	Continuously adaptable.
Fault tolerance	None without special processors.	Significant in the very nature of the interconnected neurons.
Neurobiology in design	None.	Moderate.
Programming	Through a rule-based system.	Self-programming; but network must be set up properly.
Ability to be fast	Requires large processors.	Requires multiple custom-built chips.

Table 3.2: Comparison between ANN and Expert Systems

Although expert systems have been very successful (Watson and Marir, 1994), they have encountered problems in areas such as vision, continuous speech recognition and synthesis, machine learning, etc. Traditional AI methods are very often restricted by the fact that experts don't always speak in rules.

Although ANNs have proved more successful than traditional (symbolic) AI approaches in specific problems, they are not the complete solutions (Haykin, 1994), and

- ANNs learn, but even so, it is not possible to demonstrate that they can provide an answer 100% correct, and
- when a network has been developed, there may be no way to ensure that the network is the optimal network.

ANNs are also very demanding and require:

- a good data set which includes the information characterising the problem,
- an adequately sized data set to train and test the network,
- an understanding of the basic nature of the problem to be solved so that basic decisions on the structure of the network can be made. These decisions include the activation and transfer functions, and the learning methods,
- adequate processing power (some applications demand real-time processing that exceeds what is available in the standard, sequential processing hardware).

If these conditions are met, ANNs offer the opportunity of solving problems that in many cases can not be solved by traditional AI. ANNs provide a unique way to solve some problems but also make demands. The biggest demand involves an empirical skill, an intuitive feel as to how a network might be created.

3.4.2 Fuzzy systems

Some neural networks are semantically poor (Haykin, 1994); there is almost nothing in the way of information you can name about the system under study in the neural networks - except a set of numbers. This is why they are so general. Expert systems on the other hand are semantically rich, but not general at all: they contain lots of explicit facts and rules which apply only to the domain for which they are crafted. Fuzzy expert systems tread a path between these two, having free parameters like ANN, yet having qualitative rules like expert systems. The parameters are used to quantify the degree of

application of the rule. The parameters may be learned from experience or determined by an expert.

Fuzzy expert systems, like certain kinds of neural networks, can be useful in situations where there is incomplete or ambiguous information. Fuzzy systems have been applied successfully in control applications, classification, and even in the form of hybrid systems with ANN. It is possible also to map certain ANNs such as RBF into Fuzzy sets and vice versa and in the same way extract knowledge from an ANN using Fuzzy set theories (Brown *et al.*, 1995).

3.5 Time series forecasting

ANNs are commonly used to predict what will most likely happen (Weigend and Gershenfeld, 1995). There are many applications where prediction can help in setting priorities or to avoid problems. When dealing with time series, the one step ahead forecasting problem based on experimental data is the problem of estimating the autoregression function of the underlying process. The aim of flexible forecasting systems is to minimise the output error, so the complexity of a model can be adjusted to the complexity of the training data. The multilayer perceptron, for example, possesses this ability (Canu *et al.*, 1997).

During the last decade the number of different methods used in forecasting problems has increased substantially (Weigend and Gershenfeld, 1995). Investigations into time series have three different goals:

- **Forecasting**, which aims to obtain an accurate prediction of the short term evolution of a system,
- **Modelling**, which seeks to find a description that accurately captures features of the long term evolution of a system and
- **Characterisation**, which attempts with little or no *a priori* knowledge to determine fundamental properties, such as the number of degrees of freedom of a system.

Weigend and Gershenfeld (1995) present in their book: "*Time Series Prediction: Forecasting the Future and Understanding the Past*", an excellent review of several time series forecasting methods, in which there are successful systems based on "Delay Coordinate Embedding", "Connectionist ANN", "Hidden Markov Models with Mixed Estates", "Visual Fitting and extrapolation". The particular interest in the current research is the development of a real-time adaptive ANN system for forecasting in complex environments. In addition, looking ahead to the development of a hybrid AI system for forecasting, which is developed in Chapter 6, interest is also in an ANN with good real-time, generalisation and adaptation capabilities, which may be applied to automate and simplify the adaptation process of a case-based reasoning forecasting mechanism.

The Finite Impulse Response algorithm (Wan, 1996) was one of the most successful models presented to the "*Santa Fe time series prediction competition*" (Weigend and Gershenfeld, 1995) and this fact, together with its real-time forecasting and adaptation characteristics was the motivation for investigating this method. The results of this research are presented in the following section.

The multi-layer perceptron has also been found to be a successful forecasting network (Canu *et al.*, 1997). However its training times are too high and therefore not suitable for this type of problem. Radial basis Function ANNs are also supervised learning systems with high adaptation capabilities and with much faster training times. These ANNs have been found to be successful as predictors and also as a good model to adapt cases (with high numerical-syntactical connotation) during the reuse phase of the CBR cycle.

Time series prediction (Fyfe, 1997) is based on the assumption that an observable feature of a system is determined by an underlying deterministic system. If the evolution of the system can be described by a set of n ordinary differential equations in n variables, there exists a unique trajectory through every point in R^n . In order to make a

prediction, knowledge of both the underlying rules of the deterministic system and the current state of the system is needed.

For example, consider a system in which a single scalar quantity, x_t , is observed which is the value of x at time t and which is determined by the state, \mathbf{a}_t , of the system at time t . Now if the underlying system is based on the n dimensional set of differential equations described above, then the state, \mathbf{a}_{t+1} , of the system at time $t+1$ can be described by the set of equations $\mathbf{a}_{t+1} = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{a}_t)$, while the state of the system at time $t+1$ is given by $x_{t+1} = g(\mathbf{a}_{t+1}) = g(\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{a}_t))$ (Fyfe, 1997). It can be shown that there exists a value d such that the vector $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_d)^T$ consisting of d consecutive observations of x , fully characterises the system. i.e. the evolution of the system may be absolutely specified using the function $F()$ or equally by using the function $H()$, where $x_{t+1} = H(\mathbf{x}_t) = H(x_t, x_{t-1}, \dots, x_{t-d+1})$.

Therefore merely by finding a sufficiently long set of consecutive observations of x (d is known as the embedding dimension of the system) a complete specification is obtained of the future observations of the system. It is well known, of course, that, for non-linear systems, the underlying dynamics are often such that there will be divergence of trajectories from nearby initial conditions. Thus, since observables may never be measured with infinite precision, predictions in such systems may only be of a finite length into the future.

3.5.1 Finite impulse response ANN

Figure 3.3 shows the architecture of the Finite Impulse Response (FIR) model (Fyfe, 1997). Input data is fed in from the left of the diagram and in successive time steps is passed onto the further neurons as shown. At time t , $y_i(t) = f_i(x_i)$, for $1 \leq i \leq n$, where n is the number of inputs to the network and the actual values of the inputs are a function of the observed time series.

Figure 3.3: Negative Feedback ANN with 3 embedded layers and 2 inputs

The feedback lines signify trainable connections; there are no self connections i.e. from a set of inputs to the equivalent y -neuron. The equations governing the activation transfer in the network are given by

$$y_i(t) = f(x_{i0}) - \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n \sum_{k=1}^d w_{ijk} f(x_{jk})$$

where $f(x_{jk})$ is the value of the j^{th} input at time $(t-k)$, and w_{ijk} is the weight from the i^{th} neuron to this input. The d parameter measures the length of the embedding dimension and n is the number of neurons in parallel in each embedded layer. Learning is done by simple Hebbian learning with momentum:

$$\Delta w_{ijk}(t) = M(\eta y_i f(x_{jk})) + (1 - M)\Delta w_{ijk}(t - 1)$$

where η is a learning rate which may be decreased during the course of the simulation, and M is a parameter which determines the magnitude of the momentum. The negative feedback in the network ensures that the network does not suffer from the usual Hebbian problem of weights growing without bound. Now since the expected value of $\Delta w_{ijk} = 0$ only when y_i and $f(x_{jk})$ are decorrelated, y_i and $f(x_{j0})$ must be decorrelated and then

y_i and $f(x_{j1})$ etc. and then similarly with respect to the time-delayed values of the other inputs.

At convergence then an approximation to independence between the neuron's outputs and the input data stream is obtained. To extract the value of the embedding function, $H()$, from the network's weights it is required to create a basis of the function space using predefined $f()$ functions. $f()$ can take different shapes going from simple polynomial functions to sinusoidal functions. For example, simple polynomial functions are used to model the Henon map (Haykin, 1994), presented in the next section.

$$\begin{aligned}y_1(t) &= f(x_{10}) = 1 \\y_2(t) &= f(x_{20}) = data(t) \\y_3(t) &= f(x_{30}) = (data(t))^2 \\y_4(t) &= f(x_{40}) = (data(t))^3 \\&\text{and so on.}\end{aligned}$$

Thus $f(x_{1k}) = 1, \forall k$

while $f(x_{2k}) = data(t - k), \forall k$ and

$f(x_{3k}) = (data(t - k))^2, \forall k$ etc.

When the residuals tend to zero, the mapping the Network has learned from the Network weights. In addition, if the Network is run with historical data, and no current input, the negative of the residuals is the forecast for the missing input.

3.5.1.1 The Henon map

This section presents the results of applying the FIR Model to the Henon Map. The Henon Map is an iterative map given by the equations $q_t = 1 - 1.4q_{t-1}^2 + 0.3q_{t-2}$ where the values of the parameters have been chosen to be close to those which give an exponential divergence from initially close starting points. This may in fact not be

chaotic since it has been shown by Robinson (1990) that nearby parameters give an infinity of periodic orbits with very small basins of attraction. However this still gives a difficult to predict function. Figure 3.4 shows 200 consecutive examples from the Henon Map.

Figure 3.4: Data from the Henon time series

All simulations reported herein were carried out over 1000 iterations and with a learning rate of 0.1 which is annealed to 0 during the simulation and a momentum parameter equal to 1 (i.e.: no momentum). The Henon Map is difficult to predict, although there is some structure in the data, as can be seen in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5: Mapping $x(t)$ against $x(t-1)$ for the Henon time series data

Figure 3.5 reveals that there is a relationship between q_t and q_{t+1} . There is only a certain set of possible values for q_{t+1} given q_t ; though there is not a mapping from q_t to q_{t+1} : there is not an unique value of q_{t+1} given q_t since there are more dependencies in the driving equation than a simple first order dependency. To extract the value of the embedding function, $H()$, from the network's weights, a basis of the function space is created using the following $f()$ functions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 y_1(t) &= f(x_{10}) = 1 \\
 y_2(t) &= f(x_{20}) = data(t) \\
 y_3(t) &= f(x_{30}) = (data(t))^2 \\
 y_4(t) &= f(x_{40}) = (data(t))^3
 \end{aligned}$$

and so on.

Thus $f(x_{0k}) = 1, \forall k$

while $f(x_{1k}) = data(t-k), \forall k$

and $f(x_{2k}) = (data(t-k))^2, \forall k$ etc.

The Henon map runs from a random initial value in the range $[0,1]$ and performs 2000 iterations of the mapping before collecting 1000 samples of the mapping which are the

selected data points. Using a 4-input function set $(1, \text{data}(t), (\text{data}(t))^2, (\text{data}(t))^3)$ the weights *into* the first neuron converged to the values shown in Table 3.3.

Time-Embeddings	Neurons - Inputs		
	2 = (data(t))	3 = (data(t)) ²	4 = (data(t)) ³
t	1.00	0.00	-0.01
t-1	0.01	1.39	0.00
t-2	-0.29	0.01	0.00

Table 3.3: Henon Map equation weight values

Now each neuron is attempting to turn the other neurons off. When looking at the output of the first neuron it is possible to see that the other neurons have been largely successful; its output is approximately zero for all inputs suggesting that the mapping has been captured. Recall that the above values of the weights are used as inhibition. Therefore since the initial activation of the first neuron is 1, its final value is

$$1 - 1.00x_t - 1.39x_{t-1}^2 + 0.29x_{t-2}.$$

The original equation can be approximately recovered by letting this equal to zero.

$$x_t = 1 - 1.39x_{t-1}^2 + 0.29x_{t-2}$$

which can be used to make subsequent predictions.

3.5.1.2 Inserting noise in the quadratic map

A quadratic map (Figure 3.6) can be created with the iteration

$$q_t = 1 - 4q_{t-1}(1 - q_{t-1}) + \gamma_t$$

where zero mean Gaussian noise of standard deviation 0.05 has been added to the map. Notice that since the noise appears in the iteration, it appears as coloured noise (noise which is dependent on the time) in the data sequence.

The same type of network was used with this data ($q_t = 1 - 4q_{t-1}(1 - q_{t-1}) + \gamma_t$) and again it was extremely simple to extract the underlying equations, which created the data. To illustrate the independence of the outputs, Figure 3.7 shows the residual at the first neuron and the noise at time t . The first residual output is extremely close to the noise though not exact since the actual noise in the data contains noise from previous iterations.

Figure 3.6: Mapping of x_t against x_{t+1} from the noisy logistic map

It is of interest though that the fact that the noise is *coloured* is essential to the accuracy of the above graph: if the Henon mapping is performed and then white Gaussian noise is added to the final values, the output of the first neuron does not accurately reflect the magnitude of the noise. I.e. by calculating $q_t = 1 - 1.4q_{t-1}^2 + 0.3q_{t-2}$ for all values of the

Henon map and then add noise to all calculated values by $q_t \leftarrow q_t + \gamma_t$, where γ_t is the noise at time t , the network's output after training is not an accurate reflection of the magnitude of the noise.

Thus this method can be used to estimate noise inherent in the data series (equivalent to modelling error) but not noise due to, for example, measurement inaccuracies. The underlying map, though, is recovered in both cases.

Figure 3.7: Graphing the residual output of the first neuron at time t against the Gaussian noise at time t . Notice that this last value does not take account of the fact that the noise is coloured because it is included in the iterative mapping

3.5.1.3 Maps with no constant term

Consider the noiseless logistic map $q_t = 4q_{t-1}(1 - q_{t-1})$, consecutive values from which are shown diagrammatically in Figure 3.8.

Figure 3.8: Mapping of consecutive values of the logistic map

Now this map has no constant term and the network cannot self-organise to make the first output equal to zero. In this case the weights into the *second* neuron converge to the values presented in Table 3.4.

Time- Embeddings	Neurons – Inputs	
	2 = (data(t))	3 = (data(t)) ²
t	0.0	0.0
t-1	-4.0	4.0

Table 3.4: Logistic map weight values

The results in Table 3.4 correspond to $q_t - 4q_{t-1}(1 - q_{t-1}) = 0_t$; i.e. the original mapping has been learned. It is for this reason that weights must feed not only into the constant term; weights into other neurons will also give information about the underlying structure of the mapping.

3.5.1.4 Finding the length of the embedding

If the embedding is too short, the magnitude of the residuals does not decrease to zero. This suggests that it is a good policy to start with a short embedding and increase the length till the magnitude of the output of the first neuron is zero. However there is a simple test to find if the embedding is too long. Table 3.5 shows the weights learned on the Henon mapping when the embedding is only a single time unit too long,

Neuron Input	2 (=data(t))	3 (=data(t)) ²
Time t	0.50	0.00
Time t-1	0.50	0.70
Time t-2	-0.15	0.70
Time t-3	-0.15	0.00

Table 3.5: Henon map weight values (for an embedding one unit too long)

The network is giving two equivalent mappings for the data.

$$1 - (0.5x_t - 0.7x_{t-1}^2 + 0.15x_{t-2}) - (0.5x_{t-1} - 0.7x_{t-2}^2 + 0.15x_{t-3})$$

For complex data sets, the optimal length of the embedding and the number of input neurons to the network can only be found empirically.

3.5.1.5 Forecasting using the FIR Network

The network was trained on 1000 samples of the noisy Henon series. The last data points were then moved through the embedding sequence in the same manner as used in the learning phase and the network's output at the first output neuron used as its estimate of the next value from the sequence. The results are shown in Figure 3.9.

Figure 3.9: Prediction of the Henon mapping using the trained network

Figure 3.9 compares the continuation of the Henon series without noise with the network's predictions. A noiseless Henon series is used for the comparison (though a noisy series is used during training) to estimate the accuracy of the network's mapping.

The method used to obtain these results is repeated one-step lookahead prediction: the results for time $(t+1)$ are used to predict the value of the observable at time $(t+2)$ etc. It should be emphasised that the network did not see the continuation data during training. The network uses the data structure that has been learned during training to forecast the future i.e. this is not a look-up table method.

3.5.2 Application of the FIR model to the oceanographic problem

The following sections show the results of using this ANN to forecast the data presented in Figure 2.6. The success of this type of ANN relies on the selection of the right bases for the function space. There are an infinite number of bases, which can be used in the network. The characteristics of the oceanographic data suggest that sinusoidal bases functions could be appropriate, and after several experiments with different functions, the best results were obtained using the following functions:

$$y_1(t) = x_t \text{ and}$$

$$y_n(t) = \sin((n-1) * x_t) \quad \forall n > 1$$

So

$$y_1(t) = x_{10} = data(t) \text{ and}$$

$$y_n(t) = x_n = \sin((n-1) * data(t)) \quad \forall n > 1$$

Thus $x_{1k} = data(t - k), \forall k$ and $x_{nk} = \sin((n-1) * data(t - k)) , \forall k$ and $\forall n > 1$

The methodology used can be summarised in the following points:

- A window of 500 km was used to train the ANN and then used to forecast the temperature at 5 km, 10 km, 15 km and 20 km ahead.
- This window was moved from the beginning of the data set to the end in 10 kilometre steps. Every time that the window was moved, the ANN was retrained and the forecast performed.
- Once the ANN was trained for a sufficient number of iterations of the 500 km data set, the value of the temperature 5 kilometres ahead was forecasted; this value was fed back and used to forecast the value of the temperature 10 km ahead, and so on until 20 km ahead.
- The final embedding of this ANN was empirically determined. For simple time series there is an automatic method to determine the embedding of this FIR model (Fyfe, 1996); nevertheless, for complex real life problems the simplest method is to study the characteristics of the data and to try several networks with different lengths of embedding and number of inputs and to select the one which produces smallest errors.

Figure 3.10: Temperature forecast using different number of embedding and input layers in the FIR ANN

Figure 3.10 illustrates this issue. It shows the temperature forecasts at a point 5 km ahead of two networks with different amount of embedding and input layers, and compares it with the real data set. The forecast of the FIR ANN (NN4*4) with an embedding length of 4 and 4 inputs is smoother and reacts more slowly to changes than the FIR ANN (NN10*8) with embedding length of 10 and an 8 dimensional input layer. The FIR 10*8 ANN overreacts to changes because it has too many degrees of freedom. This is an instance of the well known bias-variance trade off (Geman *et al.*, 1992). If the network has too many weights, it will tend to model the noise as well as the underlying structure of the data set. This increases the variance of the errors from such a network. If it has too few weights, it will not be powerful enough to model the structure of the data set. This increases the errors and the forecast will be perceived to have a bias.

Experiments with FIR ANN 4*4 :

An ANN with 4 layers of embedding ($d=4$) and 4 neurons in parallel (four input layers, $m=4$) was used. The value of the learning constant was 0.01 and the momentum value was 0.5. The ANN was trained for 10000 iterations of the 500km data set or until the average error in the training did not decrease by less than 0.0001 units over 600 iterations. Table 3.6 shows the average error and the standard deviation of the absolute value of the residuals for the forecast performed using a FIR 4*4 ANN.

Figure 3.11: Weights of the FIR 4 *4

<i>Distance Ahead (km)</i>	<i>Average Error of forecast temperature (°C)</i>	<i>Standard Deviation of forecast temperature (°C)</i>
5	0.099	0.180
10	0.206	0.305
15	0.343	0.402
20	0.468	0.526

Table 3.6: FIR ANN 4*4 Forecast Average Error and Standard Deviation

Looking at the weights of the ANN it is possible to extract the general model of the whole data set. As can be seen from Figure 3.11, the absolute value of the means of w_{11} (2.02), w_{12} (1.38), w_{21} (0.48) and w_{22} (0.38) are much higher than the absolute value of

the other weights which are below 0.15. From these results it could be easily concluded that the data set presented in Figure 2.6 can be modelled by a polynomial based on the functions $y_1(t) = data(t)$ and $y_1(t) = sin(data(t))$ for the two first levels of embedding. Nevertheless if only these functions are used the error of the forecast (for 5 km) increases by a factor of 2.3, therefore the other weights do perform significant functions.

Experiments with FIR ANN 8*5:

The aim of this particular experiment is to forecast the temperature ahead of an ongoing vessel, but what it is more important, to forecast thermal changes as soon as possible. Therefore a new experiment was conducted to improve the forecasting error in areas where the temperature changed considerably and the FIR 4*4 failed in the forecast. Selecting the number of embedding and input layers is a trade off between fast response to changes and smooth forecasts. Several experiments were done and the most successful results were obtained using an ANN with 8 embedded layers ($d=8$) and 5 neurons in parallel per layer ($m=5$). Again the learning rate was 0.01 and the momentum was 0.5. Figure 3.12 shows the errors in the forecast. The training method was exactly the same as the one used for the FIR 4*4.

<i>Distance Ahead (km)</i>	<i>Average Error of forecast temperature (°C)</i>	<i>Standard Deviation of forecast temperature (°C)</i>
5	0.096	0.215
10	0.192	0.367
15	0.324	0.428
20	0.435	0.561

Table 3.7: FIR ANN 8*5 Forecast Average Error and Standard Deviation

Table 3.7 shows the forecasting average error of the FIR 8*5 ANN. The average error in the forecast is slightly smaller using a FIR 8*5 ANN than with a FIR 4*4 ANN. The greater length (8 neurons) of the embedding helps to model the data more accurately.

The FIR 8*5 ANN reacts faster to changes, but tends to overreact to those changes in areas where the trajectory of the evolution of the temperature change substantially; this overreaction increases the standard deviation of the error. But, since the main aim is to detect changes as soon as possible, the ANN with an embedding length of 8 and 5 inputs is considered to be more accurate from a qualitative point of view for this time series.

Figure 3.12a: Absolute value of the error using a FIR 8*5 to forecast up to 5 km

Figure 3.12b: Absolute value of the error using a FIR 8*5 to forecast up to 10km

Figure 3.12c: Absolute value of the error using a FIR 8*5 to forecast up to 15 km

Figure 3.12d: Absolute value of the error using a FIR 8*5 to forecast up to 20 km

Comparing Figures 3.12 with Figure 2.6, it is observed that the higher errors in the forecast are exactly in areas where the temperature changes more. So the error in the forecast is directly related to the dimension of the change in temperature. This ANN can extract the general structure of the data set presented in Figure 2.6, but the accuracy of the forecast relies on the specificity of the data characteristics.

3.6 Radial Basis Function ANN

Although Radial Basis Function (RBF) ANNs can be graphically represented by a diagram similar to the one used to represent the well known multilayer perceptron (Figure 3.1), their supervised learning strategy is completely different (Haykin, 1994).

This section outlines the learning strategy of the RBF ANNs and compares it with the multilayer perceptron ANN (MLP). It also presents the results of applying the RBF ANN to the oceanographic forecasting problem.

3.6.1 RBF architecture

The input layer of a Radial Basis Function network is a receptor for the input data vectors. The hidden layer performs a non-linear transformation from the input space to the hidden layer space. The neurons of the hidden layer are the basis for the input data vectors. The output layer calculates a weighted linear combination of the output of the neurons of the hidden layer.

Gaussian functions are often used as a basis; their mean and standard deviation can be determined by the input data vector (as shown below). If $\phi(x)$ is the vector of the hidden neurons' outputs when the input pattern x is presented and if there are M hidden neurons, then

$$\phi(x) = (\phi_1(x), \phi_2(x), \dots, \phi_M(x))^T$$

$$\text{where } \phi_i(x) = \exp(-\lambda_i \|x - c_i\|^2)$$

where c_i are the centres of the Gaussians determined by input data vectors and $\|x - c_i\|$ is the Euclidean distance between the input and the i^{th} centre

The output of the ANN is calculated by:

$$y = w \phi(x) = w^T \phi(x)$$

where w represent the weights between the hidden neurons and the output neuron.

3.6.2 RBF learning

RBFs are universal approximators; the parameters that define the approximation process are:

- the weights between the basis functions, of the middle layer, and the output layer,

- the positions of the centres,
- the spread of the basis function and
- the number of basis functions.

Weights are normally adjusted using the Least Mean Square (LMS) algorithm, but can also be adjusted using other algorithms such as the Pseudoinverse method (Broomhead and Lowe, 1999).

The LMS algorithm can be summarised as (Haykin, 1994):

Initialisation:

$$w_{km}(1) = \text{small random number.} \quad \text{for } k = 1, 2, \dots, p; \text{ and } m = 1, 2, \dots, l$$

Filtering.

For time $t = 1, 2, \dots$, compute

$$y_m(t) = \sum_{j=1}^p w_{jm}(t)x_j(t)$$

$$e_m(t) = d_m(t) - y_m(t)$$

$$w_{km}(t+1) = w_{km}(t) + \eta e_m(t)x_{km}(t) \text{ for } k=1, 2, \dots, p \text{ and } m = 1, 2, \dots, l$$

where

p number of centres (or neurons in the middle layer)

l number of neurons in the output layer

$w_{km}(1)$ weights between the centres and the output neurons at time 1

$y_m(t)$ outputs of the neurons of the output layer

$x_j(t)$ outputs of the centres

$d_m(t)$ desired outputs of the neurons of the output layer

$e_m(t)$ errors in the neurons of the output layer

η learning constant

The centres can be selected in several different ways:

- **Random Selection of centres:**

Some vectors are chosen from the input space; if possible, we select them so that they spread evenly over the input vector space. This strategy is valid if it is assumed that the input data set is representative. In this case the Gaussian function used by the basis is chosen taking into consideration the spread of the centres. So, for example, if for the i^{th} basis function, the centre is c_i

$$\phi(x) = G(\|x - c_i\|) = \exp\left(-\frac{M}{d^2} \|x - c_i\|^2\right)$$

where M is the number of basis functions

d is the maximum distance between the chosen centres

- **Self organised centre Selection:**

The location of the centres can be moved at the same time as training the weights. One possibility for training this ANN is to use an unsupervised training method on the centres (while using supervised learning on the weights, i.e. Least Mean Square) (Moody and Darken, 1989). The centres of the radial basis functions are allocated in those regions of the input space where significant data is presented.

A k-nearest neighbour rule can be used for the self-organised selection of the hidden units' centres. This rule classifies an input vector x by assigning it the label most frequently represented among the k-nearest samples; a decision is made by examining the labels on the k-nearest neighbours and taking a vote (Duda and Hart, 1973).

- **Supervised centre Selection:**

In this approach a supervised learning algorithm controls the changes of the centres. It can be done using the error function shown before, with a generalisation of the LMS rule:

$$\Delta c_i = -\eta_2 \frac{\partial E}{\partial c_i}$$

This does not guarantee convergence because the cost of the function E is not convex with respect to the centres and so a local minimum is possible (Fyfe, 1996). The learning rate used to adjust the centres does not need to be the same as the one used to adjust the weights. Similarly it is possible to adapt the width of the Gaussian function to maximise the effect of the changes to the centres. RBFs in which all their parameters are modified using supervised learning algorithms have greater generalisation capabilities than others (Haykin, 1994).

3.6.3 Comparison between the MLP and the RBF

Both the Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) and the Radial Basis Function (RBF) ANN are universal approximators, i.e. can closely model continuous processes. RBF ANNs, in general, offer an interesting alternative to multi-layer perceptrons because of the following properties (Fyfe, 1996):

- In an MLP, generally, all the neurons calculate the logistic function of their weighted inputs. In a RBF, the neurons of the middle layer perform a non-linear mapping whereas the output layer is always linear.
- The non-linearity in the MLP is generally monotonic; while the RBF uses a radially decreasing function.
- The argument of the MLP neuron's function is the vector product of the input and the weights; in a RBF ANN, the argument is the distance between the input and the centre of the radial basis function, $\|x-w\|$.
- MLPs perform a global calculation whereas the RBFs find a sum of local outputs.
- MLPs are better at extrapolating and RBFs are better at interpolating (Fyfe, 1996).
- RBFs may require a high number of centres if accurate results are required.

- RBFs are less sensitive to the order in which data is presented to them than MLPs, because one data representation can affect the value of all the weights of the MLP network, whereas one basis function takes responsibility for one part of the input space.
- MLPs use back propagation of the error, which makes them slower to train than RBFs (which do not use back propagation).

3.6.4 Fritzke: Fast learning adaptive RBF model

Training a RBF ANN involves the placement of the centres in the areas of the highest density of the input vector space. This is often done by some clustering method. Then, the weights to the output units are determined by the accuracy of the output. The delta rule (Haykin, 1994) determines the value of the weights since there is only one layer of connections. The complexity of RBF depends on the difficulty in determining which centres to use and where to locate them. The architecture proposed by Fritzke (1994) automates this process and positions a number of centres very close to the minimum number that gives optimum performance.

3.6.4.1 Initialisation

Initially, two vectors are randomly chosen from the input data set, and used as centres in the middle layer. All the centres are associated with a Gaussian function. The width of the Gaussian for all the functions is set to the mean length of the Euclidean distance between each centre and the two centres closest to it. The rationale for this idea is to give each centre a receptive field in the input vector space that overlaps to some extent with those of its neighbours. This applies when there are at least three centres.

3.6.4.2 Centre and weight adaptation

After an input vector activates every Gaussian unit to some degree, these activations are propagated forward through the weighted connections to the output units which sum all incoming signals. The comparison of actual and desired output gives error information for this input pattern which is used by the Least Mean Square Rule (refer back to Section 3.6.2) to modify the value of the weights.

The closest centre to each particular input vector is moved toward it by a percentage α of the present distance between them. By using this technique the centres are positioned close to the highest densities of the input vector data set. The aim of this adaptation is to force the centres to be as close as possible to as many vectors from the input space as possible. An adaptation of this type is particularly important for high-dimensional inputs.

The delta rule (or Least Mean Square Rule) is used to adapt the weighted connections from the centres to the output neurons. In particular, for each presented pair of input and desired output vectors, one adaptation step, according to the delta rule, is made.

3.6.4.3 Insertion of a new centre

A new unit is inserted after a number of adaptation steps. A new centre is inserted when the error does not fall for a predefined number of iterations. The error assessment is done by calculating the average error for all the patterns used to train the network. If the error stops falling - for the current network size - it is because the delta rule and the centre adaptation are unable to improve the performance of the network. In order to determine the most distant centre P , the Euclidean distance (the square root of the sum of the squares of the difference between the co-ordinates of two points in the same space) between each centre and each input vector is calculated and the centre whose distance from the input data vectors is largest is chosen. A new centre is inserted in between P and the closest centre to it.

3.6.4.4 Termination of training

A maximum number of centres is defined in advance; however, the output error may be small enough to stop the learning process of the RBF without including the maximum number of centres. Training and insertion is continued until either the output error is smaller than a predefined value or the number of centres is equal to the maximum stated before the training starts. This criterion makes the size of the ANN often smaller than that of a RBF network produced by other methods.

3.6.5 Adaptation strategy

On the one hand, RBFs are sufficiently plastic to accommodate novel patterns and on the other hand the process of learning a new category does not necessarily need to undo or interfere with the representation of previously learned categories. Learning without forgetting can be achieved by keeping previously chosen centres and adding new ones close to the new input patterns. Afterwards, the weights can be easily adjusted with a small number of iterations of the training algorithms.

Adding centres continuously has several problems:

- the training time grows with the number of centres,
- the ANN will remember information that it does not need to remember,
- redundancy can appear in the list of centres.

These problems can be solved by deleting the centres which are not located near the training data set and are not relevant to the output. These centres can be gradually eliminated together with their weighted connections to maintain the ANN dimensionality of the ANN as small as possible.

3.6.6 Modelling a water mass with a RBF

RBF ANNs have been used to model the thermal structure of several water masses. Several temperature data profiles have been selected from the surface of homogeneous water masses. A representative number of them were selected to train the ANN and a second set was left for testing. The results vary from water mass to water mass: the more stable the region, the smaller is the error in the forecast. Experiments have been carried out on six different water masses of the Atlantic Ocean. In all cases data profiles have been obtained from satellite pictures (Refer to Appendix A):

- 200 profiles (water temperature) over a distance of 100 km have been selected for training the ANN.
- 50 profiles (water temperature) over a distance of 100 km have been selected for testing the ANN.

These ANNs have been designed to accept as input a codified temperature vector over a distance of 80 km and to provide as output four temperature values, representing the forecast at 5, 10, 15, 20 km. The optimum dimension for the vector used to carry out the regression (80 km in this case) has been chosen empirically using historical data sets.

Figure 3.13: Thermal profile

Table 3.8 shows the average error obtained in each of the water masses for the forecast. The results obtained with the MLP are very similar to the ones presented in Table 3.8; however the training times were between three to seven times higher.

Distance Ahead ⇒	Average forecasting error (°C)			
	5 km	10 km	15 km	20 km
Water Mass 1	0.025	0.062	0.131	0.213
Water Mass 2	0.021	0.071	0.151	0.197
Water Mass 3	0.032	0.077	0.118	0.176
Water Mass 4	0.036	0.061	0.146	0.230
Water Mass 5	0.054	0.096	0.162	0.258
Water Mass 6	0.037	0.087	0.153	0.263
Average Error	0.034	0.076	0.144	0.223

Table 3.8: RBF Forecasting error using in local water masses

These results show the excellent capabilities of the RBF ANNs for forecasting and modelling the temperature of local water masses. Nevertheless when an ANN is trained with data from one water mass and tested with data from a different water mass, the forecasting error is much higher; the tests performed in this way showed that the error increases between 18% and 321% depending on the water masses.

A forecasting system based on this technology, is appropriate only if it is confined to work in a particular water mass, well defined and in which the water has homogeneous properties. Since the aim is to develop a forecasting system capable of working anywhere in the ocean, it is obvious that this technology is very restrictive, because it requires the development of a different ANN for each water mass, and this is an almost impossible task to accomplish because:

- the oceans are very dynamic systems,
- the boundaries of the water masses change constantly,
- the properties of the water masses change seasonally.

3.6.7 Results using RBF for time series

Further experiments were carried out to overcome the limitations of the previous strategy. Several simulations have been performed using the Fast Learning RBF ANN (Corchado *et al*, 1997d) proposed by Fritzke (1994) on the data presented in Figure 2.6. This ANN has the capability of learning faster than a typical RBF ANN. A window of 500 km was used to train the ANN and then used to forecast the temperature at a distance of 5 km ahead. This window was moved from the beginning of the data set to the end in 2 km steps.

Every time that the window was moved, the ANN was retrained and the forecast performed. Once the ANN was trained for a sufficient number of iterations with the 500 km data set, the value of the temperature 5 kilometres ahead was forecast.

Figure 3.14.a: Absolute value of the error ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) using a RBF to forecast up to 5 km

Figure 3.14.b: Absolute value of the error ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) using a RBF to forecast up to 10 km

Figure 3.14.c: Absolute value of the error ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) using a RBF to forecast up to 15 km

Figure 3.14.d: Absolute value of the error ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) using a RBF to forecast up to 20 km

With the RBF ANN, the larger errors appear in areas where the water masses are in contact with each other and just after the fronts are crossed (refer to Figure 3.14). In this case, the ANN takes longer to readjust after crossing the fronts. The average error of the forecast and the standard deviation of this error is shown in Table 3.9. The forecast is very accurate in areas where the temperature changes in a continuous fashion. This ANN has the ability to learn without forgetting, adding new nodes in the middle layer allows learning new features without forgetting figures previously learned. The amount of centres or neurons that this ANN can hold in its middle layer needs to be limited because the higher the number of neurons, the higher the training time and also may model noise. Therefore the number of centres in the middle layer is a trade off between the forecasting error, the training time and the diversity of the training data set (the more features to map in the 500 km data set, the more centres are required). As new centres are added, redundant centres may be eliminated.

Table 3.9 shows that the average errors in the forecasts are slightly higher than the ones obtained with the FIR model. The standard deviation of the error is similar to the one obtained with the FIR 8*5 ANN. One of the reasons why the average error obtained with the FIR8*5 ANN is smaller than the error obtained with the RBF ANN is that the FIR ANN has better extrapolation capabilities.

<i>Distance Ahead (km)</i>	<i>Average Error of forecast temperature (°C)</i>	<i>Standard Deviation of forecast temperature (°C)</i>
5	0.114	0.210
10	0.226	0.338
15	0.351	0.435
20	0.469	0.574

Table 3.9: RBF Forecast Average Error and Standard Deviation

3.7 Forecasting using statistical methods

Although ANNs have their own rationale, they are heavily inspired by statistics and in many cases ANNs are just a different way of implementing statistical methods. Table 3.10 shows the terminological relationship between ANN and statistical methods that can be used to compare their similarities (Orr, 1996).

The main difficulty in using regression analysis is the requirement of prior knowledge of the functional form; in many cases researchers make the simplifying assumption of linearity in the data structure, which has the advantage that the model can be built more easily. Linear regressions have problems in detecting turning points. Besides this issue, several other methodological problems such as multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity are involved in regression analysis (Walpole *et al.*, 1989). Also conventional multiple regression analysis can only deal with one dependent variable at a time.

ANNs try to overcome the above-mentioned difficulties. ANN methods are non-parametric in the sense that functional forms do not need to be specified *a priori*. ANNs build their own model by “learning”, “testing” and “modifying” (Bishop, 1995). ANNs adapt their weights as new data becomes available, this adjusting depends on the characteristics of a changing environment, whereas a typical regression method is not adaptive but typically processes all data simultaneously. In ANNs, the activation of each neuron is a separate non-linear combination. Thus neural networks, being a collection of neurons, define complex relationships. ANNs can handle non-linear/chaotic high dimensional data series by deriving suitable maps between input and output pattern

spaces. Unlike regression equations, ANNs are extremely good at dealing with more than one dependent factor at a time.

STATISTICS	ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS
Model	network
Estimation	learning
Regression	supervised learning
Interpolation	generalisation
Observation	training set
Parameters	(synaptic) weights
Independent variables	inputs
Dependent variables	outputs

Table 3.10: Equivalent terms in statistics and ANN

The other interesting feature of ANNs is that if some of the data are missing, the ANNs can generalise across gaps by modelling and interpreting owing to their fault-tolerant nature. ANNs may perform well with incomplete data, which is more difficult for regressions. A single missing value in regression analysis may require that the entire observation or the variable be ignored. Both techniques have their advantages and disadvantages, and many researchers including De Croot and Wurtz (1991), Hruschka (1993), Weiss and Kulikoski (1991) have compared them in different domains.

For comparison purposes, two statistical forecasting techniques are used in the data set presented in Figure 2.6: a linear regression model and an ARIMA model.

3.7.1 Linear regression

Linear regression is a method that can be used for forecasting. This method was chosen for comparison because it is probably the most intuitive and simple forecasting method that can be used as a means of reference for any other forecasting tool.

In this experiment a prediction of the value of the temperature y at point x can be obtained using the vector of temperatures (dependent variable) recorded between the previous values x_{-1} and x_{-n} (independent variable), where n is the number of kilometres of data used to carry out the regression. The equation used for the forecast is $y=a+bx$, where:

$$a = \bar{Y} - b\bar{X}$$

and:

$$b = \frac{n\sum xy - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2}$$

This method has been used to calculate the value of the temperature at a point 5, 10, 15 and 20 km ahead. The optimum dimension, n , for the vector used to carry out the regression has been chosen empirically using historical data sets. Table 3.11 shows the average forecasting error obtained with the linear regression method.

<i>Distance ahead (km)</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Average Error of forecast temperature (°C)</i>	<i>Standard Deviation of forecast temperature (°C)</i>
5	10	0.174	0.349
10	25	0.275	0.523
15	30	0.429	0.671
20	30	0.529	0.807

Table 3.11: Linear Regression forecasting error and Standard Deviation

Detailed analysis of results show that the Linear Regression tends to react to changes a few km after the real change occurs. The average forecasting error produced by the Linear Regression is higher than the FIR 8*5 ANN and the RBF ANN. This late reaction to changes causes the value of the standard deviation of the error to increase substantially.

3.7.2 ARIMA model

Modelling and forecasting may involve knowledge or assumptions about the mathematical model of the processes. The Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) methodology was developed by Box and Jenkins (1976) and allows the modelling and forecasting of complex data sets. It has gained enormous popularity in many areas and research practice confirms its power and flexibility (Hoff, 1983; Pankratz, 1983; Vandaele, 1983).

ARIMA(p,d,q) is composed of two common processes, Autoregression (p) and Moving averages (q), which are adequate to model and forecast the time series that consist of elements that are serially related. The Autoregressive process requires a stationary data set, which can be obtained by differentiating the data (d). ARIMA estimates parameters so that the sum of squared residuals is minimised. The estimation process is performed, in this case, on transformed (differenced) data. Research has been carried out to investigate the most parsimonious ARIMA model for the data presented in Figure 2.6.

To use an ARIMA model on a particular problem, the model needs to be constructed using historical data related to the same problem. Building an ARIMA model for each oceanographic province is a huge and unrealistic task, because it will require the study in depth of each of the provinces. Therefore since it is not intended to build a real-time forecasting tool based on an ARIMA model, this model is only used as a comparison, in order to provide some idea of the accuracy of the methods studied in the framework of this project. The average error obtained from the ARIMA(1,1,0) model is shown in Table 3.12.

<i>Distance ahead (km)</i>	<i>Average Error of Forecast temperature (°C)</i>	<i>Standard Deviation of Forecast temperature (°C)</i>
5	0.129	0.243
10	0.231	0.366
15	0.372	0.451
20	0.471	0.563

Table 3.12: ARIMA(1,1,0) Forecasting Error and Standard Deviation

The average error obtained with this model is smaller than that obtained using linear regression. But the high heterocedasticity of this data series makes an accurate forecast using this model very difficult. The results presented in Table 3.12 have been obtained by creating a model for the data presented in Figure 2.6 and testing it on a similar data set recorded one year in advance by a cruise following the same trajectory.

3.8 Analysis of results

Table 3.13 compares the forecasting errors resulting from the application of several forecasting methods. Looking at Table 3.13 may be concluded that the FIR 8*5 ANN is on average the best time series forecasting system of the methods (including the statistical methods) presented in this chapter. The average error of the FIR 8*5 ANN is smaller than the average error of the FIR 4*4, and although the standard deviation of the error is higher in the first case, the quality of the forecast of the FIR 8*5 ANN is better because this model forecasts changes in the evolution of the water temperature before and more accurately than the FIR 4*4 ANN.

The errors obtained by the RBF ANNs are slightly higher than the one obtained using the FIR models. The RBF ANNs in general, are better at interpolating than at extrapolating and this type of data requires a system with good extrapolation

capabilities. The MLP has good extrapolation capabilities, but its slow training makes it impracticable in this particular problem.

<i>Distance ahead (km)</i>	<i>Average Forecasting Error (°C)</i>				
	<i>FIR4*4</i>	<i>FIR8*5</i>	<i>RBF</i>	<i>Linear Regression</i>	<i>ARIMA</i>
5	0.099	0.096	0.114	0.174	0.129
10	0.206	0.192	0.226	0.275	0.231
15	0.343	0.324	0.351	0.429	0.372
20	0.468	0.435	0.469	0.529	0.471

Table 3.13: Comparison of forecasting error with different forecasting systems

Both FIR models, as was expected, are better predictors than the linear regression technique. The advantage of the FIR ANN over the ARIMA model is that to build an ARIMA model it is necessary to know beforehand the type of the data and its structure, whereas the FIR model can adapt to changes. In all the methods the forecasting accuracy is reduced near frontal areas (refer to Figure 2.6): Iberian Front (around the 1750 km between UK and the Falkland Islands), the Azores Front (2600km), CWB Front (4200 Km), BZ Front (8500 km), Falkland Front (10000 km). None of the techniques are able to cope with these changes and they require some time to adapt to the new characteristics of the thermal structure of the water. Between 8500 km and the 10200 km points the behaviour of the water is very chaotic and it is reasonable to expect an increment in the error of the forecast. This part of the ocean is one of the most active and its temperatures are almost unpredictable.

The results of these experiments suggest that although the FIR model is the most accurate there is not a huge different between the error obtained with this system and any of the others. This seems to be the limit of the neural network based time series prediction algorithms. Nevertheless if the results obtained with the FIR 8*5 ANN are compared (see Table 3.14) with the results obtained by the RBF ANN in local

predictions (presented in Section 3.6.6), it appears that a more sophisticated system capable of selecting appropriate data, for the training of a RBF ANN in real time, might provide a more accurate forecast.

Distance Ahead (km)	Average Forecasting Error (°C)	
	<i>FIR8*5</i>	<i>RBF for local water masses</i>
5	0.096	0.034
10	0.192	0.076
15	0.324	0.144
20	0.435	0.223

Table 3.14: Forecasting error

3.9 Summary and conclusions

This chapter has presented an introduction to the field of Artificial Neural Networks. Artificial Neural Networks are exciting mathematical algorithms capable of learning, generalising and adapting. Special attention has been taken in the finite impulse response artificial neural network. Although the forecasts obtained with this network were more accurate than the results obtained with any other artificial neural network or statistical model for time series predictions, they were not sufficiently accurate for the purpose of the current investigation.

The aim of any forecasting model is to predict the value of a variable accurately. In this particular case an accurate forecasting model is one that provides a small average forecasting error and that does not indicate that the value of the variable is increasing when it is decreasing or *vice-versa*. The forecasting error depends on the characteristics of each water mass. In areas where there is not much variation in the properties of the water mass the forecasting error will be smaller than in areas where there are oceanographic fronts. This characteristic makes it very difficult to define thresholds for determining the accuracy of predictions based just on the average forecasting error. However oceanographers (Rees *et al.*, 1996) have determined a threshold for the number of inaccurate (or inadmissible) forecasts that indicates that the temperature of

the water is increasing when it is decreasing and *vice-versa*. This threshold should be always smaller than 10% for the prediction of the temperature at any distance. This maximum number of inadmissible forecasts allowed dictates also how far ahead a model can forecast. For example, according with this criteria, the FIR8*5 ANN can only be used to forecast up to 5 km ahead. Table 3.15 shows the percentage of inaccurate (or inadmissible) predictions obtained with this ANN.

Prediction Distance (km)	FIR8*5 Average error (°C)	FIR: % of inadmissible predictions
5	0.096	7.9
10	0.192	14.5
15	0.324	27.9
20	0.435	35.9

Table 3.15: Average error and percentage of inadmissible predictions using the FIR 8*5 ANN

Although RBF ANNs have not been capable of providing acceptable forecasts for this particular type of time series, they have been effective in forecasting the temperature of water masses at a local level (see Table 3.14). The percentage of inadmissible predictions using an RBF ANN to forecast local water masses is more than 50% smaller than the values obtained with the FIR8*5 ANN.

These results suggest that in order to improve substantially the forecast of a parameter as dynamic as the temperature of the water of the ocean, more information should be taken into account and a more sophisticated system is required. It is believed that an effective solution to complex problems, such as the one addressed in this thesis, which requires adaptive problem solving mechanisms, may best be achieved through the potential synergy obtained by employing a combination of connectionist and symbolic AI paradigms. The solution of this problem may require a system capable of selecting appropriate data, in any particular time and at any particular geographical location in order to extrapolate a useful conclusion (i.e. a forecast) from it. This system may use an RBF ANN trained with appropriated data, selected by a set of algorithms that take into consideration factors such as the time of the year and the location of the particular water masses in which the forecast is carried out.

Chapter 4

Case-Based Reasoning

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4.1 Introduction

The experiments carried out with ANNs have shown that they require assistance from a reasoning model able to select in real time their training data set. A case based reasoning system is a reasoning model that encapsulates the ability of storing representative problems, of recovering those problems and of adapting them to new situations. Learning is also an inherent ability of this reasoning system. Therefore CBR systems might overcome the limitations of artificial neural networks and reinforce their advantages. Case-based reasoning (CBR) systems were investigated with the aim of:

- developing a case-based reasoning system to forecast the temperature of the water in real time,
- establishing whether the case-based reasoning model could help artificial neural networks to predict more accurately.

This chapter introduces the field of case-based reasoning systems and reviews those CBR systems used in forecasting problems.

4.2 Introduction to Case-based reasoning systems

Knowledge-Based Systems (KBS) are one of the most popular and successful branches of the Artificial Intelligence (AI) world. According to Watson and Marir (1994) there are over 2000 KBS in commercial operation. Nevertheless, developers of these systems have met several problems: in many cases it can be difficult to deal with the knowledge elicitation part of a problem; the implementation of KBS is also complicated and once implemented, KBS are often slow and are unable to access or manage large volumes of knowledge and therefore they are normally difficult to maintain.

Kolodner (1983a) proposed a revolutionary model: the case-based reasoning model which is in fact a model of human reasoning (Joh, 1997). The idea behind CBR is that people rely on concrete previous experiences when solving new problems. This fact can be tested on any day to day problem by simple observation or even by psychological experimentation (Klein and Calderwood, 1988; Klein and Whitaker, 1988; Ross, 1989). Since the CBR model was first proposed, it has proved successful in a wide range of application areas (Kolodner, 1993).

A case-based reasoning system solves new problems by adapting solutions that were used to solve old problems (Riesbeck and Schank, 1989). The case base holds a number of problems with their corresponding solutions. Once a new problem arises, the solution to it is obtained by retrieving similar cases from the case base and studying the similarity between them. A CBR system is a dynamic system in which new problems are added to the case base, redundant ones are eliminated and others are created by combining existing ones.

4.3 General structure and phases of the CBR life cycle

CBR systems record past problem solving experiences and, by means of indexing algorithms, retrieve previously stored cases, along with their solutions, and match them

and adapt them to a given situation, to generate a solution. The intention of the CBR system is to abstract a solution from the knowledge stored in the case base in the form of cases. All of these actions are self-contained and can be represented by a cyclical sequence of processes in which human intervention may be needed. A case-based reasoning system can be used by itself or as part of another intelligent or conventional system. CBR systems are especially appropriate when the rules that define a knowledge domain are difficult to obtain or the number and the complexity of the rules affecting the problem are too large for the normal knowledge acquisition problem. This AI technology has been successfully used in disciplines such as law, medicine and other diagnostic systems with rich histories of cases (López de Mántaras *et al.*, 1997).

A typical CBR system is composed of four sequential steps which are recalled every time that a problem needs to be solved (Kolodner, 1994; Aamodt and Plaza, 1994; Watson, 1997). Figure 4.1 outline the CBR cycle.

Figure 4.1: CBR cycle (Aamodt and Plaza, 1994)

This cyclical process involves four major steps, represented by the highlighted words in Figure 4.1:

- **Retrieve** the most relevant case(s),
- **Reuse** the case(s) to attempt to solve the problem,
- **Revise** the proposed solution if necessary, and
- **Retain** the new solution as a part of a new case.

The mission of the retrieval algorithms is to search the case base and to select from it the most similar problems, together with their solutions, to the new problem. Cases should therefore represent, accurately, problems and their solutions. Once one or more cases are identified in the case base as being very similar to the new problem, they are selected for the solution of this particular problem. These cases are reused to generate a proposed solution (i.e. normally using an adaptation technique). This solution is revised (if possible) and finally the new case (the problem together with the obtained solution) is stored. Cases can also be deleted if they prove to be inaccurate; they can be merged together to create more generalised ones and they can be modified. For example, every time that an attempt to solve a problem fails, whenever possible, the reason for the failure is identified and logged in order to avoid the same mistake in the future. This is an effective way of learning that represents a general learning method used by humans (López de Mántaras and Plaza, 1997). CBR systems are able to utilise the specific knowledge of previously experienced problem situations rather than making associations along generalised relationships between problem descriptors and conclusions or relying on general knowledge of a problem domain such as rule-based reasoning systems. CBR is an incremental learning approach because every time that a problem is solved a new experience can be retained and made immediately available for future retrievals.

In the CBR cycle, there is normally human intervention (Watson, 1997). Case revision and retention are often undertaken by human experts. This can be a weakness of CBR systems and one of the major challenges of CBR research is to eliminate human

intervention. This thesis presents a method to automate the process of case adaptation in problems of a numeric nature.

4.3.1 Case Retrieval

The goal of the retrieval step is to find in the case base (the memory of the CBR systems) the best match to the present problem descriptor; the best match can involve one or more cases. This major task can be divided into the following sub-steps: identify features, initial match, search, and select, normally carried out in that order (Aamodt and Plaza, 1994).

- **Identification:** determines a set of features that characterise a problem.
- **Initial Match:** searches in the memory of the CBR system and selects the cases that are significantly similar to the present problem descriptor using for example a predefined set of rules and thresholds.
- **Search and Selection:** determines (from the initial selection carried out in the previous sub-step) the best match or the set of best matches in which we start looking for the final solution.

Although CBR is a well-defined problem solving methodology, the nature of the problems determines the ultimate structure of each CBR system. For example, before implementing the retrieval algorithm it is necessary to identify whether cases must be retrieved taking into consideration their syntactic similarity or their semantic similarity (Aamodt and Plaza, 1994). In this respect, there are two approaches:

- *Knowledge poor approach:* in which systems retrieve cases based on the syntactical similarities between problem descriptors. Examples of these systems are: CYRUS (Kolodner, 1983), ARC (Plaza and López de Mántaras, 1990), and PATDEX-1 (Richter, 1991) (Refer to Chapter 6).
- *Knowledge intensive approach:* in which systems retrieve cases based on the semantic similarities between problem descriptors. Examples of these systems are PROTOS (Bareiss, 1988), CASEY (Koton, 1989), CREEK

(Aamodt, 1989) and MMA (Plaza, 1993). This second approach requires an extensive general domain model so that it can be proved that a strong match exists between cases (Aha *et al.*, 1991).

Another important issue to take into account before implementing the retrieval strategy is whether or not the retrieved cases are going to be adapted during the reuse phase. This factor may be very useful in identifying the appropriate retrieval algorithm, the number of cases to retrieve, etc.

The identification of a problem can be done by simply noting its feature descriptors. However in knowledge-intensive methods a more sophisticated mechanism which involves the understanding of the problem within its context is often required.

The identification of the closest match is normally done in two steps:

1. **Initial matching:** Identifying sets of cases which match relatively well the present problem; the problem descriptors are used for this comparison.
2. **Final Match:** Selecting the best match among the previously selected ones.

In some systems it is necessary that all features match the problem case features, but in other systems only a total match in some features may be required. In some situations it is necessary to weight the problem descriptors according to their relevance for characterising a problem during the learning phase. If the problem is more knowledge intensive and if it is necessary to understand the problem more deeply, an analysis of the problem constrains, goals, motivations, etc., may be required.

The best match is chosen by studying the initial selection of cases more closely. This can be done in different ways depending on the characteristics of the problems. For example in problems with high semantic connotations, it can be achieved by generating explanations of non-accurate matches using domain knowledge. This process may be more complex than the initial selection and in many cases requires human intervention.

4.3.2 Case Reuse

The differences and similarities between the case or cases selected (as the best matches) in the previous step and the problem case are considered in the reuse phase. During this step, an assessment is made as to whether it is possible to transfer features of the retrieved case(s) to the new case.

In simple classification problems, the differences are hidden and only the similarities are considered relevant features; in these situations the problem case adopts the solution of the retrieved case. But in the majority of the systems, when differences are important, case adaptation is required.

There are two different ways to reuse (or adapt) past cases (Allemange, 1994):

1. **Transformational reuse:** which consists of reusing past solutions. The retrieved case solution is not the solution adopted for the new problem, rather there is a transformation function that generates the new problem solution from the past case solution.
2. **Derivational reuse:** which consists of reusing the past method that constructed the solution. In this approach, the retrieved case must contain information about the method used for solving the retrieved problem, including a justification of the operations used, their subgoals, alternatives generated, failed search paths, etc. Derivational reuse reruns the retrieved method with the new case details and replays the old plan into the new context (general problem solving systems could be used here as planning systems).

4.3.3 Case Revision

In this phase the proposed solution is analysed to assess its accuracy. The proposed solution (generated in the previous phase) is evaluated, and if the solution is successful, the CBR can learn from it as will be shown in the next phase (case retention); if the solution is not successful it can be repaired using domain specific knowledge.

Evaluating a solution is normally done by applying the solution to a real word problem. Under some circumstances, the solution can be evaluated using a simulation. If the proposed solution needs to be repaired, it is necessary to identify the errors in the solution and to generate an explanation for them, using for example explanation based techniques (Kristian, 1989). The solution is repaired if the errors can be identified using failure explanation, so that the errors do not appear again.

4.3.4 Case Retention

During this step, it is determined what can be learned and retained from a problem solving episode. The learning algorithm must take into account the outcome of the previous phase of the CBR cycle. The main sub-tasks of this step are:

1. selecting which information must be retained,
2. establishing how this information must be saved,
3. establishing how to index the new problem solving episode (case) for future retrievals,
4. determining how to integrate the new case in the memory structure.

To formulate, modify or eliminate a case it is necessary to consider the problem descriptor and the problem solution.

CBR systems are dynamic systems in which the case base must be updated continuously. For example:

- if a case is reused and adapted to generate a new solution, the case may be generalised and part of the new case may be absorbed, or a completely new case may be created,
- if the solution needs user intervention, normally an entire new case is constructed.

Indexing is a feature of CBR systems that influences the learning phase substantially. When a case is retained it is important to define where and how it may be indexed; in

this operation the indexing structure is crucial. The indexing problem will be discussed in Section 4.5.

The final step in this phase is to update the case base successfully. The index for a particular case may be adjusted depending on the success in reusing this case. In knowledge-intensive approaches, learning can take place within the general conceptual knowledge model, through interaction with the user or even by another machine learning method.

4.4 Case Representation

A case represents a well structured problem, semantically and syntactically. A case contains past experiences and information about the context in which it was involved (Kolodner, 1993). A typical case is composed of:

- a **problem** that shows the state of the world at a particular time,
- a **solution** given to that particular problem,
- an **outcome** that describes the state of the world after the solution is applied.

Cases describing problems and their solutions are used to generate solutions for new, similar problems (Koton, 1989). Cases comprising problems and outcomes can be used to evaluate new solutions. Cases can be used to evaluate the outcome of possible solutions if they contain problems, solutions and outcomes (Simpson, 1985). Cases can be represented in different ways, depending on the problem under investigation and the algorithms used in each step of the CBR cycle. So cases can be represented with objects, frames, predicates, semantic nets, rules, etc. Ideally the information represented in the cases must be functional, easy to understand and easy to retrieve and interpret.

4.5 Case Indexing

Case indexing can be done deterministically in some CBR systems (Kolodner, 1993). The indexes used in CBR systems should be predictive, concrete enough to recognise a feature, flexible enough so they can be adapted if changes are necessary and be adequate

for the problems in which they are used. Although there are automatic indexing algorithms, it is believed by the majority of the research community (Kolodner 1993; Watson, 1997) that in practical applications the indexing strategy must be chosen manually. Watson (1994) proposes a classification for automatic indexing methods:

- Indexing cases by features and dimensions that tend to be predictive across the entire domain. The important features of a problem are selected after analysing the problem domain. These features are sorted (using a predefined criteria) and the cases are indexed by their values along these dimensions. Examples of systems that use this type of indexing strategy are Mediator and Chef (Kolodner, 1993).
- Difference-based Indexing focuses on the selection of indices that differentiate one case from the others. The characteristics that differentiate cases are shortened and used as indexes. Cyrus (Kolodner, 1983a, 1983b) is a CBR with this type of indexing strategy.
- Similarity and explanation-based generation methods cluster the cases, grouping together those with similar characteristics in generalised cases. Then indices to those abstract cases are generated and the unshared features are used as indices to the original cases (Hammond, 1989).
- Inductive learning methods (Goodman, 1989) identify predictive features that are then used as indices. These techniques use variations of the ID3 algorithm used for rule induction.
- Explanation-based techniques analyse each case and determine which of their features are predictive. These predictive features are used to index cases (Simoudis *et al.*, 1992).

4.6 Case-based reasoning methods

This section presents a classification of different models of CBR systems (Aamodt and Plaza, 1994). Although they all share similar features, each of them is more appropriate for a particular type of problem (Aha, 1997). Some CBR systems do not require all the phases of a typical CBR system, and some require human intervention. The

classification presented bellow has been taken from Aamodt and Plaza (1994) and is the most representative of the present state of the art.

- **Exemplar-based reasoning**

In the literature there are different views of concept definition (Smith and Medin, 1981). A concept is defined extensionally as the set of its examples. Those CBR systems that focus on the learning of concept definitions are normally referred to as being exemplar-based. PROTOS (Porter and Bareiss, 1986) is an example of this type of CBR systems. In this case, solving a problem requires finding the right class for an unclassified exemplar. The class solution of the most similar retrieved case is the problem case solution.

- **Instance-based reasoning**

An instance-based reasoning can be considered as an exemplar-based reasoning that is useful in highly syntactic problem (Aamodt and Plaza, 1994). This type of CBR system focuses on problems in which there are a large number of instances which are needed to represent the whole range of the domain and where there is a lack of general background knowledge. The case representation can be made with feature vectors and the phases of the CBR cycle are normally automated as much as possible, eliminating human intervention. Aha and Kibler (1991) have worked with this type of CBR system.

- **Memory-based reasoning**

The memory of this type of CBR system is a collection of cases and reasoning is the process of accessing appropriate cases from this (normally large) memory (Kasif *et al.*, 1998). These systems use parallel processing techniques and work with both problems having highly syntactic connotations (Stanfill and Waltz, 1988) and also with problems with highly semantic connotations. Examples of this last type are PARADYME (Kolodner, 1988) and the work done by Kitano on massive parallel memories (Kitano, 1993).

- **Analogy-based reasoning**

Analogy-based reasoning is the name given to those CBR systems that attempt to solve new problems using past cases from different subject domains, and in contrast with other case-based methods, focus on indexing and matching strategies for multiple-domain cases (Veloso and Carbonell, 1993). This term is also used to define techniques that investigate mechanisms for identification and utilization of cross-domain analogies (Kedar-Cabelli, 1988; Hall, 1989). In this sense the work of these researchers has focussed on the reuse phase, and on the development of techniques for mapping problems, i.e. on transferring the solution from the retrieved cases to the new problem domain.

- **Case-based reasoning**

Case-based reasoning is normally used to name all the above methods. In particular:

1. a typical case should have a number of distinctive and relevant features, and its internal structure is normally fairly complex,
2. a typical CBR system must be capable of adapting a retrieved solution in different problem solving contexts,
3. a typical CBR system requires background knowledge - although the type of knowledge and the way the CBR uses this knowledge may vary from case to case,
4. many typical CBR algorithms have been inspired by cognitive psychology theories.

4.7 The memory model

The structure and organisation of the case memory of a case-based reasoning system is particularly important during the retrieval phase, especially in real-time systems in which the retrieval time of the cases should be fast. A good structure and organisation of the case memory may make a CBR mechanism very efficient. There are several ways to organise the memory; the two most influential ones are the dynamic memory model of

Schank and Kolodner (1993) and the category-exemplar model of Porter and Bareiss (1986).

- **Dynamic memory model:**

In this model, the memory is organised in a hierarchical structure. This approach requires a relatively complex and rigid network structure which is hard to alter when adding new cases to the CBR memory. For example in Cyrus (Schank, 1982) cases which share similar properties are grouped under a more general structure, called a generalised episode, composed of norms (features common to all cases), cases (cases under an episode) and indices (features which discriminate between cases).

- **Category and exemplar model:**

This approach requires a large memory when the number of cases becomes large. Porter and Bareis (1986) refer to a case as an exemplar. In this model, each feature of a case is assigned a different value and every attempt to generalise a group of cases must be done very carefully. The memory is a network of categories, semantic relations, cases and indices. Each case is associated with a category. An index may point to a case or a category. Indices can be:

1. feature links pointing from problem descriptors or features to cases or categories,
2. case links pointing from categories to their associated cases,
3. difference links pointing from cases to neighbour cases that only differ in one or a small number of features.

4.8 CBR and forecasting

Several researchers (Nakhaeizadeh, 1994; Lendaris and Fraser, 1994) have used *k*-nearest-neighbour algorithms for time series predictions (Hanney *et al.*, 1995; Hanney and Keane, 1997). Although a *k*-nearest-neighbour algorithm does not constitute a CBR

system, it may be regarded as a very basic and limited form of CBR in numerical domains.

While Nakhaeizadeh (1994) uses a relatively complex system, Lendaris and Fraser (1994) forecast a data set just by searching in a given sequence for segments that nearly match the pattern of the last n measurements (where n is a positive integer) and then by supposing that similar antecedent segments are likely to be followed by similar consequent segments.

Table 4.1 presents a compilation of CBR systems that have been proposed during the past decade and which have proved successful. The table shows a number of systems that either use case-based reasoning mechanisms or which have been highly influenced by this method of reasoning. The authors of the majority of the models presented in the table claim that their systems provide better results than other methods used for the same problems. The CBR systems forecast a wide range of parameters such as sales, design costs, pollution levels, ventilation therapies, fires evolution and epidemic risks.

All the models presented in the table use flat memories with simple data representation structures. Inspection of the table reveals that the majority of the CBR systems use *k-nearest neighbour* metrics in their reuse phase (Hanney *et al.*, 1995; Hanney and Keane, 1997). The use of *k-nearest neighbour* algorithms requires a study of the problem in depth in order to define accurate comparison rules and thresholds. The cases are represented by feature vectors in most of the models. The representation of cases in this form facilitates the comparison between them, especially if they hold quantitative or numerical information. *K-nearest neighbour* metrics are acceptable if the system is relatively stable and well understood. But if the system is dynamic and the forecast is required in real time, it may not be possible to easily redefine the *k-nearest neighbour* metrics adequately.

The fourth column in Table 5.1 shows the dominant characteristic of the adaptation stage used by each different model. The systems use similarity metrics or statistical

models; in some systems, case adaptation is accomplished manually. If the problem is very complex, there may be no planned adaptation strategy and the most similar case is used directly, but it is believed that adequate adaptation is one of the keys to a successful CBR paradigm.

(System)/ Author(s)	Application field	Case Retrieval	Adaptation	Revision	Indexing/ Learning	Distinctive characteristic
CBP Model Klein & Whitaker 1988	Administrative planning, Analogue reasoning					computer-based planning; comparison based prediction
CORAL I Martin 1989	general model	Conditional probabilities used to select the most representative variables of the cases				retrieve cases by k-nearest neighbour
McIntyre Achabal, & Miller 1993	Forecasting sales	k-nearest neighbour	adaptation using similarity metrics	manually by a human expert	manually by a human expert	combine recovered cases.
Stoffler 1994	prediction of design cost of buildings	rule based system and human expert.	rule based system and human expert.	Rule based system and human expert.	rule based system and human expert.	the system only guide the expert
AIRQUAP Lekka, Aronis & Viras 1994	prediction of atmospheric pollution	comparison metrics.	two different heuristics	human expert supervision.	new cases are stored without modification	prediction requires expert supervision
VIE-VENT Miksch <i>et al.</i> 1995	Therapy planning for artificially ventilated new- born infants	comparison metrics.	data abstraction using different metrics	manual abstraction by human expert	cases are created automatically from row data	real time forecast
REBECAS Ronggetez 1993	Modelling the behaviour of fires	comparison of feature vectors	none	none	cases are based on fire histories	real time forecast
Bull, Kundr & Gierl 1997	Forecasting of health risks and epidemics	heuristics and comparison metrics	statistical models	revision of forecasting error	forecasting error used to review cases	forecast requires human supervision
Corchado <i>et al.</i> 1997	Forecasting the water temperature ahead of an ongoing vessel	comparison metrics	averaging cases features	revision of the forecasting error, use of error limits	cases are created automatically	real time forecast

Table 4.1: Review of CBR systems used in forecasting problems

Case revision (if carried out at all) is performed by human experts in the majority of the forecasting systems surveyed. The forecasting error is used to improve the metrics used in the previous stages of the CBR cycle. Such modification constitutes what might be considered to be the learning aspect of the CBR process.

The models presented in Table 4.1 are summarised as follows:

- **CBP: Comparison Based Prediction Model**

The CBP model (Klein and Whitaker, 1988) can not be considered a true CBR system because it does not include any of the four stages that characterise the CBR cycle. It has been included in this classification because it is based on the same theoretical foundation as CBR systems. This system uses a methodology based on analogical reasoning and the author recommends its application in planning problems. CBP has been designed to assist experts and its use increases the success rate of typical planning methods by 30%.

- **CORAL_L**

Martin (1989) presents a system capable of selecting and recovering past problems and solutions. However, it is not a CBR *per se*. CORAL_L employs the use of conditional probabilities that automate the selection of the variables that are the most relevant at the time of selecting cases. The model maintains conditional probabilities between pairs of related variables. If relationships do not provide successful results they are removed and new ones are defined.

- **Mcintyre *et al.***

Mcintyre *et al.* (1993) shows how a typical CBR can be successfully used to forecast sales of products. They have proposed a model that requires human intervention throughout the reasoning process. The CBR system advises experts on which cases to reuse and leaves the case adaptation to these experts.

- **Stottler**

Stottler (1994) uses a CBR approach to estimate the design costs of buildings. The author discusses the benefits of supervising the reasoning process of the CBR by experts. He also points out the advantages and disadvantages of this methodology in forecasting problems.

- **AIRQUAP**

Lekkas *et al.* (1994) have developed a case-based reasoning system to forecast atmospheric pollution levels in the city of Athens. The forecast is made in real time and requires the supervision of an expert. Cases are created automatically from data recorded by sensors in this reasoning model. Cases are created from unprocessed incoming data.

- **VIE-VENT**

Vie-Vent (Miksch *et al.*, 1995) uses a CBR approach for planning the ventilation therapy for new-born infants. It is a real time system that uses comparison metrics for the recovery of previous cases. The recovered cases are generalised and adapted using a further set of metrics. The solutions given by Vie-Vent need to be reviewed by experts. Cases are generated automatically from data sampled from patients. The system only retrieves items of information that could be more useful in the present case.

- **REBECAS**

Rougegrez (1993) has developed a CBR system for real time forecasting. The aim is to predict the temporal and spatial evolution of fires. The cases are created from fire histories collected by firemen from each fire. The system has been developed to assist firemen and requires the supervision of experts.

- **Bull *et al.***

Bull *et al.* (1997) have developed a system for identifying health risks, for forecasting the temporal and spatial spread of epidemics and for estimating the consequences of an epidemic. As in several of the above models, this system also requires the supervision of an expert. Statistical methods are used for the adaptation of cases that have been previously recovered using comparison metrics and heuristics. The adaptation of cases is improved by taking into account prediction errors.

4.8.1 A CBR system for oceanographic forecasting

A similar algorithm to that proposed by Lendaris and Fraser (1994) has been implemented at the Plymouth Marine Laboratory (Rees *et al.*, 1996). This section presents an overview of the CBR system created for forecasting the temperature in real-time.

The water temperature of the world's oceans changes on a temporal and spatial basis, as discussed in the second chapter of this thesis. The strategy was to record the temperature of the water, in real time, and to store temperature values in the memory of the CBR system. For every km sailed by the vessel a new case was created, composed of the water temperature values recorded during the last 35 km and averaged every km. Then a case x is composed of a feature vector of 35 temperature values, in which the first 30 values are the problem descriptor, p_x , and the last 5 values s_x , are the solution (or forecast).

$$p_x = (t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{30})$$

$$s_x = (t_{31}, t_{32}, \dots, t_{35})$$

Two vectors of 30 and 5 km were chosen after running several simulations, using different values on a representative (3000 km) data set recorded in the Bay Biscay in 1995. Using this basic memory model several strategies were tested for retrieval, adaptation, review and learning, which are discussed and analysed in the following

pages. For retrieval, the initial idea was to search in the case base for the case x whose problem descriptor, p_x , was the most similar to the problem descriptor, p_y , for the situation requiring a forecast. For the comparison, a simple nearest neighbour approach that compares the corresponding values of each vector p_x with p_y was used to compare the cases. In this initial system there was no adaptation and the output of the system was s_x . This initial system was modified in the Plymouth Marine Laboratory to improve the accuracy of its output.

- **Improvement in the Retrieval phase**

A new nearest neighbour approach was adopted in the current research based on the comparison, CGx , between the gradients, G_{px} , of the feature vector, p_x , of each, x , case of the case base and the gradient, G_{py} , of the problem feature vector, p_y . The vectors, s_x , of the three cases for which the CGx is smallest were retrieved.

$$\text{where } CGx = |G_{px} - G_{py}|$$

$$G_p = \sum_{i=1}^{30} (t_{30} - t_i)$$

- **Improvement in the Reuse (and adaptation) phase**

The average of the three vectors s_x retrieved is calculated and used as the forecast for the problem case.

- **Improvement in the Revision phase**

Error limits determine the final forecast. When the vessel follows a straight line, if the present system is forecasting a temperature value, F , up to 5 km ahead of the vessel, it takes exactly 5 km to find out the difference between the forecast value, F , and the real value, T . The error limits interval, CL , is calculated by averaging the absolute value, AL , of the last three computed forecasting errors (three was found to be the number that provided smaller errors in a representative data set). Then, CL , is an interval centred on the crisp (i.e. precisely defined) forecasting value F ,

$$\text{where } CL = [F-AL, F+AL]$$

- **Improvement in the Learning and case memory updating**

Experiments on this system have shown that a large case base does not necessarily improve the system performance, and also under some circumstances it may significantly reduce the accuracy of the system. A large case-base may even increase the forecasting error up to 50%, particularly if no cases are deleted from the case base. The case-base must include only representative cases; quality in this sense is more important than quantity.

After experimenting with this initial system on the Bay of Biscay it was decided to maintain in the case base only the cases recorded during the last 400 km, and therefore only keeping in the case-base the most recently created cases. This threshold was found to be adequate for this particular water mass (Bay of Biscay), but it may need to be changed for water masses with different characteristics. Tests on different water masses, have shown, in this respect, that an adequate value for this threshold is normally between 300 and 600 km.

Figure 4.2: Prediction of the temperature of the water 5 km ahead of an ongoing vessel using the CBR

Figure 4.2 shows an example of the forecast obtained with this system; the stars represent the prediction 5 km ahead of a point and the line represents the actual data set. The system is more accurate when there is a clear trend in the data set, and is more inaccurate at turning points. The average error of the forecast 5 km ahead when tested in the data set presented in Figure 2.6 is 0.12 °C; however the system becomes increasingly inaccurate when it tries to predict beyond this distance, and has the additional drawback of being unable to predict the patterns of change in the ocean.

Although the error limits absorb most of the forecasting error, the forecast lies outside the error limits in 27% of the predictions. The average error outside the error limits is 0.033 °C and the average value of the error interval is 0.098 °C.

The use of error limits can mislead the prediction on occasions in which the forecasting error (proposed solution) increases substantially and especially if there is a strong change in the thermal variation of the water. The confidence interval tends to be large in these situations. For example, error limits above 0.5 °C are meaningless because the water temperature very rarely changes more than 0.5°C in 5 km.

This initial CBR approach for forecasting has shown potential. The forecasting error was of the same order as that using other AI techniques such as neural networks (Corchado *et al.*, 1997) or statistical methods (Corchado *et al.*, 1997). The CBR system was able to capture information and produce reasonable forecasts with some data sets. It was believed that this AI methodology could be used for solving the forecasting problem, but that it needs to be assisted by more sophisticated and adequate mechanisms in each of the phases of the CBR cycle.

Improvements to this system could be:

- **In the retrieval phase:**
 - Define more accurate metrics to obtain a better case selection.
- **In the reuse phase:**

- Improve substantially the adaptation mechanism by using a technique (such as ANN) that might enable the system to adapt to the changes in the water characteristics and that could automate this phase.
- **In the revision phase:**
 - Refine the error limits strategy, using more appropriate knowledge.
- **In the retain phase:**
 - Select carefully the number and quality of the cases that must be retained in the memory of the CBR system. Define pruning rules and case refinement strategies.

To carry out all of these changes it was necessary to redesign the system completely and to include new algorithms to improve each of the phases of the CBR cycle, using more features to describe the cases. This first CBR system was the first step toward the development of the hybrid system presented later in this thesis. The improvements to this early system constitute the core of this thesis and are presented in Chapter 6.

4.9 Summary and conclusions

This chapter has introduced the general concepts related to case-based reasoning, which is one of the most interesting and active areas of symbolic artificial intelligence. Several case-based reasoning systems developed to solve forecasting problems have also been reviewed and special attention has been directed to a simple CBR system developed for forecasting ocean water temperature in real-time. Although this initial CBR system presented in Section 4.8 was not successful, the experiments carried out with it suggested that it might be used with extensions, as the basis of a system that might facilitate the organisation and selection of the vast amount of data to create a universal forecasting mechanism.

The CBR systems reviewed have shown their ability to solve the forecasting problems for which they were designed. Some of them are only frameworks that facilitate the manual retrieval, adaptation and revision of cases, by experts; other have incorporated in

them algorithms that automate some of the phases of the CBR cycle. The biggest advantage of CBR systems is that they are flexible reasoning frameworks that may facilitate the indexing, storage, retrieval and adaptation of cases.

The results obtained using the methods presented in Chapters 3 and 4 suggest that the use ANNs, statistical models and CBR systems are individually insufficient to solve adequately the problem under investigation. A solution to this difficulty requires the use of selected and condensed information, relative to the areas of the ocean in which the forecast is carried out. This information can be used by an RBF ANN to generate a forecast as explained in Section 3.6.6. The CBR mechanism could provide the framework to assist the ANN in the data storage and selection process.

Eliminating the human intervention in a CBR is difficult (as shown in the revised system) and this is one of the constraints of the problem under investigation. This constraint can be eliminated, Chapter 6 presents a CBR system that uses an RBF ANN to support the process of case adaptation so as fully automate the forecasting of the temperature of the water in real-time.

Chapter 5

Hybrid CBR-ANN Systems

Chapter 5

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5.1 Introduction

The experiments carried out and presented in the previous chapters suggest that a hybrid model composed of a CBR system and an ANN could be the solution to the forecasting problem under investigation. Both technologies have their advantages and disadvantages, and as explained in previous chapters each of them are oriented towards the solution of different problems. This chapter discusses the beneficial properties of hybrid systems in general and hybrid systems composed of CBR systems and ANN in particular.

This chapter reviews the field of hybrid artificial intelligence systems in general, placing special emphasis on the study of hybrid systems that combine artificial neural networks and case-based reasoning systems. The last section focuses on CBR-ANN systems developed to solve forecasting problems.

The term *hybrid* refers to systems that consist of one or more integrated subsystems, each of which can have a different representation language and inference technique. The subsystems are assumed to be tied together semantically and influence each other in some way. The goal of hybrid system research includes the development of techniques to increase the efficiency and reasoning power of intelligent systems. For example, some of the work developed with the aim of increasing efficiency makes use of specialised reasoners strategically called by control or supervisor modules that decide which reasoning method to use at different times (Medsker, 1995). Hybrid systems are capable of addressing some practical problems that have been addressed with traditional artificial intelligence approaches. From a fundamental perspective, hybrid systems may also give further insight into cognitive mechanisms and models (Medsker, 1995).

Many researchers are investigating the integration of different AI approaches (Sun, 1997). The issues under study range from fundamental questions about the nature of cognition and theories of computation to practical problems related to implementation techniques. There are many different directions in this research and several models for integration have been identified.

5.2 Models of integration

Several international conferences and forums have been held during the last decade to promote discussion in the integration of AI methods (Sun and Alexandre, 1997). This section summarises the three main models of integration of AI techniques that characterise the trends in the research in this area.

5.2.1 Computational intelligent classification

Bezdek (1994) proposes a framework for thinking about the real goals of research and development in intelligent systems. The model focuses on different levels of integrated activities, systems, and AI technologies. Bezdek defines three levels of increasing complexity, from computational to artificial tasks and then to biological activities. Figure 5.1 shows the components of the model going from neural components to pattern recognition capabilities, to finally intelligent activities. The diagram shows how a neural

function is part of a pattern recognition mechanism and that this forms part of the intelligence. The model shows how artificial intelligent components are built on symbolic modules that add relatively small pieces of knowledge to computational processes and data, in order to get closer to biological intelligence.

The model also shows the different types of inputs to each of the intelligence modules:

- *Computational Intelligence* uses numeric data coming from sensors
- *Artificial Intelligence* requires fragments of knowledge and data recorded by sensors
- *Biological Intelligence* uses human knowledge and data from sensory inputs

Figure 5.1: Bezdek's model (1994)

Artificial systems augment computational systems with rules and other non-numeric fragment. The role of various intelligent technologies can be viewed in this framework, in which:

- **at the bottom level, the computational neural components can be**
 - feedforward networks,
 - self-organising feature maps,
 - any other biologically inspired models such as genetic algorithms, etc.
- **at the middle layer there can be**
 - knowledge based systems,
 - case-based reasoning, etc.

This model does not consider computational and artificial intelligence systems “*intelligent*” by themselves and for Bezdek words such as learning must be very carefully used when applied to low levels of complexity. This is a general classification in which hybrid systems are ways to extend the low level computational intelligence techniques through the artificial intelligence level toward the goal of modelling biological intelligence.

5.2.2 IRIS Classification

Soucek (1991) developed the Integration of Reasoning, Informing and Serving (IRIS) model. This is an architecture that facilitates the combination of software, hardware and system levels present in any intelligent system. The aim of this methodology is to facilitate the design of systems using more efficient technologies, products and services to meet business needs. For Soucek, the development of a hybrid system requires the integration of different scientific disciplines including biology, cognitive psychology, linguistics, epistemology, and computer science.

The IRIS model identifies the need of ten ingredients of integration:

- mixing of technologies (ANN, CBR, Knowledge-based systems, etc.),
- paradigms for integration,

- standard software modules,
- special languages,
- software development tools and environments,
- automated discovery such as interactive intelligent databases and interfaces,
- standard control and automation modules,
- case studies of working applications,
- concurrency - tools for developing and monitoring,
- signal to symbol transformations and pattern to category mappings.

Figure 5.2: IRIS architecture (Soucer, 1991)

Figure 5.3: IRIS Levels of integration (Soucer, 1991)

The IRIS architecture is shown in Figure 5.2 and the levels of integration are shown in Figure 5.3. Looking at Figure 5.3 it can be observed that integration goes from the top to the bottom. Current research has achieved some success up to the cognition level and more progress is starting to be made toward the highest level of conscience. This is not just a classification that describes mechanisms of interaction between AI models. It shows how AI models can be integrated within other computer technologies to create successful knowledge-based systems.

5.2.3 A third classification

Medsker and Bailey (1992) have defined five models of integration from a practical point of view: stand-alone models, transformational, loose coupling, tight coupling and full integration. This classification presents several ways of combining connectionist and symbolic models. The integration between models can be done depending on the problem to be solved and the data and knowledge available. Figure 5.4 describes graphically the relationship between the modules of each model.

Figure 5.4: Models for integrating intelligent systems, KBS represents a symbolic system and NN represents a connectionist one (Medsker and Bailey, 1992)

Stand-Alone model

This model combines intelligent system applications consisting of independent software components. The components do not interact in any way.

This type of hybrid is characterised by the following:

- it provides the means of comparing the problem solving capabilities of the two techniques for a specific application,
- one model may provide verification of the other,
- the use of two techniques in parallel provides redundancy in processing; and developing one technique after finishing the other facilitates the validation of the process first developing.
- running two techniques in parallel permits a loose approximation of integration,
- they are used to develop quick initial prototypes, while a more time-consuming application is developed.

The stand-alone model cannot be considered a real form of integration; it is only used to compare different AI models in order to learn more about them and about the problems to be solved. The experiments carried out previously in this investigation with ANNs and CBR systems (Refer to Chapters 3 and 4) could be included under this form of integration.

Transformational model

This model is similar to the previous one. The difference is that in the transformational model, the system begins as one type and ends up as the other. Figure 5.5 outlines an example of a transformational model in which an ANN can be transformed into a knowledge-based system or *vice versa*.

For example an artificial neural network can be used to identify trends and relationships among data sets and the results obtained with it could be used to develop a knowledge-based system.

Figure 5.5: Transformational Model

The benefits are that:

- this model may facilitate the implementation of the final system and ultimately it only requires the maintenance of one AI system
- the final development is realised with the most appropriate technology.

Limitations in this model:

- fully automated means of transforming a knowledge-based system into an ANN or *vice versa* are complex to develop,
- significant modification of the system may require a new development effort,
- the finished transformational system is limited operationally to the capabilities of the target technique.

Loose coupling models

This is the first true form of integrating artificial intelligent systems. The application is composed of separate intelligent systems that communicate via data files. This model allows the interaction between systems with very different characteristics. Typical cases of this type are:

- **Pre-processors:** In this case an ANN could serve as a front-end that processes data prior to passing it on to a knowledge-based system. Following the principles of this model an ANN can be used to perform data fusion, to remove errors, to identify objects and to recognise patterns. Then the knowledge-based system can play the main role.

- **Post-processors:** In this case for example, a knowledge-based system can produce an output that is passed via a data file to an ANN. The knowledge-based system can perform data preparation and manipulation, classify inputs, etc. and the ANN can then perform functions such as forecasting, data analysis, monitoring, etc.
- **Co-processors:** This type of integration involves data passing in both directions, allowing interacting and co-operative behaviour between the ANN and the knowledge-based system. Although not very often used, this approach has the potential for solving difficult problems such as incremental data refinement, iterative problem solving and dual decision making.
- **User interfaces:** An ANN can be used, for example, for pattern recognition to increase the flexibility of user interactions with knowledge-based systems.

These types of models are easier to develop than the more integrated intelligent systems.

The limitations of this type of coupling are:

- The file-transfer protocol has a high associated communication cost which increases the operating time.
- The development of separate intelligent systems leads to redundancy of effort.

Tight coupling models

This model is similar to the previous one; however here the information is passed via memory resident data structures rather than external data files. This improves the interactive capabilities of tightly-coupled models in addition to enhancing their performance. The sub-models of this approach are the four mentioned in the previous subsection: pre-processors, post-processors, co-processors and user interfaces. In this type of situation the implementation is more complex and the operation time is smaller than in the previous case.

Fully integrated models

Fully integrated models share data structures and knowledge representations. Communication between different components is accomplished via the dual nature of structures (symbolic and connectionist). Reasoning is accomplished either cooperatively or through a component designated as a controller. Several variations of fully integrated systems exist, for example connectionist knowledge-based systems are one of the most common varieties of this model. They rely on local knowledge representation, as opposed to the distributed representation of most ANN, and reason through spreading activation. Connectionist knowledge-based systems represent relationships between pieces of knowledge, with weighted links between symbolic nodes.

The beneficial properties of this type of integration are:

- the final product is robust,
- there is no redundancy during the development of the system,

The Limitations of this model are:

- the system development is more complex,
- it is difficult to construct tools that automate the construction of this type of systems,
- the validation, verification and maintenance of these systems requires further development.

Each of the three classifications here presented contemplates the hybridisation process for a different point of view. The Computational Intelligence Classification considers the hybridisation of AI models as a way to obtain AI systems that are capable of simulating aspects of Biological Intelligence. The IRIS classification shows how AI systems should be integrated with other computational systems and with the environment and finally the classification proposed by Medsker and Bailey defines five

different ways of combining connectionist and symbolic AI systems from a practical point of view.

5.3 Hybrids containing CBR systems

CBR systems have been successfully used in several domains as shown in Chapter 4, for example: diagnosis, prediction, control and planning. Although there are many successful applications based on just CBR technology, from an analysis of this type of system it appears that CBR systems can be successfully improved, combined or *augmented* (Hunt and Miles, 1994) by other technologies. Although it may be desirable to have models in which the components are as simple and homogeneous as possible, in some cases a hybrid solution may be the best solution.

A hybrid CBR system may have a clearly identifiable reasoning process. This added reasoning process could be embedded in any of the stages that compose the CBR *Life Cycle*. For example the most common approaches to construct hybrid based CBR systems are:

- the CBR can work in parallel with a co-reasoner and a control module activates one or the other, ie: ROUTER (Goel, 1991),
- a co-reasoner can be used as a pre-processor for the CBR system as happens in the PANDA system (Roderman, 1993); and finally,
- a CBR can use the co-reasoner to augment one of its own reasoning processes (Corchado *et al.*, 1998) as previously mentioned.

The last approach is used by the majority of the CBR hybrid systems. Hunt and Miles (1994) have investigated the areas where Artificial Intelligence (AI) approaches (used as co-reasoners by this type of hybrid CBR based systems) are applied (refer to Figure 5.6):

- to define alternative partial solutions,
- in the adaptation stage,
- in the evaluation stage,
- for justification and as a fall back,

- to generate alternative (partial) solutions,
- for specification and for repair, etc.

Figure 5.6: CBR reasoning process along with some of the places in which knowledge-based systems (KBS), neural networks (ANN), Genetic algorithm (GA), Rule Based Systems (RBS), Qualitative reasoning (QR), Fuzzy Systems (FS) and constraint satisfaction problem (CSP) can be built Medsker (1995).

Techniques used to augment the efficiency of CBR hybrids are (Hunt and Miles, 1994):

- rule based reasoning systems,
- (numerical) constraint satisfaction,
- qualitative reasoning,
- genetic algorithms,
- knowledge-based systems,
- artificial neural networks.

Most of the initial work combines CBR systems with rule-based reasoning systems, but the number of applications in which other AI techniques are combined with case-based reasoning systems is increasing continually and quickly as has been reported by Medsker (1995), Sun and Alexandre (1997). Figure 5.6 shows some of the possible ways in which other intelligent technologies can be integrated within the CBR cycle. Following some hybridization possibilities are reviewed.

The following section reviews several possibilities for hybridisation between CBR systems and other AI methodologies:

Knowledge-based systems and case-based reasoning

CBR systems have been used together with knowledge-based systems (KBS) (including rule based reasoning systems) in many different ways. The synergy between both systems is due to the similar applicability of both technologies in problem domains. They are natural alternatives:

- they can be developed as independent stand alone systems for learning about a problem.
- one can be developed to acquire knowledge for implementing the other as the target operational system (transformational model).

Knowledge-based systems are also used to improve some of the stages of the CBR life cycle. Vo and Macchion (1993) use a CBR system to understand knowledge domains for knowledge-based systems to support satellite

development. Risland *et al.* (1993) use knowledge-based systems to improve interaction with the user by making sure that the user's overall goals are reflected in the case retrieval. A good review of this type of hybrid systems can be found in Medsker (1995).

Fuzzy systems and case-based reasoning

The number of hybrids combining these two types of AI systems is still very small. Nevertheless this approach can potentially improve CBR-KBS hybrid systems (Medsker, 1995). Xu (1994) has investigated the use of Fuzzy-CBR hybrids in the area of AIDS prevention. His system uses fuzzy rules to retrieve relevant previous cases. Gui (1993) uses fuzzy rules to evaluate design alternatives that are generated by case-based reasoning systems.

Genetic algorithms and case-based reasoning

Louis, McGraw and Wyckoff (1993) use CBR systems to explain the results of genetic algorithms. Oppacher and Deugo (1991) discuss the ability of genetic algorithms to improve learning in noisy environments and improve the quality of the system. Slotter, Henke and King (1989) used several genetic algorithms to retrieve cases in different CBR systems.

Qualitative reasoning and case-based reasoning

CADET (Navinchadra *et al.*, 1991) is one of the most complex and powerful CBR systems ever implemented. It is a specialised design system for solving hydro-mechanical problems. It uses a case base of previous designs which can realise sub-functions of the desired artifact. The evaluation module is composed of a qualitative reasoner and a constraint checking system.

Constraint satisfaction and case-based reasoning

CADSYN (Maher and Zhang, 1991, 1993) is a structural design system for buildings. It integrates the design of cases with generalised domain knowledge, CADSYN uses a constraint satisfaction engine to transform design cases to match the current situation. Hinrichs and Kolodner (1991, 1992) developed a

CBR system called JULIA for planning meals. The adaptation process uses a constraint satisfaction mechanism to identify and subsequently resolve constraint violations.

5.4 ANN and case-based reasoning

CBR systems are flexible systems capable of using the beneficial properties of other technologies to their advantage; in particular, the interest here is in the advantages of combining CBR and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). During the last decade an increasing number of scientists have been researching into the hybridisation of CBR systems and ANNs. Before reviewing this area it is necessary to clearly define when and where ANN can be used in this context.

ANNs are not especially appropriate for stepwise expert reasoning and their explanation abilities are extremely weak. Nevertheless their learning and generalisation capabilities can be very useful as was shown in Chapter 3. Therefore they can only be used as part of CBR systems in those areas that do not involve knowledge explanation and reasoning. In particular, they can be used in areas involving knowledge generalisation.

Learning is a powerful feature of most ANNs, and learning forms an intrinsic part of many stages of the CBR cycle, so ANNs can be used to learn to retrieve the closest case to a particular situation, or in other words to learn to identify the closest distance between several cases. For an ANN it is reasonably easy in most situations to learn new cases and to learn how to generalise (adapt) a case from a pool of cases.

CBR systems and ANNs are complementary techniques, ANNs deal easily (and normally) with numeric data sets whereas CBR systems deal normally with symbolic knowledge. Even when symbolic knowledge can be transformed into numeric knowledge and numeric into symbolic, by doing this there is always the risk of losing accuracy and resolution in the data and hence getting misleading results. Therefore a combination of CBR systems and ANNs may avoid transforming data and therefore gain precision. As mentioned before, generalisation is a useful ability of most ANNs, but in

many cases it is necessary to hold information about special cases, and this is a natural ability of CBR systems.

When CBR systems and ANN are used together, the most common approach (Reategui, 1996) is to hold the cases as a integral part of the ANN because CBR systems can successfully use them in the indexing and retrieval stages. For example, in the hybrid system created by Myllymaki and Tirri (1993), cases are identified as neurons or nodes in the ANN. The CBR system uses Bayesian probabilistic reasoning and is implemented as a connectionist network (also called belief networks), which uses probability propagation to provide the theoretical explanation for the case matching process. Cases are represented as neurons in the middle layer of the ANN in this particular model.

Becker and Jazayeri (1989) have developed a hybrid system focused on design problems, in which cases are represented as neurons in the middle layer of an ANN and case-retrieval is done with a hybrid structure. Thrift (1989) uses an ANN with a back propagation learning algorithm for case filtering; the ANN selects the most relevant cases from the case base depending on some constrains (input to the ANN). GAL (Alpaydin, 1991) is based on a similar architecture, the difference being that GAL uses the prototype-based incremental principle, in which every class of objects is represented by the accumulation of relevant samples of the class and the modification of other class representations. Similar to a nearest-neighbour algorithm, this ANN grows when it learns and shrinks when it forgets because only representative cases are kept.

INSIDE (Lim *et al*, 1991) and ARN2 (Azcarraga *et al*, 1991) are very similar to GAL. In these systems, the neurons of the input layer of the ANN represents attributes, the nodes or neurons of the second layer correspond to prototypes (which are represented by n-dimensional vectors) and the neurons or nodes of the output layer represent classes. Each n-dimensional vector has an area of influence of a determined dimension. During the learning the dimension of the areas of influence of the activated vector (prototype) is reduced if the ANN answer is wrong. Although INSIDE and ARN2 are very similar they

differ in the methods that they use for learning the prototypes and adjusting their areas of influence.

Prototype-Based Indexing System (PBIS) (Malek, 1995) was developed with the aim of improving the performance of the ARN2 model by keeping both prototypical and non-prototypical cases. PBIS has the memory divided to two levels. The first level is the middle layer of the ARN2 ANN and contains prototypical cases. The second level is a flat memory in which similar cases are grouped together in regions. Each region with similar cases is connected to the closest prototype of the same class.

PBIS also contains a region to store boundary cases that fall into uncertain areas. When a new case is presented to the ANN the prototype with the highest output is selected, if only one class is activated. When several classes are activated, the memory zones associated with the activated prototypes are selected and the most similar case is retrieved from these memory zones. If none of the prototypes are activated the system searches for similar cases in the atypical memory area.

Quan *et al.* (1994) have developed an algorithm for neural network based analogical case retrieval. This algorithm has been applied to industrial steam turbine design. Main *et al.* (1996) have investigated the use of fuzzy feature vectors and neural networks as a means of improving the indexing and retrieval steps in case-based reasoning systems.

PATDEX/2 (Richter *et al.*, 1991) is a CBR-ANN hybrid system in which the relationship between the CBR and the ANN is different from the previous models. PATDEX/2 is a fault diagnosis system based on case-based reasoning technology. Cases are symptom vectors and their associated diagnosis. In PATDEX/2, an ANN using a competitive learning algorithm is the core of the retrieval algorithm. The similarity measure is based on a matrix that associates the relevance of every symptom to every possible diagnosis. The weights of this matrix are learned and modified by the ANN: after each diagnosis, the weights of the matrix are updated depending on the success of the diagnosis.

Garcia Lorenzo and Bello Perez (1996) use an ANN as a basis for calculating a measure of similarity between a new problem case and each stored candidate case. The ANN provides a mechanism to retrieve cases using information that in other models would require a parallel architecture. The connection between both case-based and rule-based reasoning mechanisms, and high level connectionist models has been investigated by Sun (1996) in the process of exploring the use of such models for approximate common-sense reasoning.

Agre and Koprinska (1996) propose a different type of relationship between the CBR and the ANN in their hybrid model, which combines a CBR system and a knowledge-based ANN. The CBR is applied only for the correction of the knowledge-based ANN solutions that seems to be wrong. Potential corrections are carried out by matching the current situation against the cases that constitute the knowledge-based ANN training data set. Agree and Koprinska have shown that the performance of knowledge-based ANN (which are concerned with the use of domain knowledge to determine the initial structure of a ANN) can be considerably improved with the use of CBR systems.

Reategui *et al.* (1995, 1996) have been working on several hybrid ANN-CBR models and on general classifications of this type of system. Basically their hybrids are composed of two separate modules: a CBR system and an ANN. Both modules work independently, the reasoning process is interleaved between them and both co-operate via a central control unit. In one of his experiments while the ANN learns general patterns of use and misuse of credit cards, the CBR system keeps track of credit card transactions carried out for a particular card (thus different sets of cases are used by the neural network and the CBR system). The central control mediates answers given by the two separate mechanisms.

In the domain of medical diagnosis, Reategui *et al.* (1996) have used an integrated CBR-ANN approach. The task of the neural network is to generate hypotheses and to guide the CBR mechanism in the search for a similar previous case that supports one of the hypotheses. The model has been used in developing a system for the diagnosis of

congenital heart diseases. The hybrid system is capable of solving problems that cannot be solved by the ANN alone with a sufficient level of accuracy.

Liu and Yan (1997) have explored the use of a fuzzy logic-based ANN in a case-based system for diagnosing symptoms in electronic systems. The aim of the hybrid system is to overcome the problems related to the descriptions of uncertain and ambiguous symptoms.

Lees and Corchado (1997) have also investigated the combination of CBR systems and supervised ANN. They have proposed an agent architecture for oceanographic forecasting in which the CBR agents and the ANN agents complement each other at different stages of the forecast. They have also developed a CBR model in which an ANN automates the adaptation of cases, to solve a forecasting problem with high syntactical (numerical) connotations.

5.5 Summary and conclusions

This chapter has reviewed several classifications of hybrid systems. Such classifications complement each other and approach the hybridisation problem from different points of view. From the purpose of the current research the classification proposed by Medsker and Bailey (1992) is the most interesting because it focuses on practical ways of hybridising connectionist and symbolic AI models. This classification has been used to classify the hybrid systems reviewed in the previous section.

Special attention has been placed on hybrids containing case-based reasoning systems and in particular on those combining CBR systems and artificial neural networks. Table 5.1 presents the hybrid systems containing ANN and CBR systems, which have been reviewed in this investigation; it shows their distinctive characteristic and the type of hybridisation used by them.

The table emphasises the distinctive features of the various systems, for comparison purposes.

Hybrid	Distinctive characteristic	Type of hybridisation
<i>Myllimaki and Tirri (1993)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bayesian probabilities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Symbolic Neural Network. Full Integration.
<i>Becker and Jazayeri (1989)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Applied in a design problem. Data recovery is done by a hybrid structure. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Symbolic Neural Network. Full Integration.
<i>Thrift (1989)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ANN (<i>back-propagation</i>) for case filtering. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Symbolic Neural Network. Full Integration.
<i>GAL Alpaydin (1991)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This model follows the principle of incremental construction of prototypes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Symbolic Neural Network. Full Integration.
<i>INSIDE Lim et al. (1991)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attributes – Prototypes - Classes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Symbolic Neural Network. Full Integration.
<i>ARN2 Azcarraga and Giacometti (1991)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attributes - Prototypes - Classes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Symbolic Neural Network. Full Integration.
<i>PBIS Malek (1995)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maintain both prototypical and non-prototypical cases. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Symbolic Neural Network. Full Integration.
<i>Mao et al. (1994)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ANN - retrieve cases. Applied in the design of stem turbines. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Retrieve(ANN) - CBR. Co-processors.
<i>Main et al. (1996)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ANN - Fuzzy Logic – case recovery. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Retrieve(ANN) - CBR. Co-processors.
<i>PATDEX/2 Richter and Weiss (1991)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ANN - for case recovery Applied in a fault diagnosis application. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Retrieve(ANN) - CBR. Co-processors.
<i>García Lorenzo and Bello Perez (1996)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An ANN plays the role of a similarity metric. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Retrieve(ANN) - CBR. Co-processors.
<i>Agre and Koprinska (1996)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Combines a CBR with a knowledge based ANN (KBANN). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ErrorCorrection(CBR) - KBANN. Co-processor.
<i>Reategui et al. (1996)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ANN learns general patterns of use and misuse of credit cards. CBR control transactions made with credit cards. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ANN- CONTROL-CBR. Co-processor.
<i>Reategui et al. (1996)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ANN creates a hypothesis and guides the recovery phase of the CBR. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Retrieve(ANN) - CBR. Co-processors.
<i>Liu and Yan (1997)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ANN - Fuzzy Logic –Diagnosis of symptoms in electrical systems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-processor.
<i>Corchado et al. (1997)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Oceanographic predictions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ANN-CONTROL- CBR. Co-processor.

Table: 5.1: Summary of hybrid CBR-ANN systems used in forecasting problems. In this Table Retrieve(ANN) indicates that the ANN has been used in the retrieval phase of a CBR system

Table 5.1 shows how each of the hybrid systems have distinctive characteristics that make each of them different from the others. Inspecting the type of hybridisations it can be appreciated that there are two dominant models:

- full integration, in the form of a symbolic artificial neural network,
- a model in which both components of the hybrid system are total or partially coupled.

In the latter case, most of the hybrid systems use an artificial neural network in the retrieval stage of the CBR life cycle. In some systems both coprocessors are controlled by a meta-system and in other cases both coprocessors simply work in parallel doing independent tasks. The developers of the previously mentioned systems critically analyse the advantages and disadvantages of their models; in all the cases the beneficial properties of the hybrids overcome their disadvantages. Studying this classification it is clear that there is a huge scope for investigating the combination of artificial neural networks with case-based reasoning systems. For example, different types of ANN can be used at different stages of the CBR life cycle to solve different problems.

ANNs have been used in the retrieval stage of a CBR system in situations in which there was no prior knowledge from constructing a KNN (K-nearest neighbour) algorithm or a Rule Based System (RBS). Although the use of ANN for retrieving cases has been shown to be successful (Mao *et al.*, 1994; Main *et al.*, 1996), it is not considered good practice if there is knowledge sufficient to build a KNN or a RBS. Also the real time constraints imposed by the nature of some problems must be taken into consideration to define whether or not it is possible to afford the time overhead for the training of the ANN.

Although the creation of neuro-symbolic models requires the existence of prototypical cases and a certain amount of knowledge, almost any CBR system can be represented as a neuro-symbolic system in which the neurons are prototypical cases or rule based systems. The connections between neurons could be defined also by rules.

The following chapter presents a hybrid system in which an artificial neural network is used during the adaptation stage of the life cycle of a CBR system. As will be shown later the strategy is to develop a novel system with the aim of solving a complex problem and developing a hybrid-reasoning model.

Chapter 6

The Hybrid CBR-ANN System

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6.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the hybrid system developed in this investigation. The hybrid system is composed of a *case-based reasoning* system and a *radial basis function artificial neural network*. It is a universal forecasting model. *Universal* in this context means the ability to produce accurate results anywhere in any Ocean at any time. The system is capable of adapting itself in real-time to different oceanographic water masses.

To facilitate the understanding of the model the chapter focusses on the forecasting of the temperature of the water up to 5 km ahead. The concepts presented in this chapter are valid for longer distances; the metrics, dimensions of the vectors and some

algorithms have been adapted for such longer distances as will be shown in following sections.

6.2 Overview of the model

Figure 6.1 shows the top-level relationships between the processes comprising the hybrid CBR system. The cycle of operation is a derivation from the CBR cycle of Aamodt and Plaza (1994), and of Watson and Marir (1994). In Figure 6.1, shadowed boxes (together with the dotted arrows) represent the four steps of a typical CBR life cycle; the arrows labelled with words in italics represent data coming in or out of the Case Base (situated in the centre of the diagram) and the text boxes represent the result obtained after each of the four stages of the cycle. Solid lines indicate data flow and dotted lines show the order in which the processes that take part in the life cycle are executed.

Figure 6.1: CBR skeleton

In the operational environment, oceanographic data (e.g. sea-surface temperature) is recorded in real time by sensors in the vessels; also, satellite pictures are received on a weekly basis. The satellite pictures are stored in a centralised database. A problem case is generated every 2 km using the temperatures recorded by the vessel during the last 40 km and consists of a vector of 40 temperature values, recorded at 1 km intervals. The problem case is used to retrieve the k most closely matching cases from the Case Base. Experiments carried out with data sets recorded in the Atlantic Ocean (cruise AMT 4) shown that 40 km was an appropriate dimension for the problem case (Rees *et al.*, 1997b).

Each of the cases stored in the Case Base is defined by an *Input Vector* (I_1, I_2, \dots, I_{40}) of 40 water temperature values, a Forecast Value F (representing the value of the temperature of the water 5 km ahead of the point at which I_{40} was recorded) and several parameters defining its importance (how many times it has been retrieved, etc.) (refer to section 6.3). Both F and I_k must be recorded by a vessel following a straight line.

The k retrieved cases are adapted by a neural network during the reuse phase to obtain an initial (proposed) forecast. Through the revision process, the proposed solution is adjusted to generate the final forecast using error limits, which are calculated taking into account the accuracy of previous predictions. Learning (retaining) is achieved by storing the proposed forecast, modifying some parameters of the cases (as will be shown in following sections) and storing knowledge (ANN weights and centres) acquired by the ANN after the training and case adaptation.

Whilst Figure 6.1 presents the basic concepts of CBR as a cycle of operations, Figure 6.2 shows the detailed information flow throughout the CBR cycle and in particular how the ANN has been integrated with the CBR operation to form a hybrid forecasting system. Data acquisition (top of Figure 6.2) is through sensors on board the vessel (in real time) and from satellite pictures (which are received weekly). The data is indexed so it can be transformed into cases and stored in the Case Base as required.

Figure 6.2: Hybrid system control flow

To obtain an accurate forecast in the vast and complex ocean it is imperative to use up-to-date satellite data. Fortunately, current technology now enables detailed satellite images of the oceans to be obtained on a weekly basis. The relevant data from these images is appropriately indexed for fast retrieval in a centralised database. Data is also acquired in real time as a vessel moves across the ocean; average sea surface temperatures are recorded every kilometre. Satellite images are used in this particular context because from them can be obtained the temperature of the water of the ocean in the form of thermal vectors as shown in Appendix A. These thermal data vectors can be transformed into cases and stored in the case base (refer to Section 6.5).

During the retrieval phase, the k cases that most closely match the problem case are selected from the case base using k -Nearest Neighbour matching algorithms. These k cases are then used to compute the forecast value of the temperature of the ocean a constant distance ahead of the vessel (refer to section 6.6).

The set of k retrieved cases is used in the reuse phase of the CBR life cycle to train an ANN, the output of which is the Proposed Forecast (see Figure 6.2). The radial basis function ANN is retrained in real time to produce the forecast; during this step the weights and the centres of the ANN, used in the previous prediction, are retrieved from the knowledge base and adapted, based on the new training set. The goal of the ANN is to extract a generalised solution from the k cases (refer to Section 6.7).

In the revise phase the Final Forecast is obtained by modifying the Proposed Forecast taking into account the accuracy of the previous predictions. Each case has associated an average error which is a measure of the average error in the previous predictions for which this case was used to train the ANN. Then the error limits are calculated by averaging the average error of each of the k cases used to train the ANN to produce the current forecast (refer to Section 6.8).

Learning is achieved in two different ways:

- (i) after *retraining the ANN*, by saving the internal structure of the ANN: i.e. the weights and centres. The ANN is continuously retrained and its internal structure is saved after each forecast is done,
- (ii) by modifying some of the constituent parameters of the cases (as will be shown later).

A database records all the forecasts done during the last 5 km and all the cases used to train the ANN to obtain these forecasts. These forecasts are eventually compared with their corresponding real values of the temperature of the water (there is a 5 km lag between the point at which the forecast is made and the point for which the forecast is made). The forecasting errors are then used to modify relevant features of the cases, to prune the case base and to determine error limits, etc. (refer to Section 6.9).

6.3 Case representation

A case represents specific knowledge about a particular situation. A case is created to represent the 'shape' of a set of temperature values (a vector of values) and the most representative characteristics of this vector. Each case is composed of the fields listed in Table 6.1.

A 40 km profile has been empirically found (using representative data sets) to give sufficient resolution to characterise the problem case (and the Input Vector I_k). The parametric features of the different water masses that comprise the various oceans vary substantially, not only geographically, but also seasonally. Because of these variations it is therefore inappropriate to attempt to maintain a case base with cases from all the water masses of the ocean. Furthermore:

- there is also no need to refer to cases representative of all the possible orientations that a vessel can take in a given water mass. Vessels normally proceed in a given predefined direction. So only cases corresponding to that particular orientation are normally required at any one time,

- recall also that the aim is to create a forecasting system which is able to adapt to the changes in the ocean environment, in time and space.

With the above considerations, the strategy adopted was to maintain a centralised data base in which all the thermal data tracks and satellite pictures, available for all the water masses in the world, could be stored, in a condensed form; and then only retrieve from it (transformed into cases and stored in the case base) the data relevant to a particular geographical location.

Identification	Description
Identification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unique identification: positive integer number (between 0 and 64000).
Input Vector I_k	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A 40 km temperature input profile (I_1, I_2, \dots, I_k, where $k = 40$) representing the temperature of the water between the present position of the vessel and its position 40 km back.
Output Value: F	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a temperature value representing the water temperature 5km ahead of the present position of the vessel.
Source	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data source from which the case was obtained (satellite image or data track). Its acquisition date, time and geographical co-ordinates identify each source. e.g.: SAT1501981030500-4910 i.e. a satellite picture taken on 15th January 1998, at 10:30 the top left corner having latitude 50.00° and longitude -49.10°.
Time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time when recorded. Although giving some redundancy of information, this field helps to ensure fast retrieval.
Date	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Date when the data was recorded (incorporated for the same reasons as for the previous field).
Geographical position	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The geographical co-ordinates of the location where the value I_{40} (of the Input vector) was recorded.
Retrieval	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The number of times the case has been retrieved to train the ANN (a non-negative integer).
Orientation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An integer x ($1 \leq x \leq 12$) corresponding to the approximate direction of the data track, as indicated in Figure 6.3.
Retrieval time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time when the case was last retrieved.
Retrieval date	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Date when the case was last retrieved.
Retrieval location	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geographical co-ordinates of the location in which the case was last retrieved.
Average error	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The average error in all forecasts for which the case has been used to train the ANN.

Table 6.1: Case attributes

Figure 6.3: Orientation of a case is defined by this figure. This will be assigned a value of 1 in the case of a vessel travelling in the direction from b to a, and a value of 7 if travelling from a to b

Plymouth Marine Laboratory (PML) maintains a database composed of thousands of data profiles recorded during the last decade, together with satellite images. The database is updated weekly. For the purpose of the current research a new database has been constructed for a region of the Atlantic Ocean between the UK and the Falkland Islands (between latitudes: 50 to -52 and longitude: 0 to -60). This database is a subset of the main PML database.

Figure 6.4: Satellite Image and a track obtained from a satellite image. See Appendix A for more detailed pictures and data tracks

6.4 Case indexing mechanism

Time is a very important factor in real time forecasting. Therefore the indexing mechanism used to retrieve both the data stored in the database and the cases in the case base must be fast and reliable. Also the selection mechanism for the creation of cases from data stored in the database must be accurate. Research has also shown in the INRECA project (Wilke and Bergmann, 1996) that very large case bases have poor performance results. Therefore only representative cases must be created and stored. This fact, together with the need for creating them within a small period of time, makes a good indexing algorithm essential.

There are several approaches for organising the information held by a case base. Commonly used approaches are:

- **flat memory system**, that requires a large memory when the case base become large,
- **shared-features network**, that has a hierarchical case organisation (Kolodner, 1993), that requires a rigid network structure, hard to modify once the case base is in use and cases are added into the case base.

The complexity and the quantity of the data with which this system is dealing requires a simple but rigid indexing mechanism in order to minimise the retrieval time of the cases.

The relevant cases to be retrieved are those geographically close to the position of the vessel. The cases stored in the case base at any one time are always geographically close to the position of the vessel. This is enforced by the algorithms in charge of retrieving data from the database and storing it into the case base. These algorithms also give priority to the retrieval of the most recent cases.

Because more refined spatial and temporal selection is required a simple indexing structure has been implemented which groups cases, taking into account their geographical proximity and secondly their temporal proximity. Cases within the same geographical region defined by a square of side 0.1 degrees (10 km) are stored together.

This group is divided again into smaller units, each of which has been recorded in the same week.

6.5 Transformation of data into cases

Cases are constructed from the data held in the database and stored in the case base, according to the rules defined in Table 6.2.

Rule	Description
Rule 1	<p>Cases within an area delimited by a circle of radius P km centred on the present position of the vessel.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">i.e. $P = X + (X * 0.25)$.</p> <p>Where</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • X is the distance between the present position of the vessel and the <i>geographical position</i> of the case with a <i>retrieval</i> field equal to 4 and in which the <i>averaged error</i> is smaller than 0.05 and which has been retrieved within the last 20 km or 24 hours. If there is no case with a retrieval field equal to 4, the one having a value closest to 4 will be chosen. These threshold values have been empirically obtained in experiments carried out with data sets obtained in AMT cruises. • $25 \leq P \leq 200$
Rule 2	Cases with the same orientation as the present cruise track.
Rule 3	Cases from data recorded during the same month as the cases that are stored in the case base in which the forecasting error is less than 0.05 and which have been used during the last 24 hours or 50 km. Cases are also constructed from data recorded in the previous month under the same conditions.
Rule 4	Cases are constructed from data recorded in the last two weeks.

Table 6.2: Rules for case construction

The rules presented in Table 6.2 have been empirically obtained using large numbers of tests carried out on the data set presented in Figure 2.6. The following section shows how cases are selected during the CBR operation to create the final output, how they are deleted from the Case Base and how they can be reused.

6.6 Case retrieval

From the data recorded in real time, the input profile, I , of the problem case is created. A search is made in the case base to retrieve all cases having similar profiles. Five metrics

are used to determine the similarity between the problem case and each of the retrieved cases.

At this stage the aim is to retrieve all the cases that are similar to the problem case. The cases stored in the case base have been extracted from satellite images or data tracks. In the problem under investigation even if the antecedent, I , of different cases are similar the consequent, F , may be completely different. Therefore it is required to recover as many cases similar to the problem case as possible so that in the following stage a forecasting model based on all the recovered cases could be created.

The metrics used in the retrieval process give priority to cases based on complementary criteria. They enable cases to be retrieved whose input profiles are similar to the problem case with respect to their temperature profiles (*Metric 1* and *Metric 2*), general trend in temperature (*Metric 3*), similarity in terms of the frequency of oscillation of the Sobel filter of the profile (*Metric 4*), and similarity with respect to the average sea temperature over the distance represented by the case (*Average Temperature Metric*).

Metric 1

This metric calculates the difference between I_{40} and eight other values of the *Input Profile (of the Problem Case)*, spread along the input profile at 5 km intervals (starting with I_1). This is repeated for all the cases stored in the Case Base. The value of the gradients are weighted, giving a higher value to the ones closer to I_{40} . The weighted gradient of each case (retrieved from the Case Base) is compared with the value of the weighted gradients of the *Input Profile of the Problem Case*, and the absolute value of the differences are added up. The value of Gradient 1 used to retrieve the cases is given by:

$$Metric_1 = \sum_{i=0}^7 (| (I_{40} - I_{i*5+1}) - (IA_{40} - IA_{i*5+1}) | * (84 + i*2) / 100)$$

where the vector I_j , ($j = 1, 2 \dots 40$) represents the input profile of the problem case and IA_j , ($j = 1, 2 \dots 40$) represents the input profile of the case being considered from the case

base. The closer that the profiles being compared match, the smaller will be the value of *Metric 1*. This metric provides a general idea of the degree of similarity between the problem case and all the cases of the memory of the CBR.

Metric 2

This metric is similar to the previous one, the difference is that the input profile is first smoothed using a window of four values. This metric uses the difference between I_{40} and each of thirteen other values of the input profile of the problem case relating to points at 3 km intervals (starting at I_1). The values obtained are weighted and summed as in the calculation of *Metric 1*. This is repeated for all the cases stored in the case base. This metric gives a more general indication of the similarity between the present case and the retrieved cases than *Metric 1*. This metric provides a stronger degree of similarity than the previous one due to its higher level of granularity and the fact that by smoothing the case vector, irrelevant features (such as noise) are eliminated. The smaller the value of the metric, the more similar is the retrieved case to the *Present Input Profile*.

Metric 3

The output of this metric is the absolute value of the difference between the gradient of the *Problem Input Profile* and each of the cases of the case base. The gradient is calculated using the average value from the first and last 20% of each *Input Profile*. A percentage of 20 has been empirically found to be an adequate value to calculate a gradient that defines, in general terms, whether the temperature is increasing or decreasing.

$$Metric_3 = \left| \left(\left(\sum_{i=1}^5 I_{i+35} - \sum_{i=1}^5 I_i \right) / 5 \right) - \left(\left(\sum_{i=1}^5 LA_{i+35} - \sum_{i=1}^5 LA_i \right) / 5 \right) \right|$$

This metric compares the general trend of the problem case with the general trend of the retrieved cases, so for example, it can be identified cases which show a similar general increment or decrement in the temperature.

Metric 4

The *Sobel filter* (Gonzalez and Wintz, 1987) value is calculated for the present case and all the *input profiles* of the retrieved cases. The output of the metric 4 is the absolute value of the difference between the number of oscillations of the Sobel filter of the input profile of the retrieved cases and Problem case.

The value of the Sobel Filter for a case is calculated as follows:

$$(\forall x_i; 3 < i < 38): Sobel_x_i = ((\sum_{j=i-2}^{i+2} x_j) - x_i) / 4$$

This metric gives priority to the cases, which Sobel filter is similar to the Sobel filter of the input vector of the problem case. This metric helps to identify cases from water masses of similar characteristics because case vectors extracted from similar water masses have similar Sobel filters (Corchado *et al.*, 1996).

Average Temperature Metric

The *Average Temperature Metric* compares the average temperature, over the distance represented by each retrieved case, with that of the problem case. This case is used to identify cases that have been extracted from the sea in similar seasons of the year and similar water masses because cases extracted from the same areas of the ocean and extracted during the same season have similar average temperatures.

After applying the above metrics to all the cases in the Case Base, the best matches to the problem case are used to obtain the final forecast. The best matches of each metric will be used to train a Radial Basis Function ANN in the adaptation stage of the Reuse phase. The number of best matches selected from the outcome of each metric is determined as follows:

1. For each metric, the value of the outcome is expressed on absolute scale between 0 and 1. Thus the cases, which are more similar to the problem case, will have a value closer to 0 and the more distant cases will have a value closer to 1.
2. For each metric, the two hundred best matches are used in the adaptation phase of the CBR cycle to train the ANN. If the value of the metric associated with any of these 200 cases is bigger than 3 times the value of the best match, this case is not used in the training of the ANN.

A reasonable number k of cases is required to train the ANN; empirically it has been observed that a value of between 500 and 1000 produces satisfactory results. If k is greater than 1000 it becomes impossible to train the ANN in the time available, whilst a value smaller than 500 may restrict the ANN's generalisation ability. The same cases may be selected using different metrics, and will have a higher influence during the adaptation step of the reuse phase.

The metrics presented above are only applied to the cases which have a *date* field equal to or within 2 weeks of the *date* field of any of the cases used to train the ANN in the most recent forecast, or for which the geographical position differs by less than 10 km to the geographical position of any of the cases used to train the ANN in the most recent forecast.

6.7 Case reuse (adaptation)

Several hybrid systems have been developed in which CBR components co-operate with one or more reasoning elements (Hunt, *et al*). In particular, there are a number of CBR systems that use Constraint Satisfaction, Numeric Constraint Satisfaction, Model Based Reasoning, etc., for case adaptation.

Case adaptation is one of the most problematic aspects of the CBR cycle. Most adaptation techniques are based on generalisation and refinement heuristics. This section proposes a novel approach based on ANNs and their ability to generalise. The

ANN acts as a function that obtains the most representative solution from a number of cases. This ANN does not require any type of human intervention and has only a small number of rules that supervise the training of the ANN.

Aamodt and Plaza (1994) describe the main type of CBR methods, which differ in the way that they retrieve, adapt, utilise and index the knowledge retained in past cases. Each of those methods are more appropriate for a particular type of problem. Aamodt and Plaza differentiate between exemplar-based reasoning, instance-based reasoning, memory-based reasoning, typical case-based reasoning and analogy-based reasoning. For the current problem, the approach is closer to an instance-based reasoning than to any other method.

In the context of the present problem, instance-based reasoning (Aha *et al.*, 1991) is required to compensate for the lack of guidance from specific and accurate background knowledge about the propagation of the temperature of the water of the oceans, with a relatively large number of instances. This is a highly syntactic CBR-approach, in the sense that a simple feature vector (refer to Section 6.3) is only needed to represent each instance and no user is required in the CBR life cycle.

Each of the cases or instances retrieved from the CBR represents a particular problem and its solution (feature vector). The aim of the CBR operation is to determine which of the cases stored in the CBR case base characterises better the present situation so that it may be reused. The determination of an algorithm to automate this process and retrieve the best case at any point is difficult because of the complexity of the environment, its dynamism and its heterogeneity.

The method adopted is to use a mechanism able to absorb the knowledge of all the cases that are representative of one particular problem and extrapolate from them a solution. To this end, experiments were carried out with nearest neighbour algorithms (which find the case among the retrieved cases that is most similar to the present problem), averaging techniques and artificial neural networks. A Radial Basis Function ANN has

been found to be able to absorb the underlying model represented by the retrieved cases and generalise a solution from them, better than any other technique (Corchado *et al.*, 1997d). This ANN is retrained before any forecast is made using the retrieved cases and the internal knowledge (weights and centres) of the Radial Basis Function ANN. Every time that the ANN is retrained, its internal architecture is adapted to the new problem and the cases are adapted to produce the solution, which is a generalisation of those cases.

Radial Basis Function ANNs are adequate in this problem because they can be trained fast, they have very good generalising abilities (though being better at interpolating than at extrapolating) (Fyfe, 1996), and they learn without forgetting by adapting their internal structure (adding new centres) (Fritzke, 1994). This last property is particularly interesting in the present situation because since the ANN is continuously being retrained, it can learn new features within one particular water mass without forgetting a number of the others previously learned (for a variable number of training iterations).

Although this increases the training time, it improves the generalisation since at any time the forecast is not only based on the last k cases used to retrain the ANN, but also on those cases used in the more recent past which also influence the forecast; this contributes to the generation of a continuous, coherent and accurate forecast.

In the RBF network that has been built (refer to section 3.6), cases are coded in order to create the input and output vectors used to train the ANN. The ANN uses 9 input neurons, between 20 and 35 neurons in the hidden layer and 1 neuron in the output layer. The input data is the difference between the last temperature (of the *Input Profile*) and the temperature values of the input profile taken every 4 km. Only one neuron is used in the output layer to forecast up to 5 km. The output is the difference between the temperature at the present point and the temperature 5 km ahead.

6.7.1 Centre and weight adaptation

Initially, 20 vectors are randomly chosen from the first training data set (composed of the retrieved cases), and are used as centres in the middle layer of the ANN. This number changes with training and the training data set determines it. The topology of the ANN (i.e.: number of neurones in each layer) have been empirically chosen after many tests with data sets extracted in the AMT cruises (Corchado *et al.*, 1996a). The number of initial centres has been chosen taking into consideration the number of neurons in the input and the output layer.

All the centres are associated with a Gaussian function the width of which, for all the functions, is set to the mean value of the Euclidean distance between the two centres that are separated the most from each other.

The closest centre to each particular input vector is moved toward the input vector by a percentage α of the present distance between them. By using this technique the centres are positioned close to the highest densities of the input vector data set. The aim of this adaptation is to force the centres to be as close as possible to as many vectors from the input space as possible. An adaptation of this type is particularly important because of the high-dimensionality of the input layer. α is initialised to 20 every time that the ANN is retrained, and its value is linearly decreased with the number of iterations until α becomes 0; then the ANN is trained for a number of iterations (between 10 and 30 iterations for the whole training data set, depending on the time left for the training) in order to obtain the best possible weights for the final value of the centres. The thresholds that determine the centres and weights adaptation have been empirically determined).

The delta rule (Bishop, 1995) is used to adapt the weighted connections from the centres to the output neurons. In particular, for each presented pair of input and desired output vectors, one adaptation step, according to the delta rule, is made.

6.7.2 Insertion of new units

A new centre is inserted into the network when the average error in the training data set does not fall more than 10% after 10 iterations (of the whole training set). In order to determine the most distant centre C , the Euclidean distance between each centre and each input vector is calculated and the centre whose distance from the input data vectors is largest is chosen. A new centre is inserted between C and the centre closest to it. Centres are also eliminated when they do not contribute much to the output of the ANN. Thus, a neuron is eliminated if the absolute value of the weight associated with a neuron is smaller than 20% of the average value of the absolute value, of the 5 smallest weights. The number of neurons in the middle layer is maintained above 20. This is a simple and efficient way of reducing the size of the ANN without dramatically decreasing its memory.

6.7.3 Termination of training

The ANN is trained for a maximum time of 2 minutes in a Sun Sparc Workstation. In the real time operation the ANNs must produce a forecast every 2 km (6 minutes for a speed of 12 knots, which is the maximum speed that the vessel can attain). After that time the new set of training cases is retrieved and the ANNs are retrained. Therefore, even if the error is high the ANNs should produce a forecast. It has been found empirically, that these training times are sufficient to train the network and obtain a forecast with small errors (refer to Chapter 7). At any point if the average error in the training data set is smaller or equal to 0.02 the training is stopped to prevent the ANN from memorising the training vectors. This threshold has been chosen empirically. It has been shown that the ANN around this point stops the generalisation process and starts to learn and to memorise the training vectors.

6.8 Case revision

After case adaptation a crisp value is obtained for the forecasted temperature 5 km ahead of the vessel. This value is rarely 100% accurate, therefore revision is required to obtain a more realistic output.

Since this is a real time problem it is not possible to evaluate the outcome of the system before it is used. The solution to this problem is to define error limits, which will substitute the crisp output with a band or error interval around the output of the ANN. If the error limits are too wide the forecast will be meaningless; therefore a trade off is made between a broad error limit (that will guarantee that the real solution is always within its bands) and the crisp solution.

The expected accuracy of a prediction depends on two elements: the water mass in which the forecast is required and the relevance of the cases stored in the case base for that particular prediction. For example, as can be seen in Figure 2.6, between the 6000 km and 7000 km positions (equatorial waters), the temperature of the water is more stable than in the region between the 9000 km and 10000 km positions (near the Falklands Islands). Therefore the prediction around the equator must have a smaller error interval than around the Falkland Islands.

Each water mass has been assigned a default error limit CL_0 , which has been empirically obtained. Every time a cruise crosses a water mass, a new error limit CL_z (where $0 < z < 6$) is calculated by averaging the error in all the predictions made. If, for a certain water mass, z is equal to 5, and a vessel crosses it again, the older CL is substituted by a new one. Therefore there are at most 5 error limits associated to a water mass. This number is not critical, a smaller value can also guaranty stability in such error limits, and a larger number does not provide a better result. The CL_z error limits are used in collaboration with the *average error* of the cases used to train the ANN for a given forecast. The error limit determines the interval centred in the crisp temperature value, obtained by the ANN, for which there is a high probability that the forecast is within this interval. The value of the probability varies deepening on the distance of the forecast, but must be higher than 90%. Then, if the output of the ANN is F , the average value of the accumulated errors of the cases taking part in a given forecast is AE and ACL is the average value of the CL_z error limits, the error interval is defined by

$$[F - ((AE*0.65)+(ACL*0.35)), F + ((AE*0.65)+(ACL*0.35))]$$

The values used in this formula have been empirically obtained using a sufficient amount of data from all the water masses of the Atlantic Ocean. However, these values may not be appropriate for water masses from different oceans.

6.9 Case retention and learning

Incorporating into the case base what has been learned from the new prediction is the last stage of the CBR life cycle (Leake D. B. and Wilson D. C., 1998). Learning is achieved in different ways in the system. When the ship has travelled a distance of 5 km (on a straight course) after making a forecast, it is possible to determine the accuracy of that forecast, since the actual value of the parameter for which the forecast was made is then known. This forecasting error is used to update the average error attribute of the cases used in that particular forecast. The cumulative error field of the cases used to train the neural network is continuously being updated and contributes to the learning strategy of the system. Accurate error limits are obtained only if the average error attribute of the cases is modified in this way.

Pruning the case base also contributes to the learning; cases in which average error attribute is very high are removed. The maximum permissible average error needs to be defined. Empirically it has been found that for cases in which the average error attains a value 0.12, the average error never subsequently reduces to a value smaller than 0.05. Therefore a threshold of 0.1 in the *average error* was chosen to determine which cases must be deleted. If the average error of a case is equal to or higher than 0.1, the case is removed from the case base. Furthermore, cases which have not been used during the previous 48 hours are deleted; so also are cases which have not been used in the previous 100 km.

It is necessary to determine when the case base must be updated with additional cases from the database. This is done when the database receives new satellite images (once per week). If the forecasting error is higher than 0.2 for more than 20 predictions, additional cases are created from data stored in the database. This is a measure used to include fresh cases in the case base; this helps to reduce the forecasting error.

If, over a period of operation in a particular water mass, it is found that most of the cases selected from the case base are clustered around some point a distance x , say, either ahead or behind the vessel, this suggests that the whole water mass has moved this distance x since the data, from which the cases were created. In such a situation, the operational strategy is then to utilise cases relating to this indicated area, which is centred on a position a distance x from the current position.

The modification and storage of the internal structure of the ANN contribute substantially to the learning of the system. The weights and centres of the network, and also the width of the Gaussian functions associated with the centres, are modified during the adaptation process and stored in the network knowledge base.

Learning is a continuous process in which the neural network acts as a mechanism that generalises from the input data profiles and learns to identify new patterns without forgetting previously learned ones. The case base may be considered as a *long term memory* since it is able to maintain a huge number of cases that characterise previously encountered situations.

In contrast, the network knowledge base may be considered to behave as a *short term memory* that has the ability to recognise recently learned patterns (i.e. the knowledge stored in the internal architecture of the neural network) that enable it to adapt the system to cope with localised situations.

6.10 Summary

This chapter has described the hybrid system developed to forecast in real-time the temperature of the water ahead of an ongoing vessel. The hybrid system is composed of a CBR system and an ANN. The ANN assists the CBR system during the adaptation of cases and also contributes to the learning of the system.

The hybrid system holds in its memory a huge amount data relating to forecasting events and selects from it those that are the most similar to the new forecasting situation. The

ANN uses the retrieved cases to create a model, in real time, for a particular water mass. This reasoning model makes use of the most up-to-date data to generate a solution in real-time in order to overcome the difficulties of predicting the evolution of a dynamic system in real time.

Although the present chapter has focused on the prediction of the temperature 5 km ahead, the same strategy has been used to forecast up to 20 km. The results obtained with this reasoning model are presented and discussed in Chapter 7.

Appendix B presents the architecture that has been developed to enable the testing of the model. The developed multi-agent system has been implemented at the Plymouth Marine Laboratory (PML) and successfully tested during the AMT 5 cruise.

Chapter 7

Results obtained with the Hybrid CBR-ANN approach

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7.1 Introduction

The aim of the research is to develop a system capable of forecasting the temperature of the water with the smallest possible error and with a percentage of inadmissible predictions smaller than 10% (refer to Sections 3.9 and 7.3 for a definition of inadmissible prediction). The hybrid system presented in the previous chapter is capable of forecasting the temperature of the water up to 20 km ahead.

This chapter presents the results obtained with the hybrid CBR-ANN approach presented in the previous chapter. These results are compared with the ones obtained using the statistical and artificial intelligence methods presented in Chapters 3 and 4. Only a small proportion of the results from the total number of experiments performed during the course of the investigation is shown here. It is believed that these results display the capabilities of the new model, and explicitly show that the hybrid system provides more accurate results than any of the other models used and studied during the investigation.

The experiments have been performed in real time during the AMT 5 cruise (refer to Section 2.5.1) and subsequently used the data recorded throughout the cruise and

presented in Figure 2.6. The results obtained by the hybrid model when forecasting 5 km ahead are presented first. Following this, the forecasted results at longer distances are presented and summarised. Finally these results are compared with those obtained using the techniques presented in Chapters 3 and 4.

The hybrid system has been implemented using an autonomous multi-agent system architecture. This system has been implemented in C (ASCII) and Oracle 7.2. C. Sun SuperSPARK II (STP1021) workstations and Novell networks have been used as the basic hardware component. The communication between the vessels and the centralised system has been done via satellite communication systems.

7.2 Predictions 5 km ahead

The predictions obtained with the hybrid CBR-ANN model are more accurate than the ones obtained by the other techniques investigated from both a qualitative and a quantitative point of view. As will be shown in the following sections, the system provides accurate predictions in areas where other methods are not even able to forecast whether the temperature of the water is going to increase or decrease. Figure 7.1 shows the results obtained for the absolute value of the error when forecasting the temperature of the water 5 km ahead during the AMT5 cruise.

Figure 7.1: Absolute value of the error using the Hybrid System

The average error of the forecast is $0.020\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Only in 4.51% of the predictions is the forecasting error higher than $0.05\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; in 8.33% of the predictions it is higher than $0.04\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and in 32.12% of the predictions it is higher than $0.020\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. These figures indicate that the hybrid system is capable of producing a forecast with an average error of $0.020\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and with a probability of 95.49% that the error in the forecast is smaller than $0.05\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Although the test has been done with a limited data set (11000 km between the latitudes 50° North and 50° South), 11 water masses, with different characteristics have been crossed; 6 of those were oceanographic fronts, and in particular, near the Falkland Islands are located several of the most dynamic oceanographic areas in the world. For this reason it is believed that this test is significant enough to extrapolate these results to the whole Atlantic Ocean (Robins, 1996).

Figure 7.1 shows the absolute value of the difference between the real value of the temperature of the water and the crisp value obtained from the RBF neural network output, used for case adaptation by the hybrid system. This graph does not take into account the improvement obtained using error limits during the review phase of the CBR life cycle. Figure 7.2 shows the value of the error limits and Figure 7.3 the error in the forecast outside those error limits.

Figure 7.2: Value of the error limit using the hybrid system

The use of error limits improves substantially the quality of the forecast, its significance and its accuracy. Although 45.52% of the predictions were outside the limits of the error band, only 3.4% of the predictions were more than $0.005\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ outside the error limits. The

average error (average error over the error limits) of the predictions using error limits is $0.001\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The shape of the confidence limit plot, shown in Figure 7.3, is very similar to the shape of the error plot of the forecast presented in Figure 7.1. This means that the error limits adapt themselves to the changes in the characteristics of the temperature of the different water masses.

Figure 7.3: Absolute value of the error using the hybrid system (outside the error limits)

The average value of the error limits is $0.019\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. In areas where there are radical changes, such as fronts or turbulences as happens between 9500 km and 10500 km position of the time series presented in Figure 2.6, the error limits are wider, but in general the value of the error limits is very stable. For example between the 4500 km and 8000 km points (see Figure 2.6) the value of the error limits is around $0.013\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The stability is due to the fact that this water mass corresponds to the equatorial area, in which the variations in the temperature of the waters are very smooth.

Figure 7.4 shows a partial view of the prediction (including error limits) and the real temperature of the water. Figure 7.4 shows a number of accurate continuous forecasts of the water temperature at 5 km. The predictions are realistic and successfully show the evolution of the temperature of the water mass. Even in areas in which other methods have problems producing successful results the hybrid system is accurate and outlines adequately the evolution of the water mass. Figure 7.5 shows another example of the accuracy of the system.

Figure 7.4: Prediction (error limits) and real temperature of the water over 640 km

Figure 7.5: Prediction (error limits) and real water temperature over 640 km

Table 7.1 summarises the results obtained with the hybrid system during the AMT5 cruise. Table 7.1 shows the different average errors when predicting 5 km ahead, in each of the water masses crossed by the vessel on its way from Plymouth to the Falkland Islands.

The table also shows the average error limits, the average error in the forecast outside the error limits, the average number of cases used to train the ANN and the number of centres used by the ANN in the forecast, for each of the water masses.

Water Mass	Average Error (°C)	Averaged error limits (°C)	Average Error (using error limits) °C)	Average Number of Cases used to train the ANN	Average Number of Centres used by the ANN
NA20 (UK shell)	-	-	-	-	-
NA21	0.012	0.011	0.0002	661	38
NA22 (Iberian Front)	0.015	0.015	0.0004	523	32
NA23	0.016	0.016	0.0001	625	46
NA24 (Azores Front)	0.030	0.029	0.0025	672	41
NA25	0.016	0.017	0.0004	626	37
NA26 (Cape Verde Front)	0.009	0.010	0.00006	773	31
EQ27	0.014	0.013	0.0003	632	37
SA28 (Brazil Front)	0.024	0.023	0.0020	790	41
SA29 (Sub-Tropical Front)	0.018	0.019	0.0011	646	33
SA30 (Sub-Antarctic Front)	0.048	0.044	0.0041	678	34
SA31	0.017	0.016	0.0007	617	39

Table 7.1: Summary of the results obtained during the cruise AMT5. These results have been obtained using satellite images recorded in the week previous to that in which the data for which the forecasts were recorded (presented in Figure 2.6)

Both the error and the error limits are, on average, higher in frontal water masses than in homogeneous ones. This was expected due to the higher dynamism and heterogeneity of those areas. Both Table 7.1 and Figure 7.6 show that the three water masses with the highest error limits correspond to three oceanographic fronts. Similarly, it is possible to observe that the water mass with the smallest error limit is also a front. Although it may look contradictory, the high accuracy in the forecast of the Cape Verde front (water mass AN26) is due to its constant slope (see Figure 7.7) and the absence of unexpected changes in the temperature. In situations where recently taken satellite pictures are used to make the prediction and the variation of the water mass slope is constant, the results obtained are very accurate, as the experiments made with data having these characteristics have shown.

Figure 7.6: Average error limits in the water masses crossed by the AMT5 cruise

Figure 7.7: Cape Verde Front

Figure 7.8: Average error in the forecast using the CBR-ANN Hybrid

Table 7.1 shows also that the error in the prediction is smaller in the water masses that do not include oceanographic fronts, with the exception of the water mass AN26, as mentioned before. The complex dynamism of the water masses AN24, AN28, SA29 and SA30 is the reason why the forecasting error is higher in these areas. Nevertheless, the predictions obtained in these areas are very accurate, and in more than 90% of the forecasts the trend in the temperature is accurately outlined. The cases used to train the ANN are integral part to the hybrid forecasting system and were extracted from satellite images of the sea surface during the seven days previous to the date in which the forecast was made.

The success of the hybrid model used is dependent on the following factors:

- the ability of the retrieval mechanisms of the CBR to select the right data to train the ANN,
- the ability of the ANN to generalise and memorise cases,
- the ability of the system to adapt to different situations,
- the efficiency of the system,
- the reliability of the data obtained from satellites.

With regard to the last point, it is necessary to mention that the results presented so far have been obtained using data extracted from satellite images recorded in the week previous to the day in which the forecasts were made. Such predictions have been performed in the best possible conditions because:

- the data used to obtain them was obtained shortly before the forecast was performed,
- there was a sufficient number of cases to train the ANN,
- the data needed for the forecast were available to the forecasting system installed in the vessel.

It is possible that any of these three conditions may not occur. In such a situation, the quality of the forecast may suffer. The following section studies how the performance of the system varies using data recorded at different times prior to the forecast.

7.2.1 Forecast using satellite images recorded at different points in time

Figures 7.9, 7.10, 7.11, 7.12 and 7.13 show the results obtained during a simulation using cases in the forecast extracted from satellite images recorded 1, 2, 3, 4 and 52 weeks before the forecast is made. The experiment has been carried out using the data recorded by the vessel (Figure 6.2) during the AMT5 cruise, but using cases obtained from satellite pictures recorded more than one week before the oceanographic data was recorded during the AMT5 cruise.

The satellite images cover the same region as that covered by the AMT5 cruise. The experiment has only been carried out using 25% of the data from each water mass. The reason behind this is that there were available only a limited amount of satellite pictures from which it was possible to extract data to create the cases to train the ANN. Table 7.2 shows the increment in the error using satellite images up to 12 months prior to the date of the forecast.

Figure 7.9: Error limits and average forecasting error of the prediction of the water temperature 5 km ahead using cases extracted from satellite images recorded one week before the forecast is made

Figure 7.10: Error limits and average forecasting error of the prediction of the water temperature 5 km ahead using cases extracted from satellite images recorded between 8 days and 14 days before the forecast is made.

Figure 7.11: Error limits and average forecasting error of the prediction of the water temperature 5 km ahead using cases extracted from satellite images recorded between 15 days and 21 days before the forecast is made

Figure 7.12: Error limits and average forecasting error of the prediction of the water temperature 5 km ahead using cases extracted from satellite images recorded between 22 days and 29 days before the forecast is made

Figure 7.13: Error limits and average forecasting error of the prediction of the water temperature 5 km ahead using cases extracted from satellite images recorded between 52 weeks before the forecast is made.

Table 7.2 and Figures 7.9 to 7.13 show that successful results could be obtained using less recent data. Figure 7.11 is not complete because it was not possible to obtain satellite pictures of the water masses AN21 and AN30 for the required time of the year. Table 7.2 shows how the average error, the average error limits and the average error outside the error limits were found to vary when satellite images of different ages were used.

Time between the day the picture was recorded and the day that the real time data set was recorded (number of weeks)	Average Error (°C)	Error limits (°C)	Average error (outside error limits) (°C)
1	0.020	0.019	0.001
2	0.024	0.025	0.001
3	0.034	0.033	0.002
4	0.048	0.045	0.003
52	0.033	0.031	0.002

Table 7.2: Average error outside the error limits and error limits in the forecast using data extracted from satellite images recorded several weeks in advance of the prediction date

Table 7.2 shows that even using satellite images that are one or even two weeks old, the accuracy of the forecast does not vary too much. The table also shows that using satellite pictures collected exactly one year back the error in the forecast may be similar or smaller than the error obtained using pictures that are three or more weeks old. This is the reason why data up to one year old is kept in the database and in the case base; if for technical reasons (i.e. clouds covering a certain area or problems with telecommunications) recent satellite images cannot be obtained, data recorded one year back can be used by the system and may in fact produce better results than data recorded three or four weeks back. This is due to the annual cycle of most of the water masses. However, such results cannot be guaranteed as there are also other factors that determine the pattern of ocean temperature variations.

7.2.2 Predictions made with cases obtained from cruise tracks

Cases can be extracted or generated from cruise tracks, as mentioned in Chapter 2. The extraction of temperature vectors from data tracks is a mechanical task; its transformation into cases can be more or less complicated depending on the orientation of the desired cases, the amount of cruise tracks, etc. The main difficulty in creating new cases is that in most of the situations there are no cruise tracks that match 100% the present cruise track for which the prediction must be obtained. Interpolating other cruise tracks to create new ones can reduce this problem.

Figure 7.14 shows the results obtained during the forecast of the AMT5 data set (Figure 2.6) using data recorded in cruises carried out before the AMT5. The average error in the forecast of the temperature of the water 5 km ahead of the vessel is 0.028 °C, the average error limit is 0.029 and the average error outside the error limits is 0.002 °C.

The increment in the forecasting error produced by the use of this type of data is primarily due to two factors:

- to create the new cases, it was occasionally necessary to interpolate data tracks that were up to 200 km apart from each other,
- such data sets were collected 7, 13 and 18 months before the AMT5 data set.

Figure 7.14: Results obtained using the AMT5 data set. Forecasting the temperature of the water 5 km ahead of a vessel using data from the Atlantic Ocean recorded in the 2 previous years to the AMT5 data set

The results obtained were satisfactory and representative of the dynamics of the system. This shows that:

- the algorithms used for the data interpolation are accurate,
- the metrics used by the CBR system are able to recover adequate instances of the problem successfully,
- the artificial neural network generalises successfully.

7.2.3 Results obtained when replacing the RBF by a k-nearest neighbour metric

Figure 7.15 shows the results obtained by substituting the radial basis function ANN by a k-nearest neighbour metric in the adaptation stage of the CBR cycle. The results have been obtained using cases extracted from satellite images recorded one week before the AMT5 data for which the forecast is done. An error of 0.003 °C has been obtained for an error limit of 0.030 °C, in forecasting of the temperature of the water 5 km ahead. The optimum values of k have been selected using data from previous AMT cruises and also from historical data (Benediktsson *et al.*, 1990, 1993).

Figure 7.15: Results obtained using the AMT5 data set, forecasting the temperature of the water 5 km ahead of a vessel using a KNN algorithm rather than a ANN.

If these results are compared with the ones obtained with the use of the ANN and presented in Table 7.3 it can be observed that the forecasting error has been tripled and the value of the error limits has been increased 50%. Using KNN methods the error in the forecast also grows with the length for which the forecast must be done and when the cases used by the system have been extracted from older satellite images. For example the average error in the forecast of the temperature of the water 5 km ahead obtained with cases generated from satellite pictures recorded 4 weeks before the data (AMT5) for which the forecast is performed is 0.006 for a error limit of 0.073. Although the average error increases, the major problem of the substitution of the RBF ANN by the KNN algorithm is that the forecasts are very irregular and in the best of the situations (using data from the previous week and forecasting 5 km ahead) the number of inaccurate cases is 32% while up to 15% of cases are completely erroneous. In some cases errors were obtained of up to 0.6 °C in situations in which the hybrid system with the RBF was producing errors of 0.3°C. This method increases the standard deviation of the error by between 200 % and 280%, depending on the water mass.

7.3 Forecasting over longer distances

The experiments presented so far have focused on forecasting the temperature of the water 5 km ahead. This section shows the results obtained using the hybrid system in forecasting over longer distances. Table 7.3 presents the results of the experiments performed to determine the longest distance up to which this model can be used to predict the temperature of the water. For this experiment satellite data recorded during the previous week to the week in which was recorded the data used to generate the forecast has been used (AMT5 data set presented in Figure 2.6).

Table 7.3 shows the average error in the forecast over different distances, the error limits, the average error taking into account the error limits, the percentage of inadmissible predictions, the standard deviation of the error and the value of I_k , (the length of the vector used to generate the forecast).

To forecast the temperature of the water 5 km ahead a 40 km vector corresponding to the temperature of the water collected during the 40 km previous to the point in which the prediction is made, has been used and averaged at intervals of one km. The size of this vector is related to the forecasting distance. The size of the vector for each forecasting distance has been optimised empirically taking into consideration the following points:

- the vector must be long enough to accurately characterise a situation,
- the smaller the vector, the faster the forecast could be re-established after a change in the vessel's direction
- the smaller the vector, the smaller the dimension (i.e. the number of neurons) of the ANN used for the case adaptation needs to be.

Distance (km)	Average Error (°C)	Error limits (°C)	Average Error using error limits (°C)	% of Inadmissible forecasts	Standard Deviation (°C)	l_k
5	0.020	0.019	0.001	2.6	0.087	40
10	0.048	0.041	0.012	6.2	0.126	51
15	0.132	0.110	0.060	8.1	0.139	59
20	0.260	0.240	0.117	7.5	0.162	65
25	0.380	0.410	0.260	19.1	0.248	72

Table 7.3: Results obtained using cases extracted from satellite images recorded during the week before to the day on which the data for which the forecast must be obtained was recorded

The values presented in column 7 of Table 7.3 have been empirically calculated using historical data recorded during the cruises AMT2, AMT3 and AMT4. It is easy to appreciate that both the value of the forecasting error and the value of the error limits grow with the distance. Column 5 of Table 7.3 shows the percentage of inadmissible predictions obtained during the experiments.

A prediction is inadmissible when it indicates that the temperature of the water is increasing when in fact it is decreasing or *vice-versa*. The goal of the system is to obtain a forecast with a small error in the prediction and with the smallest possible number of inadmissible predictions. Table 7.3 shows that there is a big gap between the results obtained forecasting 20 km and 25 km ahead. This gap is much bigger than the one existing between any two consecutive rows of the table.

The biggest difference is observed in the fifth column, in which the percentage of inadmissible predictions jumps from 7% to 19%. Experts recommend a percentage of successful predictions higher than 90% (Rees *et al.*, 1996). Therefore 19% is a too high percentage of inadmissible predictions.

The value of the standard deviation is also very high when forecasting 25 km ahead. For this reason, and having taken into consideration the results presented in Table 7.3 it can be concluded that using cases extracted from satellite images that are one week old, the

hybrid system can successfully forecast the temperature of the water 20 km straight ahead. The errors presented in Table 7.3 increase if cases are extracted from older satellite pictures or cruise tracks.

Tables 7.4, 7.5, 7.6, 7.7 and 7.9 show the average error in the forecast at different distances, the error limits, the average error taking into account the error limits, the percentage of inadmissible predictions, the standard deviation of the error and the value of I_k , (the length of the vector used to generate the forecast). In the experiment 35% of the data recorded during the AMT5 cruise has been used. Again the reason for this is the availability of data.

Distance (Km)	Average Error (°C)	Error limits (°C)	Average Error using error limits (°C)	% of inadmissible forecasts	Standard Deviation (°C)	I_k
5	0.024	0.025	0.002	3.2	0.084	40
10	0.047	0.044	0.021	5.6	0.138	51
15	0.159	0.143	0.072	7.9	0.151	59
20	0.313	0.291	0.101	8.1	0.178	65
25	0.428	0.432	0.218	21.2	0.237	72

Table 7.4: Results obtained using cases extracted from satellite images recorded during two weeks before the day on which the data for which the forecast must be obtained was recorded

Distance (Km)	Average Error (°C)	Error limits (°C)	Average Error using error limits (°C)	% of inadmissible forecasts	Standard Deviation (°C)	I_k
5	0.034	0.033	0.002	3.1	0.096	40
10	0.060	0.071	0.026	7.1	0.116	51
15	0.184	0.196	0.042	10.9	0.210	59
20	0.360	0.348	0.131	12.8	0.263	65

Table 7.5: Results obtained using cases extracted from satellite images recorded during three weeks before the day on which the data for which the forecast must be obtained was recorded

Distance (Km)	Average Error (°C)	Error limits (°C)	Average Error using error limits (°C)	% of inadmissible forecasts	Standard Deviation (°C)	l_k
5	0.048	0.045	0.003	6.2	0.092	40
10	0.071	0.061	0.044	9.8	0.172	51
15	0.216	0.220	0.076	14.6	0.231	59
20	0.490	0.516	0.134	16.9	0.296	65

Table 7.6: Results obtained using cases extracted from satellite images recorded during four weeks before the day on which the data for which the forecast must be obtained was recorded

Distance (Km)	Average Error (°C)	Error limits (°C)	Average Error using error limits (°C)	% of inadmissible forecasts	Standard Deviation (°C)	l_k
5	0.033	0.031	0.002	4.1	0.106	40
10	0.058	0.061	0.021	4.7	0.120	51
15	0.193	0.184	0.052	9.6	0.174	59
20	0.370	0.362	0.152	13.2	0.240	65

Table 7.7: Results obtained using cases extracted from satellite images recorded during 52 weeks before the day on which the data for which the forecast must be obtained was recorded

Distance (Km)	Average Error (°C)	Error limits (°C)	Average Error using error limits (°C)	% of inadmissible forecasts	Standard Deviation (°C)	l_k
5	0.028	0.029	0.002	3.7	0.098	40
10	0.110	0.102	0.064	8.2	0.116	51
15	0.298	0.316	0.098	16.9	0.181	59
20	0.521	0.532	0.159	32.1	0.32	65

Table 7.8: Results obtained using cases extracted from satellite images recorded during previous cruises.

The tables previously presented show that only by using cases extracted from satellite images that are one week old, it is possible to guarantee that less than 10% of the predictions are unacceptable when forecasting 20 km ahead. The use of other type of

data only guarantees acceptable results in the forecast at up to 10 km. The rows for which the results of the forecast are successful are highlighted in the previous tables.

7.4 Comparison with results obtained by other techniques

Chapter 3 and 4 presented several artificial neural networks and CBR systems as well as the results obtained with them while forecasting the temperature of the water at several distances ahead. Table 7.9 shows a summary of the results obtained using these techniques.

Prediction Distance (km)	Forecasting Method						
	FIR4*4 (°C)	FIR8*5 (°C)	RBF (°C)	Linear regression (°C)	ARIMA (°C)	Specialised RBF (°C)	CBR (°C)
5	0.099	0.096	0.114	0.174	0.129	0.034	0.12
10	0.206	0.192	0.226	0.275	0.231	0.076	-
15	0.343	0.324	0.351	0.429	0.372	0.144	-
20	0.468	0.435	0.469	0.529	0.471	0.223	-

Table 7.9: Summary of the average error obtained with several methods when forecasting the temperature of the water at several distances ahead of the vessel

Although the specialised RBF provides the best results, as shown in Chapter 3 (section 3.6.5) this method is not appropriate for the construction of a universal system. The use of this ANN requires the construction of a different ANN for each water mass and this is an unrealistic possibility. As shown in Table 7.9 the ANN FIR 8*5 produces the smallest errors (without taking into account the specialised RBF).

If those results are compared with the ones obtained by the hybrid CBR-ANN system it is seen that the hybrid model provides smaller errors in the forecast of the water temperature at different distances. Table 7.10 shows the average errors and the percentage of successful predictions obtained by the hybrid system and the FIR 8*5 ANN.

Prediction Distance (km)	FIR8*5 Average error (°C)	FIR: % of inadmissible predictions	Hybrid system Average error (°C)	Average error. Hybrid system considering error limits. (°C)	Hybrid system: % of inadmissible predictions
5	0.096	7.9	0.020	0.001	2.6
10	0.192	14.5	0.048	0.012	6.2
15	0.324	27.9	0.132	0.060	8.1
20	0.435	35.9	0.260	0.117	7.5

Table 7.10: Summary of the average errors and percentage of inadmissible predictions using the FIR 8*5 ANN and the hybrid system

The previous tables show that the hybrid system method is more accurate than any other technique studied during this research. The experiments have been performed with a representative data set recorded in the Atlantic Ocean between the parallels +50 and -50. Data from all the water masses that a vessel traverses when travelling from the UK to the Falkland Islands have been used. Such water masses have very different characteristics and are representative of the majority of the water masses of the oceans. (Tomczak and Godfrey, 1994).

Taking only into consideration the water mass SA30, in which the error in the forecast is the highest, as shown in the Figures of the section 7.2, the percentage of adequate prediction is:

- 93% when forecasting at 5 km.
- 94% when forecasting at 10 km.
- 92% when forecasting at 15 km.
- 88% when forecasting at 20 km.

These percentages of successful predictions are extremely good taking into consideration that this is one of the most dynamic and unstable areas of the ocean. These results also show that the hybrid AI system is able to adapt itself to the characteristics of the different water masses and that although the value of the forecasting error is related to the magnitude of the changes in the temperature of the water, the percentage of inadmissible predictions is very similar in all the water masses. The hybrid system is

therefore capable of forecasting the tendency of the evolution of the temperature of the water consistently and accurately. Figures 7.16, 7.17, 7.18 and 7.19 present some examples of predictions. These Figures show that the values of the error limits are bigger when the forecasts are made over a longer distance. These figures show a dynamic and unstable area of the North Atlantic Ocean. The figures show how the hybrid system is capable of forecasting successfully in such complex areas.

Figure 7.16: Prediction of the temperature of the water 5 km ahead. The graph presents a section of the data collected during the AMT5 cruise

Figure 7.17: Prediction of the temperature of the water 10 km ahead. The graph presents a section of the data collected during the AMT5 cruise

Figure 7.18: Prediction of the temperature of the water 15 km ahead. The graph presents a section of the data collected during the AMT5 cruise

Figure 7.19: Prediction of the temperature of the water 20 km ahead. The graph presents a section of the data collected during the AMT5 cruise

7.5 Summary and conclusions

This chapter has presented and discussed the results obtained with the hybrid system. These results have been compared with previous results obtained with the ANN, statistical methods and a CBR system. Although some results have been obtained with data sets different from the one presented in Figure 6.2, in all cases representative data sets from different areas of the Atlantic Ocean have been used. These data sets have been selected by expert oceanographers taking into consideration their variety and dynamism.

The hybrid system is capable of forecasting more accurately than any of the other systems because:

- the average forecasting errors produced by the hybrid system are smaller than the errors produced by others such as the ANNs or the CBR system,
- the percentage of inadmissible forecasts is smaller than that provided by other methods and under some circumstances is smaller than 10% in the predictions up to 20 km ahead.

Chapter 8

Conclusions

Chapter 8

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8.1 Oceanographic forecasting

Several forecasting models capable of predicting time series with different degrees of accuracy have been presented throughout this thesis. The aim of the research is to develop a universal forecasting system to predict the temperature of the water ahead of an ongoing vessel, in real time. For such a system, the forecasting error and the standard deviation of the error should be as small as possible and the percentage of inadmissible forecast must be smaller than 10%. The system had to be autonomous and be capable of learning from its experiences. Universal here means that the system should provide accurate predictions independently of the time of the year and the geographical position of the vessel from which the forecast is made.

Several artificial neural networks (RBF, MLP, FIR) and statistical models (ARIMA, Linear regressions) were used initially. Although some of these methods provided successful partial results, none of them satisfied all the requirements mentioned above.

The results obtained with the artificial neural networks were better than the ones obtained with the statistical models as shown in Chapter 3. Nevertheless the difference in the quality of the forecast was not significant. For example, the average error in the forecast of the water temperature 5 km ahead, for the data profile presented in Figure 6.2 is:

- 0.096°C using a FIR8*5 model, which is the ANN that produced the smallest average error.
- 0.129°C using the ARIMA model, which is the statistical model that produced the smallest average error.

So the difference in errors is only 0.033°C and experts in oceanography classified both errors as being too high because they are close to 0.1 °C and the percentage of inadmissible prediction in both cases is close to 10%.

Several models based on ANNs with unsupervised learning capabilities and specialised in time series forecasting have been presented throughout this document. After studying and experimenting with several techniques, a finite impulse response ANN was modified and improved to forecast oceanographic thermal time series. Such an ANN satisfied all the requirements specified initially, with the exception that the results obtained with it were not accurate enough. The FIR8*5 ANN provides an average error of 0.96 °C in the forecast for 5 km ahead, 0.192 °C at 10 km, 0.324 °C at 15 km and 0.435 °C at 20 km. This ANN is capable of predicting changes in the evolution of the temperature of the water; nevertheless the predictions are unstable because after announcing a change in the evolution of the temperature, the ANN has problems in stabilising itself. This is the reason the standard deviation of the error and the percentage of inadmissible predictions are too high. Chapter 3 shows the results obtained with this ANN and with several statistical models.

The errors in the forecasts presented above can be reduced by more than 50% with the use of radial basis function ANNs. This reduction in the forecasting error is only obtained if the ANN is trained and tested with data extracted from the same water mass

(see Sections 3.6.6 and 3.8). Therefore the RBF ANN cannot be considered to be a universal forecasting mechanism. However this ANN in combination with other models can be extremely useful because it can learn fast, generalise well and forecast successfully.

The hybrid system developed, based on a case-based reasoning system and a radial basis function ANN, provides a forecasting error between 40% to 80% smaller than the finite impulse ANN (see Section 7.4). The hybrid system is capable of predicting accurately the temperature of the water with a percentage of inadmissible predictions smaller than 10%, as shown in Chapter 7. This forecasting system is capable of producing a forecast with an acceptable degree of accuracy and within the time constraints imposed by the real time nature of the problem. Although the accuracy of the forecast depends, to a great extent, on the quality of the cases and on the actual date when the data from which the cases were created was collected, it has been demonstrated that good quality forecasts may be obtained even with data collected one year before the forecast was made.

The method combines the ability of case-based reasoning to index, organise and retrieve relevant data with the generalisation, learning and adaptation capabilities of the radial basis function neural network. The resulting hybrid system thus combines complementary properties of both connectionist and symbolic AI methods. The neural network plays an important role in the system; it adapts the cases selected by the retrieval algorithms of the CBR, combines aspects of the knowledge contained in several cases and supports the generation of the prediction. The radial basis function network adapts its structure to the characteristics of the environment in which the system is operating and acts as a function that facilitates system learning by extracting the relevant characteristics of a number of closely matching cases and combining them in the form of a representative case.

The experiments carried out on data from the Atlantic Ocean showed that in optimal conditions it is possible to predict the temperature of the water (with a percentage of inadmissible predictions smaller than 10%) at:

- 5 km with a percentage of inadmissible predictions of 2.6% and an average error of 0.020°C
(0.001 °C if the error limits are taken into consideration)
- 10 km with a percentage of inadmissible predictions of 6.2% and an average error of 0.048°C
(0.012 °C if the error limits are taken into consideration)
- 15 km with a percentage of inadmissible predictions of 8.1% and an average error of 0.132°C
(0.060 °C if the error limits are taken into consideration)
- 20 km with a percentage of inadmissible predictions of 7.5% and an average error of 0.260°C
(0.117 °C if the error limits are taken into consideration)

Even if the hybrid system does not use the most recent data sets, accurate prediction can be obtained up to 10 km ahead. The predictions obtained with the hybrid system are very stable. As shown in Section 7.3, the average standard deviation of the error in the forecast at 5 km is between 0.084 °C and 0.106 °C depending on the cases used by the hybrid system. This value is 50% smaller than the value provided by the FIR8*5 ANN and the ARIMA model (see Sections 3.5.2 and 3.7.2).

The implementation of the system has required the development of several programs and the use of powerful computers and telecommunication systems. The final system has been implemented as an autonomous agent-oriented system, which does not require human intervention (refer to Appendix B). This hybrid model is capable of learning from errors and experiences and of adapting to the different water masses and their seasonal variability. Forecasting errors are used to generate the error limits. Therefore it is believed that the final system satisfies the requirements specified at the beginning of the research project.

8.2 Abstraction of the model

The case-based reasoning system has been found to be adequate in organising information and in facilitating a solution to the problem. The reasoning process is based on the recovery and adaptation of the cases stored in the memory that are most similar to the problem to be solved. The CBR mechanism is also involved in the revision of the solution and in the learning from the errors. The case-based reasoning system can be considered a long-term memory capable of remembering situations similar to a given one, using analogies, similar to human beings.

The artificial neural network acts as a short term memory which uses the information recovered by the CBR; what the ANN has learned in the previous instance is used to create a model of the present problem in real-time. The ANN adapts the recovered cases to the present situation and generalises from them to solve the problem.

The hybrid system provides a more accurate forecast than any of the other methods studied in this investigation, as has been shown empirically. The reasoning model used can be applied in situations that satisfy the following conditions:

- each problem can be represented in the form of a vector of quantified values,
- such vectors must have a dimension appropriate to the real time requirements of the system. This is due to the direct relationship between the training time and the dimensionality of the ANN,
- the case-base should be representative of the whole spectrum of the problem,
- updated cases must be provided periodically,
- there must be enough cases to train the ANN.

This thesis has presented a novel reasoning model for predicting time series values using additional information extracted from satellite images. It is believed that the same principle could be used, for example, in financial market forecasting, power loading forecasting and atmospheric forecasting problems.

8.3 Adaptive system

The development of an autonomous agent or a multi-agent system implies the automation of the reasoning model and any of the other modules used by the agent (refer to Appendix B). The reasoning system must be capable of:

- providing accurate answers, within the expected limits,
- differentiating an accurate forecast from a non accurate one,
- learning from errors,
- acting autonomously,
- adapting its structure and information to new situations,
- interacting with the environment, with the users, and, in the case of a multi-agent system, each agent must be capable of interacting with other agents.

The system implemented satisfies these requirements, because it can adapt its memory or case base and the structure of some of its components to the characteristics that describe the behaviour of the environment in which the multi-agent system is embedded. Such adaptation is guided by a number of relatively simple rules that affect the majority of the components of the hybrid system.

The system is composed of several agents (refer to Appendix B) with the ability to interact between themselves, with the environment, and with the users. This is a flexible system in which additional agents can be incorporated, or agents deleted. Each agent depends on the others which, collectively, constitutes a multi-agent system with a high degree of autonomy.

8.4 Possible improvements to the system

The hybrid system, as finally implemented, provides successful results and verifies the initial hypothesis. Nevertheless, there are ways to improve it. This initial system has opened several investigation options that are under study in the Plymouth Marine Laboratory. Some of the options for improving this system are suggested below:

Prediction after changes in the trajectory

The present system forecasts the temperature of the water when the vessel follows a straight line. Therefore to predict after the vessel has changed trajectory, it is necessary to wait until the vessel travels a distance (following a straight line) long enough to record the information used to create the problem case. The vessels normally follow a predefined straight trajectory, at the turning points, the present system does not work effectively. It is believed that this limitation can be reduced or even eliminated if the system incorporates:

- an algorithm to adapt dynamically the length of the problem vector,
- a mechanism to adapt the orientation and shape of the problem vector and the solution vector to the changes in the trajectory of the vessel.

Predictions in two and three dimensions

It could be possible to forecast the temperature of the water in two and three dimensions. In a similar way that the temperature of the water is forecast ahead of the vessel, it could also be forecast laterally, so the temperature of the water could be forecast in two dimensions. To create a three-dimensional model, it would be necessary to extrapolate the previously simulated temperature to the required depths.

8.4.1 Hybrid combinations

Looking at the potential of hybrid systems and in particular at the advantages of combining case-based reasoning systems and artificial neural networks, it is possible to propose areas of improvement. For example it would be interesting to study:

- whether the rules that govern the recovery of cases and the identification of the error limits could be substituted by artificial neural networks (or other AI techniques) that could perform these tasks in an unsupervised manner,
- the ability of artificial neural networks (or other AI techniques) to select which data needs to be transferred from the main memory to the case-base of each forecasting agent,

- the ability of artificial neural networks (or other AI techniques) to define the size of the forecasting vectors that describe the cases, and to determine which variables of the vectors are those most relevant to the prediction.

The number of possibilities for constructing hybrid algorithms is only limited by the human imagination. The characteristics of the problem for which the hybrid system is built must dictate which properties need to be incorporated into the AI hybrid system.

8.5 Final remarks

The success achieved with this investigation has made it possible for the hybrid system presented in this document to constitute the core of the STEB (Rees *et al.*, 1997) system developed in the Plymouth Marine Laboratory. The aim of the STEB project is the development of an oceanographic system capable of simulating the environment in three dimension around an ongoing vessel. Although a hybrid system has been implemented for vessels that navigate on the surface of the water, the same concept can be applied to underwater vessels. The present technology and knowledge of the ocean allow the simulation of the temperature of the water at different depths from knowledge of the temperature at the waters surface.

The work presented in this thesis has been recognised internationally. This work has been presented at and published in the proceedings of more than 20 conferences. It has also been submitted to several international journals.

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Appendix A

Satellite Data Samples

This appendix includes four satellite pictures (Figures A1, A2, A3, A4) of the sea water surface of the Atlantic Ocean located south west of the British Islands. The AVHRR images have been taken at intervals of six months. These images show the dynamism of the temperature of the water.

Figure A5 shows a data track extracted for the Figure A4. This data series has not been processed, and correspond to the vector defined by the coordinates (49° North, 5° West) and (48° North, 15° West). The vertical lines that cross the horizontal axis correspond to areas in which the temperature is unknown. Clouds can cause this.

Figure A6 shows the data track presented in Figure A5 after it been processed. This data set has been processed using several image-processing techniques to eliminate noise and to average the data set. Programs have been developed by the Plymouth Marine Laboratory to automate this process completely.

Figure A1: Processed Satellite Picture. This picture has been obtained on the 5th of May 1997. It shows the temperature of the sea water surface

Figure A2: Processed Satellite Picture. This picture has been obtained on the 1st of September 1996. It shows the temperature of the sea water surface

Figure A3: Processed Satellite Picture. This picture has been obtained on the 25th of May 1997. It shows the temperature of the sea water surface

Figure A4: Processed Satellite Picture. This picture has been obtained on the 14th of September 1997. It shows the temperature of the sea water surface

Figure A5: Thermal data track , extracted from Figure A4 from the vector defined by the coordinates (49° North, 5° West) and (48° North, 15° West)

Figure A6: Processed thermal data track, extracted from the data Track presented in Figure A5

Appendix B

The Implementation: Multi-agent system

B.1 Introduction

This appendix presents a multi-agent based platform developed to implement the AI hybrid system for forecasting the thermal structure of the ocean in real time. The multi-agent system consists of several independent agents, each of them being responsible for different tasks (Riesbeck, 1996). Agents co-operate with each other to learn and exchange information so that their forecast may be more accurate. The system has been successfully tested in the Atlantic Ocean in September 1997.

The implementation of the forecasting model has required the construction of a sophisticated system that is:

- autonomous,
- distributed,
- heterogeneous from the point of view of the software components, since the construction of the system has required the use of different software packages,
- heterogeneous from the point of view the hardware components, since the construction of the system has required the use of different types of hardware components such as PCs, workstations, sensors, networks, etc,
- real time operation,
- experimental.

The Appendix shows the main features of the implemented forecasting system. Technical details have been omitted for the following reasons:

- The fundamental aim of this research project is to develop a forecasting model for working in real time. The reason for building the application is that it is needed to test the AI hybrid model.
- The author of the thesis has designed the autonomous multi-agent system and programmed the main communication system between the sensors that read the temperature of the water in real time and the computer modules that compose the hybrid forecasting model. Mr. N. Rees and his team of programmers at the Plymouth Marine Laboratory have built the rest of the modules of the autonomous multiagent-agent system. The implementation of the system has been realised in C (ASCII) and Oracle 7.2. C and Oracle libraries from the Plymouth Marine Laboratory programming archives have been used. Sun SuperSPARK II (STP1021) machines and a Novell network are used as the basic hardware component. The communication between the vessels and the centralised system is done via satellite communication systems.

The prototype has been designed in the form of a multi-agent system to facilitate its construction. The system presented here is able to forecast the temperature of the water 5 km ahead of a vessel. Agents interact among themselves using message passing protocols, client-server protocol and by sharing information and data.

This Appendix presents a general overview of the multi-agent system first, followed by each of the individual agents of the system. Each agent is sub-divided into the modules that compose it. Finally a evaluation of the agent based system is carried out.

B.2 Multi-agent system

The qualifying attributes of multi-agent systems have been the subject of debates within the Distributed Artificial Intelligence (DAI) community for several years, and in particular the agent research community. Now, there is a huge interest in the creation of software agent systems because they are seen as the means to transform static rule based systems into dynamic adaptive and more human-like reasoning models.

The term agent is widely used by many people working in related areas and it is very difficult to produce a single universally accepted definition. Agents may be partitioned, for example, into static/mobile agents, deliberative/reactive agents, task/resource agents. However the approach presented in this paper is based on that of Michael Wooldridge and Nicholas R. Jennings (Wooldridge and Jennings, 1994), who define an agent from the standpoint of functional characteristics that an agent should possess: autonomy, social ability, reactivity and pro-activeness.

A multi-agent system is a computational system composed of several agents capable of mutual and environmental interaction. Gerhard Weiß (1995) describes the properties that a multi-agent system must possess, which are an extension of the four mentioned above. Multi-agent systems enjoy all the benefits of distributed artificial intelligence, such as robustness, parallelism or scalability. Multi-agent systems allow the interaction of different elements (i.e. autonomous agents) which increases their ability to learn more quickly. Today's technology facilitates the implementation of such systems: fast computers, dedicated software and computing networks are available to us.

Figure B1: Multi-agent architecture

To specify an almost complete multi-agent system it is necessary to determine the internal knowledge and behaviour of each agent and its relation to the outside world and to other agents. In this system there are two types of agents: a unique co-ordination agent and several vessel agents. Figure B1 shows a view of the agents involved in this system and their relationships. The co-ordination agent holds the data used by the vessel agents. As shown in Figure B2, it is composed of several units or semi-independent modules: Data Handler Unit, Registration Unit, Central database, Temporal database and a number of Selector Units, which are the modules in charge of the communication with the Vessel Agents. The vessel agents (Figure B3) are installed in ships and their goal is to forecast the water structure ahead of an ongoing vessel.

B.3 Co-ordinator Agent

Figure B2 shows the modules that compose the co-ordination agent. This agent holds a centralised database with the data tracks and the satellite information that is used by the agents to create the cases for the case based reasoning mechanism (As specified in Section 6.4). These cases are eventually used by the hybrid system to generate a forecast.

Figure B2: Co-ordination Agent

The Co-ordination agent is composed of the following modules:

- Data Handler Unit
- Registration Unit
- Temporal Database
- Central Database
- Several Selector Units

The selection units handle the communication between the Co-ordination agent and the Vessel agents. The Vessel agents are installed in the vessels and they use the forecasting AI hybrid system mentioned in Chapter 6. Figure B3 shows the structure of these agents. Each of the components of the Co-ordination agent is presented below.

B.3.1 Data Handler Unit

The Data Handler Unit manages the data stored in the Central and Temporal databases. It periodically receives satellite images and cruise tracks and stores them in the Databases. The aims of this unit are:

- *Indexing satellite Images:*
 - receiving the Images,
 - determining the quality of the pictures and assigning to each picture a quality value. This value is related to the percentage of the picture uncovered by clouds or noise,
 - associating the picture with the water masses covered by the picture,
 - characterising the picture by
 - identifier (i.e. SAT2009971030500-4910),
 - location (Geographical Co-ordinates that determine the vertices of the image).

- *Indexing cruise' data:*

- receiving cruise data,
- associating the cruise with the water masses that it crosses,
- characterising the cruise by
 - identifier (i.e. CRU2009971030500-4910),
 - geographical Co-ordinates of the cruise trajectory.

- *Indexing Water Masses:*

The ocean waters can be divided into provinces. The water masses that form such provinces have similar bio-geo-optical characteristics. These provinces or water masses can be categorised and the data handler unit processes this information and transfers it to the central database. This information is used by the Central Database to update its indexes and pointers. The attributes associated with each water mass are:

- identifier, i.e. NA23. NA corresponds to North Atlantic,
- name, if any. i.e. Iberian Front,
- position: Co-ordinates of the rectangle in which the water mass is confined,
- rules defining the cyclical change of location of the water mass, if known,
- cruise Identifiers, for all the cruises crossing the water mass,
- satellite Image Identifiers, for all the satellite images of this water mass,
- pointer to the error limits table of the water masses.

- *Selecting:*

The Data Handler unit also selects data (satellite images or cruise tracks) from the Central Database and temporarily stores it in the Temporal Database. When the Vessel agent communicates to its Selector Unit (in the Co-ordination Agent) that data from a

particular water mass is required, the Selector Unit contacts the Data Handler unit, which selects the data from the Central Database and transfers it to the Temporal Database. This data remains in the Temporal Database until it is sent to the Vessel Agent.

B.3.2 Registration Unit

This Unit registers new Vessel Agents. The Vessel Agent is registered in the Registration Unit of the Co-ordination Agent when it is installed on board a vessel. This Unit:

- installs the Selector Unit attached to the corresponding Vessel Agent,
- keeps track of all the Selector Units.

B.3.3 Selector-n Unit

Each of the vessel agents communicates with the Co-ordination Agent via one of the Selector Units “n”. Where “n” is a unique identifier: an integer greater than 0. When a new Vessel agent is installed in a ship, this event is communicated to the Co-ordination Unit via the Registration Unit, which generates a Selector Unit for this Vessel agent. The Selector Unit is the gateway between the Co-ordination agent and the Vessel agent. This Unit:

- is responsible for the communication between the Vessel agents and the Co-ordination agent: it keeps the TCP-IP address of the vessel agent, sends messages, etc,
- contacts directly with the Communication Unit of the Vessel agent,
- receives information of the geographical location of the vessel continuously. This information is used by the Data Handler Unit to retrieve from the Central Database the information that the Vessel agent requires to generate the forecast. Once retrieved this information is sent to the Temporal Database and this is communicated to the Selector Unit. Then the Selector Unit sends it to the Vessel agent.

B.3.4 Central Database

The Central Database stores all the information related to water masses, satellite images and cruise data. It is a relational database which can only be accessed by the Data Handler Unit. It is implemented in Oracle.

B.3.5 Temporal Database

The Temporal Database holds data (satellite pictures and cruise tracks) related to one or more water masses for a short period of time. Once the Data Handler detects that a particular Selector Unit requires data related to one or more water masses, the Data Handler retrieves this data from the Central Database and stores it in the Temporal Database. As soon as this operation is done, this fact is communicated to the Selector Unit. Then the Selector Unit sends the information stored in the Temporal Database to the Vessel Agent as soon as possible.

B.4 Vessel Agent

Vessel Agents are installed in the vessels for which the forecasts are to be made. These agents are manually installed due to their hardware requirements such as sensors, workstations and a communication network. Once they are set up, they automatically register themselves with the Co-ordination Agent via the Registration Unit. Figure B4 shows the units that form part of each of these agents.

The Vessel Agents need updated information of the water mass in which they are located in order to generate an accurate forecast. This information can be obtained directly from the Co-ordination Agent, as mentioned above. A Vessel Agent can use another Vessel Agent as an intermediate step in communicating with the Co-ordination Agent if it cannot contact directly with the Co-ordination Agent, as will be explained later.

Figure B3: Vessel Agent

B.4.1 Communication Unit

This unit is in charge of the communication between the Vessel agent and the Co-ordination agent via the Selector Unit. The Communication Unit periodically sends the geographical position of the Vessel to the Co-ordination Agent. This unit can communicate directly with other vessel agents in order to ask or receive information about their cruise track (in case both vessels follow the same track). Vessel agents inform each other regularly about their geographical location. When the Selector Unit x (where x is an integer between 0 and n) sends the data stored in the Temporal Database

to the Vessel Agent, the Communication Unit is responsible for collecting this information and sending it to the Partial Database.

B.4.2 Data Transformation Unit.

The hybrid forecasting model requires information in the form of cases. This unit transforms the data (satellite images and data tracks) stored in the Partial Database in cases and stores them in the Case Base. The metrics presented in Section 6.5 are used for such transformation. Several applications have been developed to automate the extraction of data vectors from satellite images and to interpolate data tracks.

B.4.3 Data Acquisition Unit.

This Unit reads data from sensors in real time. The temperature is read at 8Hz, filtered using several noise filters and averaged every 1 km. The Data Acquisition unit creates the *input profile* using the data recorded during the last 40 km. This profile is sent to the Forecasting Unit, which uses it to select the cases from which to generate the final forecast. This data is also used to create complete cruise tracks that are stored in the General Knowledge Data unit and eventually sent to the Co-ordination Agent.

B.4.4 General Knowledge Data Unit.

The General Knowledge Unit stores information in its Case Base, Backup Data Base and Partial Database. It also stores information related to the internal structure of the RBF ANN. This information is eventually used to generate the final forecast.

- The Partial Database stores the Satellite Images and the cruise tracks associated with the water mass in which the vessel is currently, at any particular time and to all its neighboring water masses. The Data Transformation Unit transforms this data into cases, which are stored in the Case Base. The cases are stored in the Case Base until the transformation module decides to eliminate them.

- The Backup Database is only used when the Vessel agent *A* asks another Vessel agent *B* to be its gateway to the Co-ordination agent; this only happens if there is a communication problem between the Vessel agent *A* and the Co-ordination agent. In the case of a problem, the Vessel agent *B* retrieves the data from the Co-ordination agent and stores it in its Backup database. Then the Communication Unit of the Vessel agent *B* communicates to the Communication Unit of the Vessel Agent *A* that the data is in its backup database and this data is sent to the Case Base of the Vessel agent *A*.

B.4.5 Forecasting Unit

The forecasting system presented in Chapter 6 is confined to this unit. It is divided into four modules or individual programs. They work in a cyclical sequence.

- The data retrieval sub-module selects cases from the Case Base using several rules that compare the characteristics of the *input profile* (previously obtained from the Data Acquisition Unit) with the cases stored in the Case Base (Refer to Section 6.6).
- The radial basis function ANN is confined inside the Data Reuse sub-module. This ANN takes care of the case adaptation. All the relevant information of the ANN is stored in the General Knowledge Base (i.e.: weights, centres, etc.) (Refer to Section 6.7).
- Once the ANN has produced its output, the data revision sub-module is called. The data revision sub-module generates the error limits and associates them with the output of the ANN (Refer to Section 6.8).
- Finally, the knowledge gained by the ANN is stored in the General Knowledge Base during the data retention phase. This module evaluates the results of the predictions and indicates to the Transformation Unit which

cases must be deleted from the Case Base and when to generate more cases from the data stored in the Partial Database (Refer to Section 6.9).

This loop is repeated every 2 km.

B.4.6 Human Computer Interaction Unit

The purpose of this Unit is to facilitate the interaction between the agents and the users. It presents a number of screens from which the operators can follow the evolution in the temperature of the water, the state of the system and even historical results.

The user can also advance the trajectory of the vessel for the whole trip, so the Vessel agent can contact the Co-ordinator agent and retrieve from it data sets in advance to forecast during the whole cruise. In this case, if new data is received by the Co-ordinator agent, it will be sent to the Vessel agent.

B.5 Assessment of the multi-agent system

Adaptation and learning in multi-agent systems have been recently studied by a number of scientists from the AI community (Weiß *et al.*, 1996). Distributed Artificial Intelligence has been strongly influenced by multi-agent concepts. Multi-agent systems seem to be the follow up to traditional knowledge based systems and the number of scientists applying this new concept to traditional AI is increasing continuously.

Adaptation and learning are two very related topics; in fact most of the research community accepts that adaptation is covered by learning (Weiß *et al.*, 1996). In this respect, adaptation refers to the modifications that enable a system to survive in a changed environment. The multi-agent system, presented in this paper, has the ability to adapt itself and to learn in two different ways:

- Each Vessel agent contains a Forecasting Unit which has incorporated in it a Hybrid Forecasting engine in its structure, able to adapt its prediction to the changes in the environment. The internal structure of the ANN adapts itself to

the changes in the environment and the system successfully selects the information that must be used at each particular point in time.

- Learning is augmented by sharing information and experiences. The ability to share information is indispensable in an agent-based system. Also the capability of Vessel Agents to contact with the Co-ordination agent using another Vessel Agent as a gateway or middle step improves the reliability of the system and its performance.

Communication occurs between the agents, between the agents and the environment and between the agents and the users.

- The thermal sensors and the communication networks allows the multi-agent system to make contact with the environment. The satellite pictures are manually inserted in the database by technicians with the help of several computer applications that have been developed to automate this process. This process could be totally automated with a new agent being responsible for it.
- Users interact with the system via the Human Computer Interaction Unit. The users can visualise the predictions in real time, study historical predictions, perform statistical calculations on the data, etc.

A system similar to the one presented above has been used during the AMT5 cruise. This system only allows forecasts of the temperature of the water 5 km ahead of an ongoing vessel. The system has now been improved to allow for forecasts at different distances in real time.

Appendix C

List of publications

- Corchado J. M. (1995). **Application of Filters, Masks and Artificial Neural Networks to Oceanographic Frontal Warning**. BSc Hons. Project. Computing and Information systems Dept. University of Paisley.
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Appendix D

Glossary of technical terms

<i>ART</i>	Adaptive Resonance Theory
<i>AVHRR</i>	Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer
<i>AI</i>	Artificial Intelligence
<i>ANN</i>	Artificial Neural Network
<i>AMT</i>	Atlantic Meridional Transect
<i>ARIMA</i>	Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average
<i>BAM</i>	Bi-directional Associative Memory
<i>BAS</i>	British Antarctic Survey
<i>CBR</i>	Case-based Reasoning
<i>CBP</i>	Comparison Based Prediction Model
<i>CSP</i>	Constraint satisfaction problem
<i>DRA</i>	Defense Research Agency
<i>FIR</i>	Finite Impulse Response
<i>GDEM</i>	Generalised Digital Environmental Model
<i>IRIS</i>	Integration of reasoning, Informing and Serving
<i>JCR</i>	James Clark Ross
<i>KNN</i>	K-nearest neighbour
<i>KBOS</i>	Knowledge Based Oceanographic System
<i>KBS</i>	Knowledge Based System
<i>MLP</i>	Multi Layer Perceptron
<i>ORKA</i>	On line Real Time knowledge based Analysis

<i>PML</i>	Plymouth Marine Laboratory
<i>PCA</i>	Principal Components Analysis
<i>RBF</i>	Radial Basis Function
<i>RSDAS</i>	Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service
<i>JCR</i>	Royal Research Ship James Clark Ross
<i>SST</i>	Sea Surface Temperature
<i>SOM</i>	Self-Organizing Maps
<i>STEB</i>	Simulated Tactical Environmental Bubble
<i>T-S</i>	Temperature-Salinity relationship